

Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey

Campus Monterrey

School of Engineering and Sciences

**TECNOLOGICO
DE MONTERREY®**

**Automated Design of Population-based Evolutionary Algorithms for
Solving Practical Engineering Problems**

A dissertation presented by

Daniel Fernando Zambrano Gutiérrez

Submitted to the
School of Engineering and Sciences
in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

in

Computer Science

Monterrey, Nuevo León, December, 2025

Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey

Campus Monterrey

The committee members, hereby, certify that have read the dissertation presented by Daniel Fernando Zambrano Gutiérrez and that it is fully adequate in scope and quality as a partial requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Computer Sciences.

Dr. José Carlos Ortiz Bayliss
Tecnológico de Monterrey
Principal Advisor

Dr. Jorge Mario Cruz-Duarte
Université de Lille
Co-Advisor

Dr. Juan Gabriel Avina-Cervantes
University of Guanajuato
Co-Advisor

Dr. Anna Karen Gárate Escamilla
Tecnológico de Monterrey
Committee Member

Dr. Herman Castañeda Cuevas
Tecnológico de Monterrey
Committee Member

Dr. Elisa Virginia Vázquez Lepe
Dean of Graduate Studies
School of Engineering and Sciences

Monterrey, Nuevo León, December, 2025

Dedication

This work is not the end of a journey, but the beginning of a greater one. As a great friend once said: **Here, the story begins.** Each page of this thesis carries the love, patience, and strength of those who walked beside me. To all of you, I dedicate this achievement with heartfelt gratitude.

- To my beloved wife, Grecia Carolina Duque Giménez, whose love, patience, and unwavering support have been the light guiding every step of this journey. Without you, I would never have reached this point. I love you deeply.
- To my parents, Betty Enohemi Gutiérrez Sánchez and José Fernando Zambrano García, for teaching me the true meaning of perseverance, humility, and dedication. Your example has been my greatest lesson and strength.
- To my siblings, María, Yohana, and Jhosep, whose lives and efforts continually inspire me to become a better person every day.
- To my niece, Camila Daniela, a brilliant light full of potential. You will always have the unconditional support of your uncle, who believes in you endlessly.
- To Tenten, my loyal companion, who never failed to bring joy and peace throughout this extraordinary path.
- To Mr. Oswaldo and Mrs. Carolina, for always being attentive and supportive.
- To Juan Gabriel Aviña Cervantes and his family, thank you for helping me so much and embracing me as one of your own.
- To Gerardo Humberto Valencia, more than a colleague, a friend throughout this doctoral journey. Thank you for the meaningful conversations, academic and beyond, and for your constant support and companionship.
- To all my friends, thank you for your constant encouragement and for reminding me, even in the toughest moments, that yes, it was possible.
- And above all, to God, the source of wisdom, strength, and purpose; to Him be all the glory.

Acknowledgements

The completion of this dissertation has been possible thanks to the support, guidance, and generosity of many remarkable people and institutions. To all of them, I express my deepest gratitude.

- I am deeply grateful to Tecnológico de Monterrey for its tuition support through grant NUA A00836756, and to the Secretaría de Ciencia, Humanidades, Tecnología e Innovación (SECIHTI) for their support under grant number 1046000. Their financial support made it possible for me to pursue and complete this dissertation.
- I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the PhD and MSc Program in Computer Science direction, as well as to the Fondo de Apoyo a Publicaciones (FAP), for their continuous academic and financial support throughout this journey.
- My deepest appreciation goes to José Carlos Ortiz Bayliss, for his guidance, professionalism, consistency, and immense patience during the development of this work. Thank you for always being willing to listen and provide thoughtful advice when it was most needed.
- I am equally grateful to my advisor, Jorge Mario Cruz Duarte, for his support, dedication, and demanding rigor that constantly pushed me to achieve excellence. Your mentorship has left a profound mark on my academic path.
- I wish to extend my heartfelt thanks to Juan Gabriel Aviña Cervantes, whose generosity, insight, and constant encouragement went far beyond academic collaboration. Thank you for believing in me and for offering your friendship.
- I am also grateful to Iván Mauricio Amaya Contreras for his valuable contributions, ideas, and companionship throughout the development of this dissertation.
- A special acknowledgment goes to Julio Antonio Juárez Jiménez, for being a person of critical thinking and thoughtful words when they were most needed.
- A very special acknowledgment goes to Jorge Menchaca and Maricela Rodríguez Nieto, whose academic passion, kindness, and motivating words inspired me when I needed it most. Their example reminded me that true mentorship is built on both wisdom and humanity.
- Finally, to all those who, in one way or another, shared their time, knowledge, and support during this process, thank you.

Contents

1	Generalities	1
1.1	Introduction	1
1.2	Problem definition	3
1.3	Hypothesis and Research Questions	4
1.4	Objective	5
1.5	Scope	5
1.6	Contributions	6
1.6.1	Scientific products	6
1.6.2	Scientific products as co-author	8
1.6.3	Conference Participation	8
1.6.4	Academic Formation and Student Involvement	9
1.6.5	Academic Exhibitions and Competitions	9
1.7	Thesis Organization	9
2	Foundations	11
2.1	Optimization Problem	11
2.1.1	Classification of Optimization Problems	12
2.2	Heuristics	12
2.2.1	Simple Heuristics	14
2.2.2	Metaheuristics	16
2.3	Hyper-heuristics	18
2.4	Search Operators from some Classical Metaheuristics	19
2.4.1	Perturbators	20
2.4.2	Selectors	23
2.5	Population and Search Dynamics	24
2.5.1	Population	24
2.5.2	Exploration and Exploitation	24
2.6	Automated Algorithm Design	25
2.6.1	Design Space	27
2.6.2	Design Strategy	28
2.6.3	Performance Evaluation Strategy	29
2.6.4	Problem	29
2.7	Summary	30

3	High-Level Approaches for Automated Algorithm Design	31
3.1	Design Space	31
3.2	Design Strategy	33
3.2.1	Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH)	36
3.2.2	Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH)	37
3.2.3	Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS)	38
3.3	Performance Evaluation Strategy	40
3.4	Problems	42
3.5	Summary	43
4	Automated Algorithm Design for Control Problems in Electrical Engineering	44
4.1	Automatic voltage regulation	44
4.1.1	PID and Fractional-Order PID Controllers	47
4.2	DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters	48
4.2.1	Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers	50
4.3	Methodology	52
4.3.1	Automatic Voltage Regulator with PID and FOPID	52
4.3.2	DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters with Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers	55
4.4	Experimental Results	57
4.4.1	Automatic voltage regulation	57
4.4.2	DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters with ASMC	69
4.5	Summary	76
5	Automated Tailoring of Heuristic-Based Rényi Entropy Maximizers for Efficient Melanoma Segmentation	78
5.1	Melanoma Image Segmentation	78
5.1.1	Multilevel Thresholding	79
5.1.2	Two-Dimensional Histograms	79
5.1.3	Rényi Entropy for Segmentation	80
5.2	Methodology	81
5.2.1	Low-Level Domain	81
5.2.2	High-Level Domain	83
5.3	Experimental Results	83
5.3.1	Hyper-Heuristic Search for the Tailored Metaheuristic	84
5.3.2	Performance Distribution and Stability Analysis	85
5.3.3	Bayesian Analysis of Operator Selection	86
5.3.4	Application of the Tailored Metaheuristic to Melanoma Segmentation	88
5.4	Summary	89
6	Automated Algorithm Design in Bioengineering Applications	90
6.1	Cell Mechanics	90
6.1.1	Viscoelasticity and Fractional-Order Zener Model	91
6.1.2	Atomic Force Microscopy Measurements	92

6.2	Methodology	94
6.2.1	Low-level Problem: Model Identification	94
6.2.2	High-level Problem: Automated Algorithm Design	96
6.2.3	Comparative Evaluation and Analysis	96
6.3	Experimental Results	98
6.3.1	Effect of the Cardinality of the Tailored Metaheuristic	98
6.3.2	Effect of Hyperparameter Tuning in Metaheuristic Design	101
6.3.3	Effect of the Position of Search Operators on Metaheuristic Performance	105
6.3.4	Analysis of Viscoelastic Parameters	106
6.4	Summary	107
7	Conclusions and Future work	109
7.1	General Conclusions and Impact	109
7.2	Fulfilled Objectives	110
7.3	Limitations and Future Work	115
7.4	Prospectives	117

List of Figures

2.1	Hierarchical classification of heuristics.	14
2.2	Metaheuristic model composed of simple heuristics.	17
2.3	AAD workflow for metaheuristics.	27
4.1	Automatic Voltage Regulation (AVR) system.	45
4.2	Uncontrolled output voltage of the AVR system.	46
4.3	Basic circuit diagram of a DC-DC Buck–Boost converter.	48
4.4	Open-loop response of the Buck–Boost converter.	50
4.5	DC-DC Buck–Boost converter driven by an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller.	51
4.6	Block diagram of the AVR system with PID and FOPID controllers.	52
4.7	Block diagram of the Buck–Boost converter regulated by an ASMC.	55
4.8	Fitness distribution across 61 HH runs	59
4.9	The trend of operator one from the tailored MH.	59
4.10	The trend of operator two from the tailored MH.	60
4.11	The trend of operator three from the tailored MH.	60
4.12	Evolution trend of fitness for best MH	62
4.13	Replicate testing of tailored MH ₇ in AVR-FOPID tuning	63
4.14	AVR step response with tuned controllers	64
4.15	Evolution of candidate MH per HH step in AVR-FOPID tuning	65
4.16	Fitness evolution of candidate MHs at steps 0 and 9 of the HH process.	65
4.17	Distribution of controller parameters and fitness in AVR tuning	66
4.18	FOPID AVR step responses	67
4.19	Landscape of relationship λ and μ and their effects over the overshoot.	69
4.20	Landscape of relationship λ and μ and their effects over the settling time.	69
4.21	Performance metric and MH behavior in ASMC tuning	70
4.22	Fitness of 20 ASMC designs	72
4.23	Buck–Boost step response with tuned ASMC	73
4.24	Overshoot and settling time for tuned ASMC	74
4.25	Buck–Boost output under step and ramp	75
4.26	Disturbance profile and Buck–Boost response	75
4.27	ASMC response under nonlinear perturbations	76
5.1	Overview of the image segmentation process.	81
5.2	Preprocessing for melanoma segmentation: gray-scale and contrast-enhanced images.	82

5.3	Overview of the hyper-heuristic procedure for tailoring MH in dermoscopic image segmentation.	84
5.4	Overall performance across image sets	86
5.5	Performance vs. image set configuration	86
5.6	Posterior operator-selection probabilities in FOZ identification	87
5.7	Melanoma image and MH_* segmentation	88
5.8	2D histogram and optimized thresholds	88
6.1	Schematic of SLS and FOZ models	92
6.2	AFM force-relaxation schematic	93
6.3	Overview of the FOZ identification methodology using HH	95
6.4	3D landscape and contour for two-operator MHs in FOZ identification	100
6.5	Best vs. worst MH sequences performance in FOZ identification	100
6.6	Optuna-tuned vs. HH-designed MHs in FOZ identification	101
6.7	Tuned vs. HH-generated MHs for FOZ identification (cardinality 3)	102
6.8	Tuned vs. HH-generated MHs for FOZ identification (cardinality 2)	103
6.9	FOZ parameter estimates across MHs	104
6.10	Performance heat map across FOZ identification instances	105
6.11	Cumulative performance of MH_*^3 variations in FOZ model identification . . .	106
6.12	FOZ parameters under different force regimes	107

List of Tables

2.1	Classification criteria of optimization problems	13
2.2	Classification of Simple Heuristics	16
2.3	Classification of Hyper-heuristics	19
2.4	Representative categories of computational primitives used in AAD design spaces.	28
3.1	Heuristic feasible space	32
3.2	Collection of 205 search operators	33
3.3	Short collection of 24 search operators employed for AVR+PID controller tuning.	34
3.4	Heuristic space for melanoma segmentation	34
3.5	Search operators for tailored MH	35
3.6	Neighborhood actions in the HH process	36
4.1	AVR subsystems and transfer functions	46
4.2	Configuration of component values in the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter circuit.	49
4.3	Desired control specifications for Buck–Boost+ASMC system	56
4.4	Frequency of search operator family usage.	58
4.5	Performance of best and worst MH configurations	61
4.6	AVR transient response analysis	63
4.7	Operators defining the tailored MH _* for AVR tuning	66
4.8	Comparative analysis of FOPID approaches	67
4.9	FOPID robustness analysis under parameter variations	68
4.10	Variation parameters and hyperparameters of the search operators composing MH _*	71
4.11	ASMC design parameters and fitness statistics	71
4.12	Fitness metrics for each MH, including best, median, STD, IQR, and <i>p</i> -value from comparisons with MH _*	74
5.1	Performance of tailored MHs in melanoma segmentation tests	85
6.1	Best and worst MH sequences for FOZ identification	99
6.2	Best and worst MH configurations for FOZ identification	102
6.3	Selected Hyperparameters for cardinality two and three MHs.	105
6.4	Statistical indicators for FOZ model fitting	106

7.1 Summary of customized MHs generated by the AAD for each application domain. 116

List of Algorithms

1	Automated Design of Metaheuristics based on Simulated Annealing.	38
2	Automated Design of Metaheuristics based on Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic.	39
3	Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search	41
4	Tailored Metaheuristic	42

Abstract

Metaheuristics have proven to be powerful computational strategies for addressing highly nonlinear and intricate optimization problems over discrete, continuous, or mixed domains, with successful applications spanning from basic sciences to applied engineering. However, despite their effectiveness, the field has experienced an unrestrained proliferation of algorithmic variants, often lacking methodological rigor or reproducible design principles. This scenario underscores the need for systematic methodologies capable of guiding the creation, evaluation, and adaptation of metaheuristics in a principled and data-driven manner. In engineering practice, where optimization tasks frequently involve nonlinear dynamics, constraints, and uncertainty, metaheuristics have become crucial tools. Yet, manual configuration and tuning remain major bottlenecks that limit both reproducibility and scalability. This thesis introduces a unified framework for automated algorithm design based on hyper-heuristics to automate the generation and configuration of customized metaheuristics. Within this framework, the metaheuristic composition optimization problem is addressed as a high-level search process defined over a heuristic space composed of search operators. Three complementary automated algorithm design strategies were implemented: a simulated-annealing-based hyper-heuristic, a population-based random hyper-heuristic, and a randomized constructive hyper-heuristic with local search. These strategies enable automatic retrieval from metaheuristics using combinations of search operators under cardinality and performance constraints. The proposed framework is validated across two representative domains. In electrical engineering, automated algorithm design is applied to the tuning of classical and fractional-order proportional-integral-derivative controllers in automatic voltage regulators and to the tuning of adaptive sliding-mode controllers for direct-current buck-boost converters, achieving optimal transient performance and improved robustness without manual adjustment. In bioengineering, the methodology is applied to the segmentation of melanoma in dermoscopic images formulated as a Rényi entropy maximization problem, and to the viscoelastic characterization of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells through the identification of fractional-order Zener models using atomic force microscopy data. In both domains, the automatically generated metaheuristics showed consistent accuracy, convergence stability, and physical interpretability. The experimental results revealed that the effectiveness of automated algorithm design relies on the intelligent orchestration of search operators rather than on complex control schemes. A small subset of search operators, in particular *swarm_dynamic*, *differential_mutation*, and *random_flight*, which represent perturbative heuristics that modify the position of a current population, has shown to be consistently effective in optimization landscapes. Moreover, integrating model-free hyper-heuristic exploration with model-based hyperparameter tuning using Optuna generated metaheuristics that improved convergence by more than 50% and reduced variability by nearly 99%, confirming the computational efficiency and reproducibility of the approach. This research explores different alternatives for the automated design of metaheuristic algorithms capable of adapting to different optimization domains.

Chapter 1

Generalities

1.1 Introduction

Optimization has long been one of the most important tools in scientific and engineering research, encompassing a wide range of problems aimed at identifying the best configuration of decision variables under specific constraints and objectives. While early developments in optimization focused on algorithms capable of finding mathematically optimal solutions, it soon became apparent that many problems could not be efficiently solved to optimality, particularly those involving multimodal, non-differentiable, or NP-hard formulations [1–3]. With the growing complexity of real-world systems and the advent of powerful computational resources, heuristic and Metaheuristic (MH) methods became the primary approach to addressing such problems [4, 5]. Unlike exact algorithms, MHs do not guarantee global optimality but aim to provide high-quality solutions within a reasonable computational time.

MHs can be formally defined as general algorithmic processes described through the composition of Search Operators (SOs) or Simple Heuristics (SHs) [6, 7]. This definition follows a block-based perspective, in which an MH is conceived as a modular combination of functional components that explore and exploit the search space. This approach acts as a master strategy that iteratively guides the perturbation and evaluation of candidate solutions within the search space to approach an optimal or quasi-optimal solution progressively. The process concludes when a termination criterion established by the designer is met, such as a maximum number of iterations, a convergence condition, or a performance threshold [8]. Among the most notable examples are Evolutionary Algorithms (EA), Tabu Search (TS), Simulated Annealing (SA), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [9–13]. These methods integrate stochastic search mechanisms with adaptive control strategies to balance exploration and exploitation in complex search environments. However, the same versatility that makes MHs powerful has also led to an uncontrolled proliferation of variants, often lacking true mathematical novelty or formal rigor.

Designing a new MH is far from trivial; it requires substantial effort in conception, implementation, and validation, as well as a deep understanding of the underlying exploration and exploitation dynamics. Even so, classical MHs remain fundamental pillars of the field,

providing robust and well-established conceptual frameworks that serve as references for developing new optimization strategies. Nevertheless, numerous researchers continue to propose so-called “novel” algorithms inspired by natural or social metaphors, although analyses have demonstrated that many of these approaches can be mapped to existing ones through equivalent mathematical formulations [14–17]. This trend has fragmented the field, introducing redundant terminology and obscuring the theoretical foundations that support algorithmic design [18, 19]. As a result, selecting or designing an MH suitable for a specific problem has become a complex and often exhausting task for some researchers, especially beginners or experts from other fields.

For inexperienced users, the vast number of available algorithms and parameter settings poses a significant challenge to effective application. Even for experts, adjusting parameters or composing new algorithmic variants requires significant time and empirical validation to ensure consistent performance across diverse problem domains [20]. Furthermore, the No Free Lunch (NFL) theorem [21] establishes that no single algorithm can perform best across all possible optimization problems. Algorithmic superiority is therefore intrinsically problem-dependent, determined by how effectively a method’s internal biases align with the structural characteristics of the problem at hand [22]. Consequently, progress in optimization research does not come from seeking a universal solver but from developing methodologies capable of adapting algorithmic behavior to different classes of problems.

This has given rise to the Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) paradigm [7, 23–26]. AAD reformulates algorithm construction as an optimization problem in itself, where the search space is composed of algorithmic components such as search operators, control mechanisms, and hyperparameters, and the objective is to discover configurations that perform effectively for a given problem distribution [27–29]. In this context, computational resources replace or complement human expertise, enabling reproducible and data-driven exploration of the algorithmic design space. By automatically adapting components, structures, and hyperparameters, AAD can generate either new instantiations of existing algorithms or entirely novel configurations with emergent search behaviors [24, 29]. However, the approach requires that the optimization problem be clearly characterized and well defined. Within this paradigm, the Metaheuristic Composition Optimization Problem (MCOP) formalizes the search for optimal MH structures [29, 30]. In this formulation, each candidate solution represents a combination of SOs, parameter configurations, and selection mechanisms, and the goal is to identify those compositions that yield high-performance algorithms for the target problem class [30]. According to Cruz-Duarte et al. [30], this problem can be approached through high-level search processes based on Hyper-Heuristics (HHs), which explore the heuristic space to automatically generate, evaluate, and refine candidate metaheuristic compositions.

Recent advances have further strengthened the potential of HHs as an operational foundation for AAD. Based on the concept of modular design, MHs can be decomposed into mathematical operators or SHs that perturb candidate solutions using well-defined SOs [6, 31]. This decomposition enables the systematic recombination of operators to construct algorithms without relying on metaphorical analogies. Building on this principle, HHs and adaptive operator selection [32–34] elevate the automation process to a higher abstraction

level by employing evolutionary and learning-based strategies to select or generate low-level heuristics and MHs. A notable example is the CUSTOMHyS framework [35], which employs a Simulated Annealing-based HH to explore combinations of SHs derived from classical MHs. In parallel, several complementary research directions have contributed to consolidating the foundations of AAD. Beyond these, automated algorithm selection [36] and automated algorithm configuration [28, 37] represent two complementary paradigms that extend the automation spectrum: the former identifies the most suitable algorithm from a portfolio for a specific problem, while the latter fine-tunes or composes algorithmic components through hyperparameter optimization. More recently, advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) have begun to reshape the landscape of AAD by enabling semantic-driven exploration of algorithmic components, where LLMs act as high-level controllers capable of guiding operator selection, parameterization, and even structural synthesis of MHs through natural language representations [38].

Therefore, the objective of this research is to investigate, design, and implement an Automated Algorithm Design framework grounded in Hyper-heuristic principles, capable of automatically constructing customized Metaheuristics for diverse optimization problems. The proposed approach seeks to advance toward a systematic, adaptive, and reproducible methodology for generating problem-specific optimization algorithms applicable across various engineering domains.

1.2 Problem definition

The development of MHs is traditionally a manual and empirical process [20]. It requires defining suitable search operators, establishing their order of application, determining selection mechanisms, and tuning parameters to achieve a balance between exploration and exploitation [7]. This process is inherently complex, time-consuming, and highly dependent on the designer’s intuition and experience. As a result, the development of new algorithms often becomes a trial-and-error exercise with limited generalization capacity [20, 23]. Moreover, recent algorithmic proposals often lack mathematical rigor and are driven more by metaphorical inspiration [14–16, 19], resulting in redundant formulations that hinder systematic analysis. This situation exposes a fundamental limitation in the current state of MH design. Despite the vast number of available algorithms, there is no systematic or reproducible methodology to determine which configuration of search operators and selection mechanisms is best suited for a given problem domain. Consequently, identifying an effective algorithmic structure remains a non-trivial task that often depends on heuristic intuition rather than analytical formulation.

This lack of methodological consistency has motivated the emergence of the Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) paradigm, which aims to shift the algorithm development process from manual crafting to automated. Within this paradigm, the design of an algorithm is formulated as a search or optimization process operating over the space of algorithmic components, where the objective is to identify configurations that maximize performance under specific constraints. In the context of MHs, this idea has been concretized through the Metaheuristic Composition Optimization Problem (MCOP) [29, 30], whose goal is to

automatically explore the heuristic space and identify combinations of search operators that yield high-performance algorithmic structures. At this high level, the focus shifts from directly solving the underlying optimization problem to discovering how different heuristic components interact when properly ordered, parameterized, and selected, producing emergent search behaviors with desirable performance.

A first practical implementation of this paradigm was the CUSTOMHyS framework [30, 35, 39], conceived as a computational environment for the automatic composition and evaluation of MHs under the AAD-MCOP formulation. The framework provides a unified structure for representing, combining, and executing low-level search operators, allowing the systematic exploration of the heuristic space to identify operator sequences that exhibit competitive search performance. Different high-level control strategies have been explored within CUSTOMHyS, ranging from Simulated Annealing-based solvers to Random Search (RS) and learning-driven controllers based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architectures. These extensions have broadened the exploratory and adaptive capabilities of the framework, allowing it to capture dynamic interactions among operators and to generalize the composition process beyond purely stochastic mechanisms [39–41]. Its main contribution lies in the formalization of the composition process and in offering a standardized representation of heuristic components, enabling reproducible experimentation and comparative analysis of MH structures. However, despite its conceptual relevance, CUSTOMHyS still faces several methodological limitations. First, the heuristic collections available in the framework are not guaranteed to be optimal, and the large number of parameterized variants produced by the hyperparameters of each operator may introduce redundancy. Second, the exploration strategy based solely on Simulated Annealing has limited adaptability and lacks a learning mechanism capable of capturing dynamic inter-operator dependencies within the composition space.

Finally, the current implementation only supports a model-free design strategy, where the search proceeds without explicit modeling of operator performance or parameter influence. The integration of a model-based design perspective capable of adjusting established configurations remains an open line of research. Addressing these challenges is crucial for extending CUSTOMHyS into a more general, hybrid AAD framework, which combines model-free exploration with model-based adaptation to design MHs for complex real-world engineering problems effectively.

1.3 Hypothesis and Research Questions

This research is based on the hypothesis:

By implementing and analyzing strategies under the paradigm of Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) based on Hyper-heuristics (HH), it is possible to automatically generate customized Metaheuristics (MHs) capable of adapting their search dynamics to different optimization scenarios and achieving competitive performance across diverse engineering domains.

Such a hypothesis is extended from the following research questions:

1. How can engineering problems from different domains (e.g., electrical control systems and bioengineering) be characterized and represented within the AAD framework to enable automatic generation of problem-specific MHs?
2. How do different HH control strategies affect the automatic design process and the resulting MH configurations?
3. What is the impact of the number, diversity, and configuration of search operators and selection mechanisms on the performance and stability of the designed MHs across varying heuristic spaces?
4. In what way can model-free and model-based principles be integrated into a hybrid AAD strategy to enhance the adaptability and efficiency of the automatically generated MHs in real engineering problems?

1.4 Objective

The main objective of this research is to *develop, implement, and analyze Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) strategies based on Hyper-heuristics (HHs) to obtain customized Metaheuristics (MHs) and evaluate their performance in representative engineering problems, aiming to enhance their adaptability, efficiency, and generalization across diverse optimization problems.*

The specific goals pursued throughout this work are summarized as follows:

1. Select and characterize representative engineering problems from different domains, including electrical control systems and bioengineering, to serve as case studies for validating the proposed Automated Algorithm Design strategies.
2. Design and evaluate HH strategies within the AAD framework, exploring population-based and stochastic approaches to compose customized MHs tailored for real-world engineering applications.
3. Analyze the influence of search operators within the automated design process, considering different configurations of the heuristic space.
4. Propose a hybrid AAD strategy that combines model-free and model-based principles to generate customized MHs for real-world engineering problems efficiently.

1.5 Scope

This research addresses the problem of defining systematic methodologies for the design of customized MHs capable of adapting to different optimization contexts. To address this issue, the study is conducted within the framework of AAD and focuses on the development and evaluation of HH-based strategies for the composition of MHs formulated under the MCOP. The CUSTOMHyS framework is used as the computational environment for representing, combining, and assessing heuristic operators under a unified formal model.

The work involves the design and comparison of high-level HH strategies for model-free exploration of the composition space, implemented through stochastic and population-based approaches. These strategies are applied to representative engineering problems from two established domains:

- Electrical engineering, focused on controller tuning and system optimization; and
- Bioengineering, focused on parameter estimation and viscoelastic characterization.

The selected problems are well-established in the literature and are employed as validation benchmarks to examine the feasibility and consistency of the proposed AAD strategies. The goal is not to outperform existing results but to show that automatically identifying suitable MH configurations for these problems leads, as a natural consequence, to competitive performance. The analysis considers the effect of operator composition, cardinality, and selection mechanisms on algorithmic behavior, together with a preliminary exploration of hyperparameter tuning to extend the current model-free strategies toward a hybrid model-based design.

1.6 Contributions

The main contributions of this thesis are summarized as follows:

1. A unified theoretical and computational framework was established to represent, compose, and evaluate metaheuristic structures through the automated combination of heuristic operators. This formalization provides a foundation for systematic experimentation, reproducibility, and analytical comparison of metaheuristic designs.
2. The framework was adapted to support new hyper-heuristic strategies, enabling the automated generation of metaheuristics through model-free exploration mechanisms. Performance was assessed across multiple engineering problems, demonstrating the feasibility and generality of the proposed approach.
3. A methodological extension was introduced to incorporate hyperparameter tuning as an initial step toward model-based AAD.
4. The proposed methodologies were validated in two distinct domains:
 - Electrical engineering, focusing on automatic controller tuning and dynamic system optimization.
 - Bioengineering, addressing the viscoelastic characterization of biological cells and the automated segmentation of melanoma images.

1.6.1 Scientific products

The results derived from this doctoral research have been disseminated through peer-reviewed scientific publications and conference proceedings, reflecting the methodological and applied contributions of this work within the AAD. The following list summarizes the publications derived from this doctoral research:

1. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, Gerardo H. Valencia-Rivera, Iván Amaya, and Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, “Dynamic Analysis for the Physically Correct Model of a Fractional-Order Buck–Boost Converter,” *Computer Sciences and Mathematics Forum*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 2, MDPI, 2022.
2. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, José C. Ortiz-Bayliss, Jesús J. Yáñez-Borjas, and Iván Amaya, “Automatic Design of Metaheuristics for Practical Engineering Applications,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 7262–7276, 2023.
3. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, and Herman Castañeda, “Automatic Hyper-Heuristic to Generate Heuristic-Based Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller Tuners for Buck–Boost Converters,” *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (GECCO)*, pp. 1482–1489, 2023. Nominated to Best Paper Award.
4. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Alberto C. Molina-Porras, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, Rodrigo Correa, and Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, “Designing Heuristic-Based Tuners for PID Controllers in Automatic Voltage Regulator Systems Using an Automated Hyper-Heuristic Approach,” *Proceedings of the IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, pp. 1263–1268, 2023.
5. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Alberto C. Molina-Porras, Emmanuel Ovalle-Magallanes, Iván Amaya, José C. Ortiz-Bayliss, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, and Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, “SIGNRL: A Population-Based Reinforcement Learning Method for Continuous Control,” *Proceedings of the IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, pp. 1443–1448, 2023.
6. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Gerardo H. Valencia-Rivera, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, Iván Amaya, and Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, “Designing Heuristic-Based Tuners for Fractional-Order PID Controllers in Automatic Voltage Regulator Systems Using a Hyper-Heuristic Approach,” *Fractal and Fractional*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 223, MDPI, 2024.
7. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, José C. Ortiz-Bayliss, Iván Amaya, and Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, “Beyond Traditional Tuning: Unveiling Metaheuristic Operator Trends in PID Control Tuning for Automatic Voltage Regulation,” *Proceedings of the IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, pp. 1–8, 2024.
8. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, Herman Castañeda, and Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, “Optimization of Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers Using Customized Metaheuristics in DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters,” *Mathematics*, vol. 12, no. 23, p. 3709, MDPI, 2024.
9. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge Ramos-Frutos, Oscar Ramos-Soto, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, Diego Oliva, and Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, “Automated Tailoring of Heuristic-Based Rényi’s Entropy Maximizers for Efficient Melanoma Segmentation,” *Proceedings of the IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Image, Signal Processing and Synthetic Media (CISM)*, pp. 1–7, 2025.

10. Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, José C. Ortiz-Bayliss, Iván Amaya, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, and Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, “Automated Design and Selection of Metaheuristics for PID Control in Power Electronics,” *Applied Soft Computing*, (Under review), 2025.

1.6.2 Scientific products as co-author

1. Fernando D. Hernández-Gutiérrez, Eli G. Avina-Bravo, Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Oscar Almanza-Conejo, Mario A. Ibarra-Manzano, José Ruiz-Pinales, Emmanuel Ovalle-Magallanes, and Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, “Brain Tumor Segmentation from Optimal MRI Slices Using a Lightweight U-Net,” *Technologies*, vol. 12, no. 10, p. 183, MDPI, 2024.
2. Keyla Ospino-Manjarres, Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, Daniel Jauregui-Vázquez, Carlos E. Osornio-Martínez, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, Kristy Escalante-Sánchez, and R. Rojas-Laguna, “Study of Machine Learning Techniques for Robotic Finger Monitoring Using Image-Based Macro-Bending Fiber Optic Sensor,” *Óptica Pura y Aplicada*, vol. 58, no. 1, 2025.
3. Grecia C. Duque-Giménez, Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Maricela Rodríguez-Nieto, Jorge L. Menchaca-Arredondo, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, Diana G. Zárate-Triviño, Juan G. Avina-Cervantes, and José C. Ortiz-Bayliss, “Viscoelastic Characterization of the Human Osteosarcoma Cancer Cell Line MG-63 Using a Fractional-Order Zener Model Through Automated Algorithm Design and Configuration,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 31436, Nature Publishing Group, 2025.
4. Guadalupe Vázquez-Cisneros, Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Grecia C. Duque-Giménez, Alejandro Flores-Mayorga, Diana G. Zárate-Triviño, Cristina Rodríguez-Padilla, Marco A. Bedolla, Jorge L. Menchaca-Arredondo, and Maricela Rodríguez-Nieto, “Integrated Study of Morphology and Viscoelastic Properties in the MG-63 Cancer Cell Line,” *IEEE Access*, (Under review), 2025.
5. Jorge Ramos-Frutos, Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutiérrez, Alexis I. Cárdenas-Torres, Israel Miguel-Andrés, Diego Oliva, and Saúl Zapotecas-Martínez, “Towards Optimizing Genetic Algorithm Parameters for Permutation Flow Shop Scheduling Using Taguchi Methodology,” *IEEE Latin American Conference on Computational Intelligence (LA-CCI)*, (Accepted, in press), 2025.

1.6.3 Conference Participation

1. 5th Mexican Workshop on Fractional Calculus (MWFC). Monterrey, Mexico, 5-7 October 2022, Paper, oral presentation, and poster.
2. Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (GECCO 2023). Lisbon, Portugal, 2023, Paper and oral presentation. Nominated for Best Paper Award.
3. 2023 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI). Mexico, 2023, Paper and oral presentation.

4. 2024 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC). Yokohama, Japan, 2024, Paper and oral presentation.
5. 2025 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Image, Signal Processing and Synthetic Media (CISM). Trondheim, Norway, 2025, Paper and oral presentation.

1.6.4 Academic Formation and Student Involvement

This doctoral research contributed to the academic training and mentoring of graduate students in the areas of computational intelligence, optimization, and applied engineering. The following theses were supervised or co-supervised as part of this work:

1. Franklin E. Carrero Murillo - *M.Sc. in Electrical Engineering and Digital Systems, Universidad de Guanajuato.*
Thesis: *Fault Detection in Induction-Motor Bearings via Machine-Learning Techniques.*
Role: Co-advisor.
2. Keyla C. Ospino-Manjarres - *M.Sc. in Electrical Engineering and Digital Systems, Universidad de Guanajuato.*
Thesis: *Modern Machine-Learning Techniques for Curvature Detection with Fiber Optics and Their Application in Biomechanics.*
Role: Co-advisor.
3. Kristy C. Escalante-Sánchez - *M.Sc. in Electrical Engineering and Digital Systems, Universidad de Guanajuato.*
Thesis: *Vibration-Signal Analysis Using a Reflective Fiber-Optic Array with Machine-Learning Techniques.*
Role: Co-advisor.

1.6.5 Academic Exhibitions and Competitions

1. ExpoIngenierías, Tecnológico de Monterrey. Participation in four editions of the institutional event *ExpoIngenierías*, presenting research and development projects. Awarded first place in one edition with the project: “Dynamic Model for Fault Detection in Civil Structures Using Intelligent Heuristic-Based Algorithms.”

1.7 Thesis Organization

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 presents the mathematical and algorithmic foundations that support the proposed research. It introduces optimization problems, heuristics, metaheuristics, and hyper-heuristics, highlighting their hierarchical relationships.

Chapter 3 describes the high-level design frameworks employed to generate metaheuristic algorithms automatically. Three strategies are developed: the Simulated Annealing

Hyper-Heuristic (SAHH), the Population-based Random Hyper-Heuristic (PRHH), and the Randomized Constructive Hyper-Heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS).

Chapter 4 applies the proposed AAD strategies to control-oriented optimization problems, including the tuning of classical and fractional-order PID controllers for Automatic Voltage Regulation (AVR) and the configuration of Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers for DC-DC Buck–Boost converters.

Chapter 5 extends the AAD framework to a biomedical application involving the segmentation of melanoma in dermoscopic images.

Chapter 6 focuses on the automated design and configuration of metaheuristics for identifying parameters of viscoelastic models from AFM data. In particular, it studies the fractional-order Zener model for the mechanical characterization of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells, integrating model-free and model-based principles within the AAD framework.

Chapter 7 presents the conclusions derived from this research and discusses its main limitations.

Chapter 2

Foundations

This chapter presents the mathematical and algorithmic foundations that underpin the rest of this thesis. Throughout the text, we adopt a hierarchical notation to distinguish between different abstraction levels in the optimization framework. We denote by $\vec{s} \in \mathfrak{S}$ a generic candidate within an abstract feasible search space. When the focus is placed on the low-level problem, which corresponds to continuous optimization in $\mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^D$, the candidate is represented as $\vec{x} \in \mathfrak{X}$, and the population of solutions at iteration t is denoted by $X(t)$. At the high-level, where the task is to select or organize heuristics, the generic element becomes a heuristic configuration $\vec{h} \in \mathfrak{H}$, with \mathfrak{H} representing an arbitrary heuristic space. This hierarchical distinction allows us to use a unified notation \vec{s} at the abstract level, while consistently particularizing it as \vec{x} for continuous solution spaces and \vec{h} for heuristic configurations, depending on the context.

2.1 Optimization Problem

In numerous systems, both natural and artificial, behaviors are exhibited that are oriented toward achieving the best possible result under certain conditions. This phenomenon is known as optimization, which constitutes a fundamental principle in nature and processes designed by humans [42]. In the natural world, for example, it is reflected in the efficiency of various biological systems, such as protein folding, whose final conformation minimizes energy consumption, or the foraging strategies of social insects, which maximize resource acquisition with the least possible expenditure. These behaviors have inspired the development of technologies that mimic or adapt such principles to solve complex problems in different domains [43, 44]. In engineering and computer science, optimization is present in the design of efficient algorithms, the configuration of complex systems, and the allocation of limited resources. In all cases, the goal is to select from a finite set of alternatives the one that offers the best performance according to previously established criteria [45].

Formally, optimization theory states that there exists a set of valid solutions $\mathfrak{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{S}$, where \mathfrak{S} defines the general set of candidate solutions associated with an objective function $f(\vec{s}) : \vec{s} \in \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which can be minimized or maximized. In this context, the problem of identifying

the best solution can be formulated as a minimization process on the pair (\mathfrak{S}, f) , expressed as follows [6, 7, 46]:

$$\vec{s}_* = \underset{\vec{s} \in \mathfrak{S}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \{f(\vec{s})\}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\vec{s}_* \in \mathfrak{S}$ denotes the optimal solution that yields the minimum value of the objective function, that is, $f(\vec{s}_*) \leq f(\vec{s}), \forall \vec{s} \in \mathfrak{S}$.

Equation (2.1) represents the general definition of an optimization problem. However, the approach adopted in this thesis involves two levels of abstraction: a low-level problem and a high-level problem [6, 7]. At the low level, we define $\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^D$, where D denotes the number of dimensions of the problem.

At the high level, the problem can be formulated as a combinatorial optimization task, where the objective is to identify a sequence of elements or Search Operators (SOs) [6] that most effectively address the low-level problem according to the designer's requirements. So, we have a feasible heuristic domain $\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{H} \subseteq \mathbb{H}^\varpi$, where \mathbb{H} is the heuristic space and ϖ is the cardinality.

2.1.1 Classification of Optimization Problems

The diversity of optimization problems that arise in both theory and practice is enormous, and their characteristics can vary significantly depending on the domain, the nature of the variables, and the specific requirements of the task at hand. For this reason, it is essential to establish a clear classification to select or design an appropriate solution method [45]. This classification also facilitates the identification of problem properties that may influence algorithmic performance and guide the choice between exact, approximate, or heuristic approaches. Table 2.1 summarizes the main mathematical and structural criteria commonly used to classify optimization problems, including objective type, variable domain, and constraint handling [8, 45].

In the context of this thesis, the low-level problem corresponds to a continuous, single-objective, unconstrained/constrained, black-box optimization task, which is prevalent in practical engineering applications. Such problems typically involve high-dimensional, multimodal search spaces and computationally expensive evaluations of the objective function, making traditional exact methods impractical. At a high level, the objective becomes a combinatorial optimization problem, in which the task involves selecting and organizing heuristics from a given heuristic space to construct an algorithmic configuration that effectively addresses the low-level continuous problem.

2.2 Heuristics

A heuristic is a problem-solving procedure designed to generate, evaluate, or modify one or more candidate solutions for an optimization problem, often leveraging problem-specific knowledge, rules, or simplified models [47]. These procedures do not guarantee the identification of the global optimum; instead, they aim to produce solutions within a

Table 2.1: Main mathematical and structural criteria used for classifying optimization problems. Adapted from [8, 45].

Criterion	Category	Description
Nature of the decision variables	Continuous	Variables take values in a continuous domain.
	Discrete	Variables take values from a finite or countable set.
	Mixed	Contain both continuous and discrete variables.
Number of objectives	Single-objective	Only one performance measure is optimized.
	Multi-objective	Two or more objectives are optimized simultaneously, often requiring a trade-off.
Constraints	Unconstrained	No restrictions are imposed on the decision variables.
	Constrained	Feasible solutions must satisfy equality or inequality constraints.
Availability of information	White-Box	Complete analytical description of $f(\vec{s})$ is available, and derivatives may be obtained when applicable.
	Black-Box	$f(\vec{s})$ can only be evaluated through simulation, experimentation, or costly computation, without derivative information.

reasonable computational effort, making them particularly useful for complex or large-scale problems where exhaustive search methods are impractical.

In the literature, the term heuristic is sometimes used interchangeably with Metaheuristic (MH). However, a heuristic operates at a lower level of abstraction, typically acting directly on the representation of a solution. In contrast, an MH coordinates one or more heuristics to guide the search more broadly and strategically. If the abstraction level is raised further, we reach the domain of Hyper-heuristics (HHs), which operate on the heuristic space rather than directly on the solution space.

From a hierarchical perspective, heuristics can be classified into three main categories according to their degree of interaction with the problem domain: simple heuristics, metaheuristics, and hyper-heuristics [30]. Figure 2.1 illustrates this classification, showing how each abstraction level differs in the type of input it processes and its operational scope. At the low level, a simple heuristic acts directly on a solution or set of solutions to produce a new candidate in the search space. At the intermediate level, a metaheuristic orchestrates one or more simple heuristics to explore and exploit the solution space. Finally, at the top level, an HH selects, combines, or adapts heuristics from a given set to address a given problem. The following sections provide a detailed definition of each category. In the context of this thesis, most heuristics are applied within a population-based search paradigm, where the search state at a given iteration t is represented as

$$X(t) = \{\vec{x}_1(t), \dots, \vec{x}_N(t)\}, \quad \vec{x}_n(t) \in \mathfrak{X}. \quad (2.2)$$

with N denoting the number of candidate solutions in the population and $\vec{x}_n(t) \in \mathfrak{S}$ representing the n -th individual in the feasible search space.

Figure 2.1: Hierarchical classification of heuristics according to their level of abstraction and interaction with the problem domain, based on the work conducted by Cruz-Duarte et al. [7].

2.2.1 Simple Heuristics

A simple heuristic (SHs) refers to a basic strategy or building block within a search process that allows direct interaction with the problem domain. It typically operates by modifying candidate solutions, evaluating them, or both, depending on its design and function. Thus, three types of SHs can be stated: Generative, Perturbative, and Collective. In the context of this thesis, most SHs are embedded in a population-based search paradigm, where the search state at iteration t is denoted as

$$X(t) = \{\vec{x}_1(t), \dots, \vec{x}_N(t)\}, \quad (2.3)$$

with N representing the number of candidate solutions in the population and $\vec{x}_n(t) \in \mathfrak{X}$ being the n -th individual in the feasible search space. In this setting, a Generative SH can initialize $X(0)$, Perturbative SHs modify one or more $\vec{x}_n(t)$, and Collective SHs decide which $\vec{x}_n(t)$ are preserved or replaced in $X(t+1)$.

First, Generative SHs (h_g) produce one or more initial solutions without relying on any prior information. This type of heuristic is commonly identified as initializer, which serves as the first block or strategy to interact with the search space $S \in \mathfrak{S}$. Mathematically, a Generative SH can be defined as

$$S \leftarrow h_g\{\mathfrak{S}\}, \quad (2.4)$$

Note that the representation of S can vary according to the level of abstraction at which it is used, that is, it can be in continuous or combinatorial space. In that case, we have two options: $S = \vec{x}$ with $\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{X} \in \mathbb{R}^D$, if we have only one candidate's solution or $S = X$ with

$\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{X} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ if we have a set (population) of possible solutions. Now, if we are working at a high level of abstraction, the heuristic space is defined as $S = \vec{h}$ with $\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{H} \in \mathbb{H}^\omega$.

Subsequently, Perturbatives are SHs with the faculty of altering one or more candidate solutions to $S' \in \mathfrak{S}$ using the current state $S \in \mathfrak{S}$. Therefore, it is formulated as

$$S' \leftarrow h_p(\mathfrak{S})\{S\}. \quad (2.5)$$

Additionally, a characteristic of these SHs is the requirement of additional information, in most cases, such as the best solution found globally, the leading candidate within a subpopulation, or the most successful position encountered throughout the search history.

Lastly, we have the SHs called Collective; these simple heuristics are responsible for deciding whether to retain the current solution $S \in \mathfrak{S}$ or replace it with an alternative candidate $S' \in \mathfrak{S}$. Like generative ones, common collectives are implemented in the literature called selectors ($h_s \in \mathfrak{H}$) [39]. Their main role is to determine whether a candidate solution should be incorporated, following an acceptance requirement defined by the designer, such as

$$S_{\text{new}} \leftarrow h_s(S) \{S'\} \equiv \begin{cases} S', & \text{if (Criterion = true),} \\ S, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

At a low level of abstraction, an h_s decides whether to accept the alternative candidate S' w.r.t. the current S and according to the `Criterion`. For example, one of the most popular selection heuristics is the Greedy strategy, where X' is accepted if its fitness value is improved over the X one.

At a high level of abstraction, these simple heuristics can also be coded to determine the next operation to perform [40]. A particular case of these selectors in the high level is labeled as finalizers ($h_f \in \mathfrak{H}$) because they can be implemented as master strategies for controlling a search process [7]. In such a case, we say w.l.g. that $S = h$ and $S' = h'$, thus,

$$h' \leftarrow h_f(h) \equiv \begin{cases} h_{\hat{e}}, & \text{if (Criterion = true),} \\ h_f \circ h, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2.7)$$

where $h \in \mathfrak{H}$ is an arbitrary SH, \circ is the composition operator, and $h_{\hat{e}}$ is the identity heuristic, i.e., $h \circ h_{\hat{e}} = h_{\hat{e}} \circ h = h$ [6]. Notice the recursive nature of this simple heuristic. So, if the set `Criterion` is met, no more h deployments are performed.

In addition, it is worth mentioning the Search Operators (SOs), which correspond to a simple heuristic composed of a h_p and a h_s . Mathematically, a search operator h_o is formulated as

$$S' \leftarrow h_o\{S\} = (h_s \circ h_p) \{S\}. \quad (2.8)$$

Consider that the composition operator is not commutative [6].

Table 2.2 quickly summarizes how each SH can be expressed based on the three types (Generative, Perturbing, and Collective), which vary depending on their level of

abstraction or problem domain. For this work, in the low-level domain, candidate solutions come from the real space \mathbb{R}^D ; in the high-level domain, they come from the heuristic space \mathbb{H}^ϖ .

Table 2.2: Summary of the classification of Simple Heuristics (SHs) according to the level of abstraction used. C_s and C_f correspond to the selection and finalization criteria defined by the designer.

	Simple Heuristics (SHs)		
	<i>Generator</i> h_g	<i>Perturbator</i> h_p	<i>Collector</i> h_s, h_f
Low-level Domain $\mathfrak{x} \in \mathbb{R}^D$	$X \leftarrow h_g\{\mathfrak{x}\}$	$X' \leftarrow h_p(\mathfrak{x})\{X\}$	$X' \leftarrow h_s(C_s)\{X\}$
High-level Domain $\vec{\mathfrak{h}} \in \mathbb{H}^\varpi$	$\vec{h} \leftarrow h_g\{\vec{\mathfrak{h}}\}$	$\vec{h}' \leftarrow h_p(\vec{\mathfrak{h}})\{\vec{h}\}$	$\vec{h}' \leftarrow h_f(C_f)\{\vec{h}_o\}$

2.2.2 Metaheuristics

Metaheuristics (MHs) are optimization strategies that iteratively guide the search toward regions of the solution space where good-quality solutions are likely to be found. In the context of this thesis, an MH is conceived as a coordinated framework that combines one or more Simple Heuristics (SHs) to explore and exploit the search space effectively. An MH can thus be understood as a policy for handling simple heuristics, whose coordinated execution generally yields better performance than using individual heuristics in isolation [48, 49]. These heuristics, whether generative, perturbative, or collective, serve as the fundamental operators that modify, evaluate, or select candidate solutions during the search process. Randomization is often incorporated to promote diversity and avoid premature convergence, while a user-defined termination criterion, such as a maximum number of iterations, a computational time limit, or the attainment of a target solution quality, determines when the search stops.

MHs can be categorized in multiple ways. For example, they can be classified as constructive or perturbative, depending on how new solutions are created. Constructive MHs, such as Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedure (GRASP) [50], build solutions incrementally from scratch by adding components until a complete solution is obtained. Perturbative MHs, including Simulated Annealing (SA) [51], or Tabu Search (TS) [9], start from an existing solution and apply iterative modifications to improve it. Another classification is into memory-based or memory-less, according to whether they store information about past solutions. Memory-based examples include TS, which maintains a tabu list to avoid cycling, and Estimation of Distribution Algorithms (EDAs) [52], which store statistical models of good solutions. Memory-less examples, such as basic Genetic Algorithms (GAs) [53] or SA, rely only on the current population or solution without explicit long-term memory structures. MHs can also be distinguished as population-based or single-solution. Population-based methods, such as GAs, PSO [11], or Differential Evolution (DE) [54], evolve a set of solutions simultaneously, enabling parallel exploration of multiple regions of the search space. In

contrast, single-solution methods, such as SA or Iterated Local Search (ILS) [55], operate on a single candidate solution at a time, iteratively modifying it and typically relying on stochastic acceptance rules to escape local optima.

A further distinction concerns whether the design of an MH is metaphor-based, drawing inspiration from natural, social, or artificial processes, or non-metaphor-based, relying instead on mathematical and algorithmic principles. Metaphor-based examples include Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [11], inspired by the social behavior of flocks of birds, and Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) [56], inspired by the foraging behavior of bees. Non-metaphor-based examples, such as Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) [57] and Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) [58], are designed based on mathematical principles without relying on an analogy.

Typically, various mathematical models of MHs derive their inspiration from analogies drawn from natural phenomena or physical processes, which are commonly expressed as metaphors. Although there is nothing wrong with these metaphors, it is worth noting that some members of the scientific community have used them to describe an MH as “novel” despite lacking substantial contributions, effectively producing rebranded versions of already established classical MHs [15–17].

An MH can be described through three main heuristic components: a generator or initializer h_g (also known as h_i), one or more search operators h_o , and a finalizer h_f [30]. These components are executed iteratively, following a defined structure, until a termination criterion is met. The search operator h_o may comprise a sequence of ϖ SOs, expressed as $h_o = h_\varpi \circ h_{\varpi-1} \circ \dots \circ h_1, \forall h_k \in \vec{h} \in \mathbb{H}^\varpi$. Due to the non-commutative nature of SOs, the reversed composition is denoted as $\bar{h}_o = h_1 \circ \dots \circ h_{\varpi-1} \circ h_\varpi$. Figure 2.2 illustrates the standard MH model, where the sequence \bar{h}_o operates between initialization and finalization.

Figure 2.2: Metaheuristic model represented through a set of simple heuristics: an initializer h_g , a set of search operators h_o , and a finalizer h_f , based on the work conducted by Cruz-Duarte et al. [7].

Formally, an MH can be expressed as

$$\text{MH}_o \triangleq \langle h_g, h_o, h_f \rangle = h_f(h_o) \circ h_g, \quad (2.9)$$

where $\vec{h}_o = (h_1, h_2, \dots, h_\varpi)^\top$ and $\#\text{MH}_o = \varpi$.

Following this approach, known MHs can be formally described in terms of their SO. For example, SA and GA can be decomposed into sequences of perturbative and selective heuristics. SA can be expressed as

$$\text{MH}_{\text{SA}} = h_f \circ (h_M \circ h_{\text{RS}}) \circ h_g, \quad (2.10)$$

where h_{RS} is a random search, h_M is a Metropolis-based selector, and h_f represents the finalization process [6]. Similarly, GA follows the structure,

$$\text{MH}_{\text{GA}} = h_f \circ (h_G \circ h_{\text{GM}}) \circ (h_D \circ h_{\text{GC}}) \circ h_g, \quad (2.11)$$

where h_{GC} is a genetic crossover, h_D represents a direct selector, h_{GM} is a genetic mutation and h_G is a greedy selector [6].

2.3 Hyper-heuristics

Hyper-Heuristics (HHs) were first introduced by Cowling et al. [59] as “*heuristics for choosing heuristics*” in combinatorial optimization. They are considered high-level algorithms that operate above MHs, managing a set of SHs instead of directly manipulating candidate solutions. In this sense, HHs either select or generate simple heuristics to provide suitable solutions to a given problem. This indirect interaction with the problem domain implies that HHs explore a heuristic space composed of SHs, rather than the solution space itself. Because of this feature, their main difference with MHs arises: while an MH executes a specific procedure to obtain a solution, an HH can reorganize itself to find the most effective sequence of SHs for solving a particular problem [60]. In the literature, we can find two widely accepted classifications that distinguish HHs in two dimensions [61]: The first refers to the nature of the heuristic search space, which distinguishes whether the HH selects from a set of existing heuristics (heuristic selection) or generates new heuristics by combining components of existing ones (heuristic generation). Both approaches can be applied to both constructive heuristics, which build solutions step by step, and perturbative heuristics, which modify already complete candidate solutions. The second refers to the feedback mechanism that guides the HH. In this case, an HH can be based on: online learning, where adaptation occurs during the search process itself (e.g., reinforcement-based selection), offline learning, where the HH learns from past training instances before being applied to new problems, or no learning, where the choice or generation of heuristics follows predefined or random rules without adaptation. These categories are summarized in Table 2.3.

The motivation for using HHs is closely related to the No-Free-Lunch theorem [21], which states that no algorithm can outperform all others across every possible problem. An algorithm that performs exceptionally well on one class of problems will necessarily perform poorly on another. In this context, HHs provide a mechanism to adaptively explore the space of heuristics, reorganizing them into effective sequences that improve problem-specific performance.

Formally, an HH can be expressed as the optimization problem as,

Table 2.3: Classification of Hyper-heuristics according to search space and feedback (based on the work conducted by Burke et al. [61]).

Criterion	Category	Description
Nature of the heuristic search space	Heuristic selection	Selects one heuristic from the available pool [61].
	Heuristic generation	Creates a new heuristic by combining or modifying existing heuristics [61].
Feedback source	Online learning	Adapts while solving a given instance, e.g., reinforcement strategies [62] or metaheuristic-based [60].
	Offline learning	Learns from training instances to generalize to unseen problems (e.g., case-based reasoning, GP [63]).
	No-learning	Does not incorporate feedback from the search process; relies on predefined rules [61].

$$\vec{h}_* = \operatorname{argmax}_{\vec{h} \in \mathfrak{H}} Q(\vec{h} \mid \mathfrak{X}, f), \quad (2.12)$$

where $\vec{h} \in \mathfrak{H} \in \mathbb{H}^\omega$ is a heuristic configuration from the feasible collection inside the heuristic space, and $Q(\vec{h} \mid \mathfrak{X}, f) : \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is a performance function that quantifies the quality of \vec{h} when applied to the optimization problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) . Hence, the HH seeks the configuration \vec{h}_* that maximizes the performance, reaching the highest attainable value $Q_{\max} = Q(\vec{h}_* \mid \mathfrak{X}, f)$.

2.4 Search Operators from some Classical Metaheuristics

To better understand the search dynamics of MH, it is useful to analyze the individual components that drive their exploration and exploitation capabilities. Among these components, perturbators play a key role, as they define how candidate solutions are modified during the search process. Likewise, selectors determine which solutions are chosen for perturbation or preserved for the next iteration. In this thesis, the set of 12 perturbators and four selectors proposed in [7] is employed. These operators were extracted from ten classical MHs, ranging from simple random modifications to more elaborate dynamic update rules. Before describing the perturbators and selectors, recall that $\vec{x}_n(t) \in X(t)$ denotes the position of the n -th agent in a population $X(t)$ of size N at iteration t , and $\vec{x}_*(t)$ represents the best solution found at that iteration. The search operators are defined to generate the n -th candidate solution $\vec{y}_n \in \mathfrak{X}$ within the problem domain $\mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^D$. These operators are expressed in vector form and, in most cases, make use of the Hadamard-Schur product \odot and the element-wise Heaviside step function $H : \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_2^D$ with $H(0) = 1$.

2.4.1 Perturbators

Random Sample. The *Random Sample* [64] perturbator generates a candidate solution by replacing the current position with a randomly sampled vector:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{r}, \quad (2.13)$$

where $\vec{r} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is a vector of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) random numbers, with each component r_i drawn from a uniform distribution $\mathcal{V}(-1, 1)$. This operator introduces purely stochastic changes, promoting exploration without relying on information from the current population.

Random Search. The *Random Search* [65] perturbator generates a candidate solution by adding a stochastic displacement to the current position:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \alpha \vec{r}, \quad (2.14)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is the step-size factor and $\vec{r} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is a vector of i.i.d. random numbers. The components of \vec{r} may be drawn from various probability distributions, such as uniform $\mathcal{V}(-1, 1)$, standard normal $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, or symmetric Lévy stable $\mathcal{L}(1.5)$. This operator supports both local and global search depending on the magnitude of α .

Local Random Walk. The *Local Random Walk* [66] perturbator modifies the current position using a probabilistic differential update between two selected individuals:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \alpha \vec{r} \odot H(p - \vec{q}) \odot (\vec{x}_{z_1}(t) - \vec{x}_{z_2}(t)), \quad (2.15)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is the step-size factor, \vec{r} and \vec{q} are vectors of i.i.d. random variables with $\mathcal{V}(0, 1)$, and $p \in (0, 1]$ is the probability of change. The vectors $\vec{x}_{z_1}(t)$ and $\vec{x}_{z_2}(t)$ correspond to individuals selected from the population according to a predefined selection scheme.

Random Flight. The *Random Flight* [66] perturbator updates the current position proportionally to its distance from the best-known solution:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \alpha \vec{r} \odot (\vec{x}_n(t) - \vec{x}_*(t)), \quad (2.16)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_+$ is the spatial step-size, and $\vec{r} \in \mathbb{R}_+^D$ is a vector of i.i.d. random variables generated from either the uniform distribution $\mathcal{V}(0, 1)$, the standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, or the symmetric Lévy stable distribution $\mathcal{L}(1.5)$.

Genetic Crossover. This perturbator operates on a ranked version of the population $\hat{X}(t) = \{\hat{x}_1, \dots, \hat{x}_N\}$, sorted by increasing cost function value. The best $M = \lfloor m_p N \rfloor$ individuals form the mating pool, where $m_p \in (0, 1]$ denotes the mating pool fraction [67]. A candidate solution is generated as:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{m} \odot \hat{x}_{z_1} + (1 - \vec{m}) \odot \hat{x}_{z_2}, \quad \forall z_1 \neq z_2 \in \{1, \dots, M\}, \quad (2.17)$$

where $\vec{m} \in [0, 1]^D$ is the mask vector, and z_1, z_2 are parent indices selected from the mating pool using a pairing scheme such as random, rank-weighted, roulette-wheel, or tournament pairing. The mask vector is determined according to a crossover mechanism, among which the most common are: single-point, two-point, uniform, blend, and linear crossover.

Genetic Mutation. This perturbator also operates on a ranked population $\hat{X}(t) = \{\hat{x}_1, \dots, \hat{x}_N\}$, sorted by increasing cost function value. Only non-elite individuals, i.e., from index $\lceil p_e N \rceil$ to N , are subject to mutation, where $p_e \in [0, 1]$ denotes the elite fraction [67]. A candidate solution is obtained as:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{m} \odot \vec{x}_n(t) + \alpha(1 - \vec{m}) \odot \vec{r}, \quad (2.18)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is the step size, \vec{r} is a random vector (commonly uniform $\mathcal{V}(-1, 1)$, normal $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, or symmetric Lévy $\mathcal{L}(1.5)$), and $\vec{m} = H(p_m - \vec{q})$ is the mask vector built from a mutation probability $p_m \in (0, 1]$ with $\vec{q} \sim \mathcal{V}(0, 1)$.

Differential Mutation. This perturbator generates a candidate solution as:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{m} + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m (\vec{x}_{z_{2m-1}}(t) - \vec{x}_{z_{2m}}(t)), \quad (2.19)$$

where \vec{m} is the target vector defined by the chosen mutation scheme, $M \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ is the number of differential perturbations, and $\alpha_m \in (0, 3)$ is the scaling factor. Indices z_i are distinct integers uniformly sampled from $\{1, \dots, N\}$, where N is the population size. Typical schemes include *rand*, *best*, *current*, *current-to-best*, *rand-to-best*, and *rand-to-best-and-current* [68].

Differential Crossover. This perturbator is typically applied after the Differential Mutation [68]. The candidate solution is obtained as:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{m} \odot \vec{y}_n + (1 - \vec{m}) \odot \vec{x}_n(t), \quad (2.20)$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard-Schur product, and $\vec{m} \in \mathbb{Z}_2^D$ is the crossover mask vector computed as $\vec{m} = H(p_{CR} - \vec{r})$, with H being the element-wise Heaviside step function ($H(0) = 1$) and $\vec{r} \sim \mathcal{V}(0, 1)$. Typical crossover types include *binomial* and *exponential*.

Swarm Dynamic. This perturbator updates the candidate position as [69]:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \vec{v}_n(t), \quad (2.21)$$

where $\vec{v}_n(t)$ denotes the velocity of the n -th agent, computed as

$$\vec{v}_n(t) = \alpha_0 \vec{v}_n(t-1) + \alpha_1 \phi_1 \vec{r}_1 \odot (\vec{x}_{n,*}(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)) + \alpha_2 \phi_2 \vec{r}_2 \odot (\vec{x}_*(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)). \quad (2.22)$$

Here, $\alpha_i \in (0, 1]$ are scaling coefficients, $\phi_1, \phi_2 \in (0, 4]$ are the self and swarm confidence coefficients, and $\vec{r}_j \sim \mathcal{V}(0, 1)$ are i.i.d. random vectors. The term $\vec{v}_n(t-1)$ is the previous velocity, while $\vec{x}_{n,*}(t)$ and $\vec{x}_*(t)$ denote the personal best and global best solutions, respectively.

Common variants include the *inertial approach*, where α_0 is the inertial weight, and the *constricted approach*, where all coefficients are scaled by a constriction factor χ .

Firefly Dynamic. This perturbator generates a candidate solution as [70]:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \alpha_0 \vec{r} + \alpha_1 \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq n}}^N H(- (I_k - I_n)) (\vec{x}_k(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)) e^{-\alpha_2 \|\vec{x}_k(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)\|_2^2}, \quad (2.23)$$

where $\alpha_0, \alpha_1 \in (0, 1]$ and $\alpha_2 \in [0, 1000]$ are scaling parameters, $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the ℓ^2 -norm, \vec{r} is a random vector sampled from $\mathcal{V}(-0.5, 0.5)$ (or similar distributions), and $I_n = f(\vec{x}_n)$ is the light intensity of agent n .

Spiral Dynamic. This perturbator generates a candidate solution as [71]:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_*(t) - \vec{r} \odot \mathbf{R}_D(\theta) \cdot (\vec{x}_n(t) - \vec{x}_*(t)), \quad (2.24)$$

where $\vec{x}_*(t)$ is the rotation center, $\theta \in (0^\circ, 360^\circ)$ is the rotation angle, and \vec{r} is a random vector sampled from $\mathcal{V}(r_0 - \sigma_r, r_0 + \sigma_r)$, with $r_0 \in (0, 1)$ as the convergence rate (central radius) and $\sigma_r \in [0, \min\{r_0, 1 - r_0\}]$. The matrix $\mathbf{R}_D(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ is a D -dimensional rotation matrix, commonly expressed as the product of all two-dimensional rotation matrices $\mathbf{R}_{i-j}(\theta)$ associated with the $D(D-1)/2$ coordinate planes.

Central Force Dynamic. This perturbator generates a candidate solution as [72]:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \frac{1}{2} \vec{a}_n(t) \Delta t^2, \quad (2.25)$$

where $\Delta t = 1$ is the time step and $\vec{a}_n(t) \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is the acceleration of agent n , calculated as

$$\vec{a}_n(t) = \alpha_0 \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq n}}^N H(M_k(t) - M_n(t)) (M_k(t) - M_n(t))^{\alpha_1} \frac{\vec{x}_k(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)}{\|\vec{x}_k(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)\|_2^{\alpha_2}}. \quad (2.26)$$

Here $M_n = f(\vec{x}_n(t))$ is the mass of agent n , $\alpha_0 \in (0, 0.01]$ is the gravitational constant, $\alpha_1 \in (0, 0.01]$ and $\alpha_2 \in (1, 2)$ are scaling factors, and $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the ℓ^2 -norm.

Gravitational Search. The candidate solution is updated as [73]:

$$\vec{y}_n = \vec{x}_n(t) + \vec{r}_0 \odot \vec{v}_n(t) + \vec{a}_n(t), \quad (2.27)$$

with velocity

$$\vec{v}_n(t) = \vec{r} \odot \vec{v}_n(t-1) + \vec{a}_n(t), \quad (2.28)$$

and acceleration

$$\vec{a}_n(t) = G(t) \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq n}}^N M_k(t) \vec{r}_k \odot \frac{\vec{x}_k(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)}{\|\vec{x}_k(t) - \vec{x}_n(t)\|_2 + \varepsilon_g}. \quad (2.29)$$

Here, $G(t) = \alpha_0 e^{-\alpha_1 t}$ is the gravitational factor, and the masses are

$$M_n(t) = \frac{f(\vec{x}_o(t)) - f(\vec{x}_n(t))}{N f(\vec{x}_o(t)) - \sum_{k=1}^N f(\vec{x}_k(t))}, \quad (2.30)$$

where $\vec{x}_o(t)$ denotes the worst solution at iteration t .

2.4.2 Selectors

We consider four representative selection operators: Direct, Greedy, Probabilistic, and Metropolis. Given the current position $\vec{x}_n(t)$ and a candidate $\vec{y}_n(t)$, with fitness values $f(\vec{x}_n)$ and $f(\vec{y}_n)$, the update is defined by $\Delta f_n(t) = f(\vec{y}_n) - f(\vec{x}_n(t))$ according to the following rules.

Direct selection. The new position is assigned directly:

$$\vec{x}_n(t+1) = \vec{y}_n. \quad (2.31)$$

Greedy selection. The new position is accepted only if it improves the current one:

$$\vec{x}_n(t+1) = \begin{cases} \vec{y}_n, & \text{if } \Delta f_n \leq 0, \\ \vec{x}_n(t), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.32)$$

Probabilistic selection. Worsened positions may also be accepted with probability $p_s \in [0, 1]$:

$$\vec{x}_n(t+1) = \begin{cases} \vec{y}_n, & \text{if } (\Delta f_n \leq 0) \vee (p_s < r), \\ \vec{x}_n(t), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2.33)$$

where $r \sim \mathcal{V}(0, 1)$ and $p_s = 0.5$ in our experiments.

Metropolis selection. Worsened solutions are accepted with a probability derived from simulated annealing:

$$\vec{x}_n(t+1) = \begin{cases} \vec{y}_n, & \text{if } (\Delta f_n \leq 0) \vee \left(r < e^{-\frac{\Delta f_n(t)}{k_B \Theta(t)}} \right), \\ \vec{x}_n(t), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2.34)$$

where $r \sim \mathcal{V}(0, 1)$, $k_B = 1.0$ is the Boltzmann constant, and the temperature decreases as $\Theta(t) = \Theta_0(1 - c)^t$, with $\Theta_0 = 1000$ and $c = 0.01$.

2.5 Population and Search Dynamics

Other fundamental concepts for understanding this thesis are *Population*, *Best solution*, *Exploration*, and *Exploitation*, which are introduced in the following subsections.

2.5.1 Population

In most MHs, the search process relies on a population of candidate solutions that evolves through iterations. Each element of this population represents a potential solution within the search space, and the algorithm applies perturbation and selection mechanisms to guide their improvement. In this context, it is also useful to define the notion of the best solution, which corresponds to the candidate with the lowest objective value in a given set. Formally, let $\mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the search space of an optimization problem and $f : \mathfrak{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ minimize its objective function. The population at iteration t is defined as

$$X(t) = \{\vec{x}_1(t), \vec{x}_2(t), \dots, \vec{x}_N(t)\} \subset \mathfrak{X}, \quad (2.35)$$

where $\vec{x}_n(t) \in \mathfrak{X}$ denotes the n -th candidate solution at iteration t .

A subset $Z(t) \subseteq \mathfrak{X}$ can be considered to represent different contexts of the search process. For example, $Z(t)$ may correspond to the entire population ($Z(t) = X(t)$), the neighborhood of a candidate ($Z(t) = Y_n(t)$), or the historical trajectory of a single agent ($Z(t) = \{\vec{x}_n(0), \dots, \vec{x}_n(t)\}$). Therefore, The best solution within $Z(t)$ is then defined as

$$\vec{x}_*(t) = \arg \min_{\vec{x} \in Z(t)} f(\vec{x}). \quad (2.36)$$

Once these concepts have been established, we can better describe the two complementary forces that govern the search process in MHs: exploration and exploitation, which are defined below.

2.5.2 Exploration and Exploitation

The effectiveness of an optimization algorithm, in our context, MHs algorithms, is determined not only by its ability to evaluate solutions, but also by the strategy it uses to traverse the search space. Therefore, two fundamental and complementary concepts present in any optimization process are Exploration and Exploitation [27, 74].

Exploration refers to the algorithm’s ability to find diverse and unvisited regions of the search space. Its purpose is to avoid premature convergence by maintaining diversity among candidate solutions, which increases the probability of locating the global optimum, if possible [75].

Exploitation denotes the algorithm’s ability to intensify the search in promising areas that already contain good-quality solutions.

This process accelerates convergence and refines the accuracy of the solutions obtained.

Exploration and exploitation are characteristics of the algorithm’s dynamics that can determine its success [74]. However, the central question arises as to what the appropriate ratio of exploration and exploitation should be for an algorithm to maintain [75]. Furthermore, due to the wide variety of existing search strategies, with different dynamics, it is not possible to establish a universal rate that is valid for all methods [76]. Rather, the design of an MH requires an understanding of the internal mechanisms (i.e., SOs) that each algorithm implements to traverse the search space and how they influence this balance. For instance, some population-based algorithms employ selection strategies that favor the survival of outstanding individuals in the next generation, as in elitist or greedy selection. These strategies reinforce exploitation and accelerate convergence, but at the cost of reducing population diversity. In methods such as Differential Evolution (DE) [54], greedy selection ensures that new solutions are accepted only if they improve upon existing ones, thereby imposing selective pressure that strengthens exploitation. In contrast, other algorithms such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [69] or Spiral Dynamics (SD) [77] do not rely on greedy selection. Instead, their search dynamics are driven by attraction operators (or perturbators) that guide the population toward prominent individuals or the current global best solution. This mechanism emphasizes intensification while implicitly preserving diversity through the collective movement of agents.

In the literature, we can find quantitative measures of population diversity as possible indicators of exploration capacity. These descriptors, based on traditional statistics like variance and mean distances between pairs, often fail to capture the actual spatial distribution of solutions, leading to misinterpretations of search dynamics [75]. In contrast, volume-based diversity metrics assess how individuals are distributed concerning the problem domain, offering a clearer signal of whether exploration remains active or is collapsing into exploitation [78]. While not definitive, such approaches provide a practical means of monitoring and adjusting diversity, thereby supporting a dynamic balance between broad search and focused refinement.

2.6 Automated Algorithm Design

The design of algorithms can be formally expressed as an optimization problem, often a combinatorial one. Given a problem domain \mathcal{X} , the objective is to identify an algorithm \mathcal{A} from a design space \mathcal{S} that maximizes its expected performance across instances of the problem and repeated executions [79],

$$\mathfrak{A}_* = \operatorname{argmax}_{\mathfrak{A} \in \mathfrak{H}} \mathbb{E}_{(\mathfrak{X}, f)} [\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{P}} [Q(\mathfrak{A} | \mathfrak{X}, f)]] , \quad (2.37)$$

where \mathfrak{A} represents the algorithm to be designed, and \mathfrak{H} denotes the available design space containing all feasible algorithmic configurations that can be instantiated. The pair (\mathfrak{X}, f) defines a problem instance, where \mathfrak{X} is the search space and f the objective function. The term $Q(\mathfrak{A} | \mathfrak{X}, f) : \mathfrak{H} \times \mathfrak{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a performance function that quantifies the quality of the designed algorithm \mathfrak{A} when applied to a given problem. Finally, \mathcal{P} represents the stochastic conditions under which the algorithm operates (e.g., initialization, random seeds, or sampling), so the inner expectation $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{P}}$ averages the results over multiple runs, while the outer expectation $\mathbb{E}_{(\mathfrak{X}, f)}$ generalizes the performance across different problem domains.

Now, let us apply Equation (2.37) to the case of Metaheuristics (MHs). The domain of high-level problems is formed by the available heuristic space \mathfrak{H} . Each candidate algorithm is an MH, which follows the structure shown in Equation (2.9), with a certain cardinality, and the low-level task is to solve the optimization problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) . By solving this low-level optimization problem in different replicas, we will obtain the value of the performance metric value. Under these identifications, the overall objective of the AAD is reduced to the Metaheuristic Composition Optimization Problem (MCOP), a specific instance of GCOP [29, 30], as follows:

$$\text{MH}_* = \operatorname{argmax}_{\text{MH} \in \mathbb{H}^\varpi, \vec{x} \in \mathfrak{X}} \{Q(\text{MH} | (\mathfrak{X}, f))\}, \quad (2.38)$$

where $\text{MH} \in \mathbb{H}^\varpi$ denotes a candidate metaheuristic configuration constructed from the feasible set of heuristic components within the heuristic space \mathbb{H}^ϖ , and ϖ represents its cardinality, that is, the number of SOs composing it. The performance function $Q(\text{MH} | (\mathfrak{X}, f)) : \mathbb{H}^\varpi \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ quantifies the ability of a given candidate MH to solve the optimization problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) . Once the MH is obtained, however, the configuration of its internal hyperparameters becomes a crucial aspect, since the final performance of the algorithm strongly depends on the proper tuning of these parameters. Consequently, a model-based approach is used to address this problem [79], where the objective is to tune the hyperparameters associated with this customized MH. This optimization process can be formally defined by

$$\Theta_* = \operatorname{argmax}_{\Theta \in \Psi} \{Q(\text{MH}, \Theta | \mathfrak{X})\}, \quad (2.39)$$

where Θ represents the set of hyperparameters, and Ψ denotes the hyperparameter search space. A more comprehensive strategy involves addressing both components simultaneously: selecting the SOs and dynamically adjusting their associated hyperparameters. This unified formulation is expressed as

$$(\text{MH}_*, \Theta_*) = \operatorname{argmax}_{\text{MH} \in \mathbb{H}^\varpi, \Theta \in \Psi} \{Q(\text{MH}, \Theta | \mathfrak{X})\}, \quad (2.40)$$

where Genetic Programming (GP) is a suitable solution to this problem.

The automated design of MH algorithms can be described in four stages, as shown in Figure 2.3. First, the high-level design space \mathfrak{H} enumerates admissible building blocks such as computational primitives, search operators and selectors, and hyperparameters. Then, the design strategy specifies an encoding of this space (for example, graphs, trees, sequences, or grammars) together with a search procedure that selects and assembles building blocks into candidate algorithms. Next, the performance evaluation strategy defines how quality is measured by specifying the metric Q , the computational budget, the set of instances, and the number of replications, and aggregates performance across repeated runs to produce feedback that steers the high-level search. Finally, the ultimate goal of automatically designing an MH algorithm is to solve a specific problem; this is formalized as the low-level problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) , which provides the information used by the metric Q to assess how well the problem was solved. As shown in Figure 2.3, once a candidate produced by the design strategy is available, it is executed on (\mathfrak{X}, f) to obtain the observed performance, which is passed to the evaluation module and fed back to guide the design strategy. From this perspective, the core AAD blocks are the design space, the design strategy, and the performance evaluation strategy, while the low-level problem acts as a fourth, external block that conditions the evaluation.

Figure 2.3: Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) workflow for metaheuristics (based on the work conducted by Zhao et al. [79]).

2.6.1 Design Space

In the context of AAD, the design space specifies the set of admissible elements from which an algorithm can be constructed. In the literature, two main perspectives have been established [61, 79, 80]. The first corresponds to primitive-based design spaces, where the elementary building blocks are computational primitives such as arithmetic, trigonometric, or statistical functions, as well as basic combinatorial or computational instructions. These primitives can be composed to form higher-level operators, which in turn serve as functional components of metaheuristics. Representative categories and examples of such primitives are summarized in Table 2.4.

Different representations have been explored for this type of space. The tree-based approach,

Table 2.4: Representative categories of computational primitives used in AAD design spaces.

Category	Examples
Arithmetic	$+$, $-$, $*$, $/$
Trigonometric	$\sin(\cdot)$, $\cos(\cdot)$, $\tan(\cdot)$, $\arctan(\cdot)$
Statistical	$\max\{\cdot\}$, $\text{mean}(\cdot)$, $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$, $\text{std}(\cdot)$
Combinatorial	swap, duplicate, roll, add, remove
Computational	crossover, greedy selection, mutation

typically in the form of GP-style binary trees [81], encodes primitives as non-terminal nodes and recursively builds operators until the root node is reached. More recent works have applied this representation to evolve operators for deep learning architectures, such as CNNs for image classification and video generation [82]. Alternatively, linear array representations execute primitives sequentially according to their position in the array [83, 84], offering simpler manipulation but reduced expressiveness. While primitive-based spaces are powerful in their ability to generate entirely novel operators, they also enlarge the search space considerably and increase the complexity of the automated design task.

The second perspective is the operator-based design space, which is more compact and directly employs algorithmic operators (e.g., crossover, mutation, or selection) as the building blocks of MHs [7, 27, 50]. In this case, the primitives are already abstracted into functional components, and the design task focuses on selecting operators, arranging them into sequences, and configuring their hyperparameters. Several encoding schemes have been proposed, including linear arrays with categorical identifiers [80], graph-based structures [26], and GP-style trees where non-terminals correspond to operators. Compared with primitive-based spaces, this representation reduces complexity and leverages existing algorithmic knowledge, but it can introduce bias toward already known algorithmic structures.

In this thesis, we adopt the operator-based perspective. The design space is instantiated as the heuristic space, composed of twelve perturbators and their associated selectors and hyperparameters, implemented in the CUSTOMHyS framework [35]. This choice balances tractability and diversity, enabling systematic exploration of MH compositions across different cardinalities. Within this framework, categorical parameters define the rules governing the operator’s action (e.g., crossover scheme), while numerical parameters control execution values (e.g., mutation or crossover rates). For instance, a DE-based mutation perturbator can be instantiated with schemes such as *rand*, *best*, or *rand-to-best*, each regarded as a distinct search operator within the same family. Although twelve perturbators initially define the heuristic space, its diversity can be expanded by adjusting hyperparameters and configurations, allowing for richer algorithmic exploration without reverting to the more granular primitive-based level.

2.6.2 Design Strategy

The design strategy defines how candidate MHs are generated and explored within the design space, which in our case corresponds to the heuristic space. In the literature, two main

perspectives have been established. The first corresponds to model-free AAD, where MHs are constructed by directly combining available operators and arranging them in sequences without assuming prior knowledge of how these design choices affect performance. Search is conducted in a trial-and-error fashion using mechanisms such as randomized search, evolutionary schemes, or hyper-heuristics that adaptively select operators from the heuristic space [6, 85]. The strength of this approach lies in its flexibility to explore novel compositions, although it requires a large computational budget and may struggle to exploit conditional dependencies between operators and hyperparameters efficiently.

The second perspective is model-based AAD, in which the emphasis shifts to learning and exploiting information about the relationship between design choices and algorithmic performance. Once a candidate MH structure has been obtained, its effectiveness depends heavily on the adequate tuning of hyperparameters. To this end, surrogate models and machine learning techniques are employed to approximate the performance landscape, reducing the number of evaluations required to identify promising configurations [28].

In this thesis, the generation of MHs is generally approached from a model-free perspective, emphasizing the direct exploration of operator compositions with different cardinalities. Nevertheless, once a candidate structure is available, in some cases, the process can be complemented by model-based strategies aimed at tuning hyperparameters and selectors more efficiently. This flexibility enables the automated design pipeline to rely on model-free exploration when novelty is the priority, while still allowing for the incorporation of model-based refinements when performance gains justify the additional modeling effort.

2.6.3 Performance Evaluation Strategy

Performance in AAD can be assessed through several complementary metrics, including solution quality, running time, and anytime behavior. Solution quality is the most widely used criterion and typically evaluates the objective function value achieved within a fixed computational budget [86]. Running time, often expressed in function evaluations, measures the effort required to reach a given quality threshold. In contrast, anytime metrics, such as the area under the performance curve or hypervolume indicators, provide a more comprehensive view of progress over time [87]. In more complex scenarios, multiple objectives may be considered jointly, for example, optimizing solution quality while maintaining diversity or reducing memory usage [88].

In this thesis, performance evaluation is based mainly on solution quality and repeatability across independent runs. This process is computationally demanding, as each candidate MH must be executed multiple times to obtain statistically reliable estimates. However, it provides fair and reproducible comparisons across different algorithmic designs.

2.6.4 Problem

The final component of the AAD workflow corresponds to the low-level problem (\mathcal{X}, f) , which provides the domain where candidate MHs are executed and evaluated. This block does not belong to the design process itself, but instead conditions the evaluation, as the

quality of an MH can only be assessed with respect to a specific optimization task. In this thesis, the low-level problems are real-world problems. In the first phase, we address electrical engineering problems, followed by some biomedical applications.

2.7 Summary

In summary, this chapter establishes the mathematical and algorithmic foundations required for the development of this thesis. First, the optimization problem is formally defined, distinguishing between low-level continuous problems and high-level combinatorial tasks related to heuristic configuration. Then, heuristics are introduced and classified into simple heuristics, metaheuristics, and hyper-heuristics, highlighting their hierarchical roles in the search process. The section also presents representative search operators (perturbators and selectors) that drive the dynamics of classical metaheuristics. Additionally, the concepts of population, best solution, exploration, and exploitation are discussed as fundamental forces that shape search dynamics. Finally, this chapter presents the automatic algorithm design as an optimization problem and addresses relevant concepts, including the design space, design strategy, and performance evaluation strategy.

Chapter 3

High-Level Approaches for Automated Algorithm Design

This chapter describes the design frameworks for metaheuristic algorithms employed in this thesis. For clarity, the work is structured into two main domains. The first, the high-level domain, corresponds to Automated Algorithm Design (AAD), where the objective is to define a computational strategy capable of exploring the design space and selecting search operators from the available heuristic set. The second, the low-level domain, corresponds to application-specific optimization tasks, which are introduced and analyzed in subsequent chapters.

3.1 Design Space

The design space considered in this thesis originates from the collection of twelve search operators, or perturbators, summarized in Table 3.1. Each perturbator is characterized by its hyperparameters, variation schemes, and the selector mechanisms that determine how solutions are chosen after their application. This compact set was extracted from classical MHs and constitutes the functional backbone of the heuristic space [7].

From this basis, the heuristic space is systematically expanded by combining perturbators with categorical variations and selectors. For instance, the differential mutation operator admits multiple instantiations (*rand*, *best*, *current-to-best*, among others), each of which can be paired with selectors such as Direct, Greedy, Metropolis, or Probabilistic. Applying this principle across all perturbators leads to a comprehensive collection of 205 search operators, as detailed in Table 3.2.

This expansion not only enlarges the design space but also enriches its behavioral diversity. Certain operators, such as Random Search, Random Flight, or Spiral Dynamics, are primarily oriented toward exploration, favoring global sampling of the search domain to avoid premature convergence. Others, such as Genetic Crossover and Genetic Mutation variants, are more exploitative, refining promising solutions and accelerating convergence once a promising region is identified. A third group, including Swarm Dynamics or Firefly Dynamics, exhibits

Table 3.1: Search operators that make up the heuristic feasible space. Perturbators are detailed, including their respective hyper-parameters, variations, and selectors.

Perturbator	Hyper-parameters	Variation parameters
Central Force	gravity, alpha, beta, dt	–
Random Flight	scale, beta	Random Distribution Function
Random Search	scale	Random Distribution Function
Spiral Dynamic	radius, angle, sigma	–
Random Sample	–	Random Distribution Function
Swarm Dynamic	factor, self-confidence, swarm-confidence	Velocity approach
Firefly Dynamic	alpha, beta, gamma	Random Distribution
Genetic Mutation	scale, elite rate, mutation rate	Random Distribution
Genetic Crossover	mating pool factor	Pairing Scheme, Crossover Scheme
Gravitational Search	gravity, alpha	–
Local Random Walk	probability, scale	Random Distribution Function
Differential Mutation	num random values, factor	Mutation Scheme
Selector		
Direct	–	–
Greedy	–	–
Probabilistic	probability	–
Metropolis	Boltzmann constant, max. temperature	–

a dual role, balancing exploration and exploitation through adaptive parameters (e.g., swarm confidence, attractiveness, or distribution functions). This balance is critical in MH design, as it ensures both diversity preservation and effective convergence toward high-quality solutions. Moreover, the incorporation of multiple selectors further modulates these behaviors. Greedy selectors tend to bias exploitation by retaining the best solutions deterministically, while Probabilistic and Metropolis selectors introduce stochastic acceptance criteria that enhance exploration. Direct selection, in contrast, enforces structural simplicity, allowing operators to act without filtering. The combination of these perturbators with selectors generates a design space that is both large, diverse, and computationally manageable, providing a wide range of SOs for the automated design of MHs.

Having established the rationale and composition of the heuristic space, it is important to note that this space was not employed uniformly across all applications addressed in this thesis. Instead, different subsets of search operators were defined according to the requirements and complexity of each problem. This strategy enabled both a controlled analysis of operator tendencies in simpler scenarios and the use of larger, more expressive collections in complex problems. Concretely, four distinct sets were employed: a reduced collection of 24 SOs for the Automatic Voltage Regulator (AVR) with a classical PID controller (see Table 3.3, Chapter 4), the complete space of 205 SOs for the AVR with a Fractional order PID (FOPID) controller and the DC-DC Buck-Boost converter with an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller (ASMC) (see Table 3.2, Chapter 4), a compact set of 12 SOs for the melanoma image segmentation problem (see Table 3.4, Chapter 5, and an intermediate set of 30 SOs for the parameter identification of the fractional Zener viscoelastic model (see Table 3.5, Chapter 6).

Table 3.2: Collection of 205 search operators. Each row groups four versions of the same perturbator varying the selector (Direct, Greedy, Metropolis, Probabilistic), except Random Search, which uses a predefined Greedy selector.

IDs	Perturbator	Variation Parameters
0	Random Search	–
1-4	Central Force Dynamic	–
5-28	Differential Mutation	/rand/, /best/, /current/, /current-to-best/, /rand-to-best/, /rand-to-best-and-current/
29-40	Firefly Dynamic	Uniform distribution; Normal distribution; Lévy distribution
41-56	Genetic Single-point Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing; Roulette Wheel Pairing; Random Pairing; Tournament Pairing
57-72	Genetic Two-points Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing; Roulette Wheel Pairing; Random Pairing; Tournament Pairing
73-88	Genetic Uniform Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing; Roulette Wheel Pairing; Random Pairing; Tournament Pairing
89-104	Genetic Blend Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing; Roulette Wheel Pairing; Random Pairing; Tournament Pairing
105-120	Genetic Linear Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing; Roulette Wheel Pairing; Random Pairing; Tournament Pairing
121-132	Genetic Mutation	Uniform distribution; Normal distribution; Lévy distribution
133-136	Gravitational Search	–
137-148	Random Flight	Lévy distribution; Uniform distribution; Normal distribution
149-160	Local Random Walk	Uniform distribution; Normal distribution; Lévy distribution
161-164	Random Sample	–
165-176	Random Search	Uniform distribution; Normal distribution; Lévy distribution
177-180	Spiral Dynamic	–
181-192	Inertial Swarm Dynamic	Uniform distribution; Normal distribution; Lévy distribution
193-204	Constricted Swarm Dynamic	Uniform distribution; Normal distribution; Lévy distribution

3.2 Design Strategy

In this thesis, three high-level design strategies are employed to explore the heuristic space or design space and tailor MHs to specific problems: the Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH), the Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH), and the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS). SAHH adapts the simulated annealing principle to sequences of search operators, utilizing neighborhood perturbations and probabilistic acceptance to strike a balance between exploration and exploitation. PRHH adopts a population-based randomization scheme, in which candidate MHs are generated by uniform sampling of the heuristic space, and the best-performing candidates are retained to guide the search. RCHH-LS follows a constructive perspective, incrementally building candidate MHs through random sampling and refining them with local

Table 3.3: Short collection of 24 search operators employed for AVR+PID controller tuning.

Ids.	Perturbator	Variation parameters	Selector
h_0	Central Force Dynamic	–	Direct
h_1	Central Force Dynamic	–	Greedy
h_2	Differential Mutation	/current-to-best/	Greedy
h_3	Differential Mutation	rand-to-best-and-current	Direct
h_4	Firefly Dynamic	Uniform distribution	Direct
h_5	Firefly Dynamic	Uniform distribution	Greedy
h_6	Genetic Uniform Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing	Greedy
h_7	Genetic Uniform Crossover	Rank Weighting Pairing	Direct
h_8	Genetic Mutation	Uniform distribution	Direct
h_9	Genetic Mutation	Uniform distribution	Greedy
h_{10}	Gravitational Search	–	Direct
h_{11}	Gravitational Search	–	Greedy
h_{12}	Random Flight	Lévy distribution	Direct
h_{13}	Random Flight	Lévy distribution	Greedy
h_{14}	Local Random Walk	Normal distribution	Direct
h_{15}	Local Random Walk	Normal distribution	Greedy
h_{16}	Random Sample	–	Direct
h_{17}	Random Sample	–	Greedy
h_{18}	Random Search	Uniform distribution	Greedy
h_{19}	Random Search	Uniform distribution	Direct
h_{20}	Spiral Dynamic	–	Direct
h_{21}	Spiral Dynamic	–	Greedy
h_{22}	Inertial Swarm Dynamic	Uniform distribution	Greedy
h_{23}	Constricted Swarm Dynamic	Uniform distribution	Greedy

Table 3.4: Collection of 12 search operators employed as the heuristic space for melanoma segmentation. Each entry includes the perturbator, its variation parameters, and the default selector.

Ids.	Perturbator	Hyper-parameter	Selector
h_1	central force dynamic	gravity, alpha, beta, dt	all
h_2	differential mutation	num_rands, factor	greedy
h_3	firefly dynamic	alpha, beta, gamma	all
h_4	genetic crossover	mating_pool_factor	all
h_5	genetic mutation	scale, elite, mutation	greedy
h_6	gravitational search	gravity, alpha	all
h_7	random flight	scale, beta	greedy
h_8	local random walk	probability, scale	greedy
h_9	random sample	–	all
h_{10}	random search	scale	greedy
h_{11}	spiral dynamic	radius, angle, sigma	all
h_{12}	swarm dynamic	factor, conf_1, conf_2	all

search, thus combining diversification and intensification. Each of these strategies was applied and validated in real engineering applications. In all cases, the objective is to address the

Table 3.5: Collection of search operators utilized to obtain the tailored MH. Each operator is described by its variation parameters, hyper-parameters, and associated selector.

Ids.	Perturbator	Variation Parameters	Hyper-parameters	Selector
h_0	Central Dynamic	Force –	gravity=0.001, alpha=0.01, beta=1.5, dt=1.0	all
h_1	Central Dynamic	Force –	gravity=0.001, alpha=0.01, beta=1.5, dt=1.0	greedy
h_2	Differential Mutation	Mutation Scheme ^{b₁}	num_rands=1, factor=1.0	all
h_3	Differential Mutation	Mutation Scheme ^{b₁}	num_rands=1, factor=1.0	greedy
h_4	Differential Mutation	Mutation Scheme ^{b₂}	num_rands=1, factor=1.0	all
h_5	Differential Mutation	Mutation Scheme ^{b₂}	num_rands=1, factor=1.0	greedy
h_6	Firefly Dynamic	Distribution ^{a₂}	alpha=1.0, beta=1.0, gamma=100.0	all
h_7	Firefly Dynamic	Distribution ^{a₂}	alpha=1.0, beta=1.0, gamma=100.0	greedy
h_8	Genetic Crossover	PS ^{c₁} , CM ^{d₃}	mating_pool_factor=0.4	all
h_9	Genetic Crossover	PS ^{c₁} , CM ^{d₃}	mating_pool_factor=0.4	greedy
h_{10}	Genetic Crossover	PS ^{c₃} , CM ^{d₃}	mating_pool_factor=0.4	all
h_{11}	Genetic Crossover	PS ^{c₃} , CM ^{d₃}	mating_pool_factor=0.4	greedy
h_{12}	Genetic Mutation	Distribution ^{a₂}	scale=1.0, elite_rate=0.1, mutation_rate=0.25	all
h_{13}	Genetic Mutation	Distribution ^{a₂}	scale=1.0, elite_rate=0.1, mutation_rate=0.25	greedy
h_{14}	Gravitational Search	–	gravity=1.0, alpha=0.02	all
h_{15}	Gravitational Search	–	gravity=1.0, alpha=0.02	greedy
h_{16}	Local Random Walk	Distribution ^{a₁}	probability=0.75, scale=1.0	all
h_{17}	Local Random Walk	Distribution ^{a₁}	probability=0.75, scale=1.0	greedy
h_{18}	Random Sample	–	–	all
h_{19}	Random Sample	–	–	greedy
h_{20}	Random Search	Distribution ^{a₂}	scale=1.0	greedy
h_{21}	Random Search	Distribution ^{a₂}	scale=0.01	greedy
h_{22}	Spiral Dynamic	–	radius=0.9, angle=22.5, sigma=0.1	all
h_{23}	Spiral Dynamic	–	radius=0.9, angle=22.5, sigma=0.1	greedy
h_{24}	Swarm Dynamic	Distribution ^{a₂} , SWA ^{e₁}	factor=0.7, self_conf=2.54, swarm_conf=2.56	all
h_{25}	Swarm Dynamic	Distribution ^{a₂} , SWA ^{e₁}	factor=0.7, self_conf=2.54, swarm_conf=2.56	greedy
h_{26}	Swarm Dynamic	Distribution ^{a₂} , SWA ^{e₂}	factor=1.0, self_conf=2.54, swarm_conf=2.56	all
h_{27}	Swarm Dynamic	Distribution ^{a₂} , SWA ^{e₂}	factor=1.0, self_conf=2.54, swarm_conf=2.56	greedy
h_{28}	Random Flight	Distribution ^{a₃}	scale=1.0, beta=1.5	all
h_{29}	Random Flight	Distribution ^{a₃}	scale=1.0, beta=1.5	greedy

Distribution: ^{a₁} Gaussian, ^{a₂} Uniform, ^{a₃} Lévy; Mutation Scheme: ^{b₁} current-to-best, ^{b₂} rand-to-best-and-current; Pairing Scheme (PS): ^{c₁} Cost, ^{c₃} Tournament; Crossover Mechanism (CM): ^{d₃} Uniform; Swarm Approach (SWA): ^{e₁} Inertial, ^{e₂} Constriction.

Metaheuristic Composition Optimization Problem (MCOP), that is, to identify the sequence of SOs that maximizes performance for a given problem. The following subsections provide a detailed description of each implementation.

3.2.1 Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH)

The first design strategy used in this thesis is the Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH), initially proposed by Cruz-Duarte et al. [7]. In its original formulation, SAHH had been applied only to reference benchmark functions; in this work, it is extended and integrated into real engineering applications.

Within SAHH, the design strategy specifies how candidate MHs are obtained and modified during the search process. In this formulation, an MH is represented as a sequence of SOs, and the exploration of the design space is achieved by applying a set of neighborhood actions A to such sequences. These actions operate as search primitives at the sequence level, i.e., they perturb the structure of the current candidate and produce a neighbor while preserving feasibility constraints, such as the maximum cardinality ϖ_{\max} . The complete set A consists of ten elementary but effective operations: add, remove, perturb, swap, shift-left, shift-right, roll, mirror, restart, and noop, summarized in Table 3.6. It is important to note that these actions are not part of the heuristic design space itself; instead, they belong to the search strategy, providing the mechanisms by which the available heuristic space is explored.

Table 3.6: Neighborhood actions $a \in A$ applied to the candidate sequence $\vec{h}(t) = (h_1, \dots, h_v)$. Each action produces a neighbor \vec{h}' while preserving feasibility under cardinality constraints.

Action	Description	Transformation Rule
add	Inserts a new operator $h_g \in \mathfrak{H}$ at random position $j \sim U\{1, v+1\}$.	$\vec{h}' = (h_1, \dots, h_v)$, $\#\vec{h}' = v+1$
remove	Removes one operator from random position $j \sim U\{1, v\}$, if $v > v_l$.	$\vec{h}' = (h_1, \dots, h_v)$, $\#\vec{h}' = v-1$
perturb	Modifies parameters and/or selector of one operator $h_j \in \vec{h}(t)$ at $j \sim U\{1, v\}$.	$\#\vec{h}' = v$
swap	Interchanges two operators $h_g, h_j \in \vec{h}(t)$ at random positions $i \neq j$.	$\#\vec{h}' = v$
shift	Circularly shifts the entire sequence one position left or right.	$\vec{h}' = (h_2, \dots, h_v, h_1)$ or $\vec{h}' = (h_v, h_1, \dots, h_{v-1})$
roll	Performs a circular rotation of $k \sim U\{1, v-1\}$ positions.	$\vec{h}' = (h_{1+k}, \dots, h_v, h_1, \dots, h_k)$
mirror	Reverses the order of the sequence.	$\vec{h}' = (h_v, h_{v-1}, \dots, h_1)$
restart	Discards $\vec{h}(t)$ and generates a new random sequence with cardinality $v' \sim U\{v_l, \varpi_{\max}\}$.	$\vec{h}' \sim U(\mathfrak{H})$
noop	Preserves the current sequence unchanged.	$\vec{h}' = \vec{h}$

At each iteration, an action $a \in A$ is uniformly sampled and applied to the current sequence \vec{h} , producing a neighbor \vec{h}' . The resulting candidate is then evaluated on the low-level problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) to obtain a performance score Q_c . If Q_c improves on the current value Q , the new sequence is accepted; otherwise, it may still be accepted with a probability

$$P = \exp\left(-\frac{Q_c - Q}{\Theta}\right), \quad (3.1)$$

where Θ denotes the current temperature. This acceptance rule, known as the Metropolis criterion, allows occasional acceptance of worse solutions, helping the search escape local minima. The temperature Θ is gradually reduced according to a cooling schedule $\Theta \leftarrow \Theta(1 - \delta)$, which controls the transition from exploration to exploitation. The process continues until Θ reaches a predefined minimum value Θ_{\min} or a stagnation threshold n_{\max} is exceeded.

The overall procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1. The algorithm starts with the random initialization of a candidate sequence of search operators \vec{h} , sampled from the heuristic space \mathfrak{H}_o . At each iteration, an action $a \in A$ (e.g., add, remove, swap, etc.) is selected uniformly at random and applied to \vec{h} to generate a neighbor candidate \vec{h}_c .

3.2.2 Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH)

The second design strategy considered in this thesis is the Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH). In this approach, each individual in the high-level population represents a candidate MH constructed by randomly sampling a sequence of search operators (SOs) from the feasible heuristic space \mathfrak{H} , subject to the cardinality limit ϖ_{\max} . Thus, the population at iteration η can be expressed as

$$\Psi(\eta) = \left\{ (h_{o_1}^{\eta,k}, h_{o_2}^{\eta,k}) \mid h_{o_1}^{\eta,k}, h_{o_2}^{\eta,k} \in \mathfrak{H}, o_1 \neq o_2 \right\}_{k=1}^N, \quad (3.2)$$

where N is the population size, k indices the individuals (agents), and η denotes the current HH step. Each pair of SOs defines a candidate metaheuristic, which can be rewritten in operator form as

$$\text{MH}_{\eta}^{(k)} = h_f \circ (h_{o_2}^{(\eta,k)} \circ h_{o_1}^{(\eta,k)}) \circ h_g, \quad (3.3)$$

where h_g and h_f denote the initializer and finalizer, respectively.

Each candidate $\text{MH}_{\eta}^{(k)}$ is then evaluated on the low-level problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) to obtain a performance score. A greedy selection rule is applied, i.e., only the best-performing MH of the current population is retained, and the process advances to the next HH iteration. This strategy emphasizes exploration by generating fresh populations at each step, while exploitation is enforced by continually propagating the best candidate. The overall procedure is summarized in Algorithm 2, which formulates the generation, evaluation, and greedy selection of candidate metaheuristics at each HH iteration.

From a computational standpoint, PRHH requires additional effort compared to single-candidate strategies such as SAHH. Since each iteration involves generating and evaluating an entire population of N candidate MHs, the evaluation cost grows proportionally to N . However, this overhead is compensated by the ability to compare multiple proposals in parallel and retain only the one with the best performance at each step. In this way, the strategy increases the coverage of the heuristic space and reduces the risk of premature convergence to suboptimal sequences.

Algorithm 1 Automated Design of Metaheuristics based on Simulated Annealing.

Require: Low-level domain \mathfrak{X} and objective $f(\vec{x})$; heuristic space \mathfrak{H}_o , initializer h_g , finalizer h_f , performance metric $\text{perf}(X_*)$, population size N , action set A , initial temperature Θ_0 , minimal temperature Θ_{\min} , cooling rate δ , max cardinality ϖ_{\max} , max iterations t_{\max} , stagnation threshold n_{\max} .

Ensure: Best metaheuristic $\langle h_g, \vec{h}_*, h_f \rangle$

```
1:  $\vec{h} \leftarrow \text{INIT}(\mathfrak{H}_o) \triangleright$  Initialize with uniformly random heuristics
2:  $n \leftarrow 0, \Theta \leftarrow \Theta_0$ 
3:  $Q \leftarrow \text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(\vec{h})$ 
4:  $\vec{h}_* \leftarrow \vec{h}, Q_* \leftarrow Q$ 
5: while  $\Theta > \Theta_{\min}$  and  $n \leq n_{\max}$  do
6:    $a \leftarrow \text{Choose}(A) \triangleright$  Randomly choose an action considering cardinality constraints
7:    $\vec{h}_c \leftarrow a\{\vec{h}\} \triangleright$  Apply the action to obtain a neighbor
8:    $Q_c \leftarrow \text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(\vec{h}_c) \triangleright$  Evaluate the candidate metaheuristic on  $(\mathfrak{X}, f)$ 
9:    $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 
10:  if  $r \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1) \leq \exp(-(Q_c - Q)/\Theta)$  then  $\triangleright$  Metropolis acceptance
11:     $\vec{h} \leftarrow \vec{h}_c; Q \leftarrow Q_c; n \leftarrow 0$ 
12:    if  $Q > Q_*$  then
13:       $\vec{h}_* \leftarrow \vec{h}; Q_* \leftarrow Q$ 
14:    end if
15:  end if
16:   $\Theta \leftarrow \Theta(1 - \delta) \triangleright$  Cooling schedule
17: end while
18: return  $\langle h_g, \vec{h}_*, h_f \rangle$ 

19: function  $\text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(\vec{h})$ 
20:    $X_* \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
21:   for  $r = 1$  to  $N_r$  do
22:      $\vec{x}_{r,*} \leftarrow \text{EVALMH}(\vec{h}) \triangleright$  Use  $\langle h_g, \vec{h}, h_f \rangle$  to solve  $(\mathfrak{X}, f)$ 
23:      $X_* \leftarrow X_* \cup \{\vec{x}_{r,*}\}$ 
24:   end for
25:   return  $\text{perf}(X_*)$ 
26: end function

27: function  $\text{EVALMH}(\vec{h})$ 
28:    $t \leftarrow 0$ 
29:    $X \leftarrow \{h_g\{\mathfrak{X}\} \mid n = 1, \dots, N\} \triangleright$  Initialize population
30:    $F \leftarrow \{f(\vec{x}_n) \mid \vec{x}_n \in X\}$ 
31:    $\vec{x}_* \leftarrow \vec{x}_k \in X$  with  $k = \text{argmin}\{F\}$ 
32:   while  $h_f\{\vec{x}_*\}$  and  $t < t_{\max}$  do
33:      $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
34:     for  $o = 1$  to  $\varpi$  do
35:        $(h_p, h_s) \leftarrow h_o \in \vec{h}$ 
36:        $(X, F) \leftarrow h_p\{X\}$ 
37:        $\vec{x}_* \leftarrow h_s\{X\}$ 
38:     end for
39:   end while
40:   return  $\vec{x}_*(\varpi)$ 
41: end function
```

3.2.3 Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS)

The third design strategy considered in this thesis is the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS). In this approach, candidate MHs are constructed by randomly sampling sequences of SOs from the heuristic space \mathfrak{H} , subject to the maximum cardinality constraint ϖ_{\max} . Formally, at each HH iteration t , a candidate is

Algorithm 2 Automated Design of Metaheuristics based on Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic.

Require: Low-level domain \mathfrak{X} and objective $f(\vec{x})$; heuristic space \mathfrak{H} , initializer h_g , finalizer h_f , performance metric $\text{perf}(X_*)$, population size N ;

1: sequence cardinality $k \leq \varpi_{\max}$, max HH iterations T .

Ensure: Best metaheuristic $\langle h_g, \vec{h}_*, h_f \rangle$

```

2:  $\vec{h}_* \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;  $Q_* \leftarrow -\infty$ 
3: for  $\eta = 1$  to  $T$  do
4:    $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \{\text{SAMPLESEQUENCE}(\mathfrak{H}, k)\}_{n=1}^N$ 
5:   Evaluate each  $\vec{h} \in \mathcal{P}$ :  $Q(\vec{h}) \leftarrow \text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(\vec{h})$ 
6:    $\vec{h}^\dagger \leftarrow \text{argmax}_{\vec{h} \in \mathcal{P}} Q(\vec{h})$ 
7:   if  $Q(\vec{h}^\dagger) > Q_*$  then
8:      $\vec{h}_* \leftarrow \vec{h}^\dagger$ ;  $Q_* \leftarrow Q(\vec{h}^\dagger)$ 
9:   end if
10: end for
11: return  $\langle h_g, \vec{h}_*, h_f \rangle$ 

12: function  $\text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(\vec{h})$ 
13:    $X_* \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
14:   for  $r = 1$  to  $N_r$  do
15:      $\vec{x}_{r,*} \leftarrow \text{EVALMH}(\vec{h})$ 
    ▷ Use  $\langle h_g, \vec{h}, h_f \rangle$  to solve  $(\mathfrak{X}, f)$ 
16:      $X_* \leftarrow X_* \cup \{\vec{x}_{r,*}\}$ 
17:   end for
18:   return  $\text{perf}(X_*)$ 
19: end function

20: function  $\text{EVALMH}(\vec{h})$ 
21:    $t \leftarrow 0$ 
22:    $X \leftarrow \{h_g\{\mathfrak{X}\} \mid n = 1, \dots, N\}$ 
    ▷ Initialize population
23:    $F \leftarrow \{f(\vec{x}_n) \mid \vec{x}_n \in X\}$ 
24:    $\vec{x}_* \leftarrow \vec{x}_k \in X$  with  $k = \text{argmin}\{F\}$ 
25:   while  $h_f\{\vec{x}_*\}$  and  $t < t_{\max}$  do
26:      $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
27:     for  $o = 1$  to  $\varpi$  do
    ▷ Apply the  $\varpi = \#\vec{h}$  search operators
28:        $(h_p, h_s) \leftarrow h_o \in \vec{h}$ 
29:        $(X, F) \leftarrow h_p\{X\}$ 
30:        $\vec{x}_* \leftarrow h_s\{X\}$ 
31:     end for
32:   end while
33:   return  $\vec{x}_*(\varpi)$ 
34: end function

```

initialized as

$$\vec{h}^{(t,0)} \sim \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{H}, \varpi), \quad \text{s.t. } \vec{h}_i^{(t,0)} \neq \vec{h}_j^{(t,0)} \quad \forall i \neq j, \quad (3.4)$$

where $\mathcal{U}(\cdot)$ denotes a uniform sampling process over the heuristic space and the corresponding MH is defined as

$$\text{MH}^{(t,0)} = \langle h_g, \vec{h}^{(t,0)}, h_f \rangle, \quad (3.5)$$

where h_g and h_f denote the initializer and finalizer, respectively. The quality of this candidate is assessed through the performance metric Q , which combines the median and interquartile range of the best solutions found in N_r independent runs.

To improve upon the initial configuration, a local search is applied to $\vec{h}^{(t,0)}$ that generates a neighbor sequence $\vec{h}^{(t,LS)}$ by applying one of two actions: swap, which exchanges the positions of two randomly chosen SOs, or replace, which substitutes one SO with another sampled from $\mathfrak{S} \setminus \vec{h}^{(t,0)}$. The resulting neighbor is expressed as

$$\mathbf{MH}^{(t,LS)} = \langle h_g, \vec{h}^{(t,LS)}, h_f \rangle, \quad (3.6)$$

and is re-evaluated to obtain $Q^{(t,LS)}$. A greedy rule is then applied to select the best candidate within the current iteration:

$$\mathbf{MH}^{(t,final)} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{MH} \in \{\mathbf{MH}^{(t,0)}, \mathbf{MH}^{(t,LS)}\}} Q(\mathbf{MH} \mid \mathfrak{X}), \quad (3.7)$$

and, if its performance improves over the incumbent best, the global record (\vec{h}_*, Q_*) is updated accordingly. The full procedure, including random construction, evaluation, local search, and global update, is summarized in Algorithm 3.

After completing T HH iterations, the best sequence \vec{h}_* is subjected to a post-optimization stage focused on hyperparameter refinement. Let $\Theta \in \Psi_{\vec{h}_*}$ denote the numerical parameters of the SOs in \vec{h}_* . These are optimized through a model-based search with Optuna, expressed as

$$\Theta^* = \arg \min_{\Theta \in \Psi_{\vec{h}_*}} Q(\langle h_g, \vec{h}_*, h_f, \Theta \rangle \mid \mathfrak{X}), \quad (3.8)$$

where Q denotes the performance metric employed to assess the quality of each configuration. The precise definition of this metric and its role in hyperparameter optimization will be provided in the following section. This final refinement ensures that the resulting MH combines a robust structural configuration with tuned hyperparameters, highlighting that the effectiveness of the high-level strategy arises not from its complexity, but from the richness of the SO space and the accurate adjustment of its parameters.

3.3 Performance Evaluation Strategy

At the core of all high-level strategies, the quality of a candidate MH is assessed by executing it on the low-level problem (\mathfrak{X}, f) through the function EvalPerformance. This routine runs the MH $\langle h_g, \vec{h}, h_f \rangle$ multiple times under independent initializations and aggregates the results into a robust performance metric defined as

$$Q(\mathbf{MH} \mid \mathfrak{X}) = -(\text{med}(F_h) + \text{iqr}(F_h)), \quad (3.9)$$

with

$$F_h = \{ f(\vec{x}_{r,*}) \mid \vec{x}_{r,*} \in X_*, r = 1, \dots, N_r \}, \quad (3.10)$$

Algorithm 3 Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search

Require: The problem's domain \mathcal{X} and its objective function $f(\vec{x})$. Heuristic space \mathcal{H} , initializer h_g , finalizer h_f , performance metric $Q(\text{MH} \mid \mathcal{X}, f)$, and population size N . Maximum cardinality ϖ_{\max} , maximum number of iterations t_{MH} for MH candidate, and maximum number of iterations T for HH.

Ensure: $\text{MH}_o^{\text{best}}$ and tuned hyperparameters Θ^* .

```

1:  $\text{MH}_o^{\text{best}} \leftarrow \emptyset$  and  $Q(\text{MH}_o^{\text{best}} \mid \mathcal{X}, f) \leftarrow \infty$  ▷ Initialization
2: for  $t = 1, \dots, T$  do
3:    $h_o^{(t,0)} \leftarrow \text{RANDOMCONSTRUCTION}(\mathcal{H}, \varpi_{\max})$  ▷ Random Construction
4:    $\text{MH}_o^{(t,0)} = \langle h_g, h_o^{(t,0)}, h_f \rangle$  ▷ Define a candidate metaheuristic
5:    $Q^{(t,0)} \leftarrow \text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(h_o^{(t,0)})$  ▷ Evaluation
6:    $h_o^{(t,LS)} \leftarrow \text{LOCALSEARCH}(h_o^{(t,0)})$  ▷ Local Search
7:    $\text{MH}_o^{(t,LS)} = \langle h_g, h_o^{(t,LS)}, h_f \rangle$ 
8:    $Q^{(t,LS)} \leftarrow \text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(h_o^{(t,LS)})$ 
9:    $k_* = \operatorname{argmin}_{k \in \{0, \text{LS}\}} \{Q^{(t,k)}\}$  ▷ Choose between  $\text{MH}_o^{(t,0)}$  and  $\text{MH}_o^{(t,LS)}$ 
10:   $\text{MH}_o^{(t,\text{final})} \leftarrow \text{MH}_o^{(t,k_*)}$ ,  $Q^{(t,\text{final})} \leftarrow Q^{(t,k_*)}$ 
11:  if  $Q^{(t,\text{final})} < Q^{(\text{best})}$  then
12:     $\text{MH}_o^{\text{best}} \leftarrow \text{MH}_o^{(t,\text{final})}$ ,  $Q^{(\text{best})} \leftarrow Q^{(t,\text{final})}$ 
13:     $\vec{h}_* \leftarrow$  sequence from  $\text{MH}_o^{\text{best}}$  ▷ Keep best structure
14:  end if
15: end for ▷ — Hyperparameter optimization stage (Optuna) —

16: Define search space from the SOs in  $\vec{h}_*$ .
17: Initialize Optuna study with TPE sampler and pruning policy.
18: for  $b = 1, \dots, B$  do
19:    $\Theta_b \leftarrow \text{OPTUNASAMPLE}(\Psi_{\vec{h}_*})$ 
20:    $Q_b \leftarrow \text{EVALPERFORMANCE}((\vec{h}_*, \Theta_b))$ 
21:    $\text{OPTUNAREPORT}(Q_b)$ 
22: end for
23:  $\Theta^* \leftarrow \text{OPTUNABESTPARAMS}$ 
24: return  $\langle h_g, \vec{h}_*, h_f, \Theta^* \rangle$ ,  $Q(\vec{h}_*, \Theta^* \mid \mathcal{X})$ 

25: function  $\text{EVALPERFORMANCE}(\vec{h})$  ▷ Initialize the set of solutions
26:    $X_* \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
27:   for  $r = 1$  to  $N_r$  do
28:      $\vec{x}_{r,*} \leftarrow \text{EVALMH}(\vec{h})$ 
29:      $X_* \leftarrow X_* \cup \{\vec{x}_{r,*}\}$  ▷ Save current best
30:   end for
31:   return  $\text{perf}(X_*)$ 
32: end function

33: function  $\text{EVALMH}(\vec{h})$  ▷ Initialize iteration counter
34:    $t \leftarrow 0$ 
35:    $X \leftarrow \{h_g\{\mathcal{X}\} \mid \forall n = 1, \dots, N\}$ 
36:    $F \leftarrow \{f(\vec{x}_n) \mid \forall \vec{x}_n \in X\}$ 
37:    $\vec{x}_* \leftarrow \vec{x}_k \in X$  since  $k = \operatorname{argmin}\{F\}$ 
38:   while  $h_f\{\vec{x}_*\}$  and  $t < t_{\text{MH}}$  do
39:      $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
40:     for  $o = 1$  to  $\varpi$  do
41:        $(h_p, h_s) \leftarrow h_o \in \vec{h}$ 
42:        $(X, F) \leftarrow h_p\{X\}$ 
43:        $\vec{x}_* \leftarrow h_s\{X\}$ 
44:     end for
45:   end while
46:   return  $\vec{x}_*(\varpi)$ 
47: end function

```

where med and iqr denote the median and interquartile range, respectively, of the set of best objective values F_h obtained across N_r replications.

This formulation favors MHs that consistently yield high-quality solutions with low variability, thereby balancing accuracy and robustness.

Once the custom MH with the best performance (MH_*) has been identified by the high-level design strategy, its execution can be described as follows. MH_* sequentially applies the search operators (SOs) contained in the optimal sequence $\vec{h}_* = (h_{o_1}, \dots, h_{o_\varpi})$, preserving both their order and cardinality ϖ . Each SO encapsulates its perturbator, selector, and hyperparameters, as determined during the automated design process. The initializer h_g generates the initial population over the domain \mathfrak{X} , while the finalizer h_f enforces the stopping criterion (e.g., maximum iterations or convergence). In this way, MH_* provides a unified and flexible structure for solving (\mathfrak{X}, f) , leveraging the sequence of operators that maximizes the performance metric.

Algorithm 4 Tailored Metaheuristic

Require: Problem domain $\mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^D$, objective function $f(\vec{x})$, search operators $h_o \in \mathfrak{H}_p$, initializer $h_g \in \mathfrak{H}_g$, finalizer $h_f \in \mathfrak{H}_f$, and population size N .

Ensure: Optimal solution \vec{x}_*

- 1: Initialize the population, $X(0) \ni \vec{x}_n(0) \leftarrow h_g\{\mathfrak{X}\}, \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
 - 2: Initialize additional features for each individual in the population
 - 3: Evaluate the population, $f_n(0) \leftarrow f(\vec{x}_n(0)), \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
 - 4: Find $\vec{x}_*(0) \leftarrow \vec{x}_k(0)$ since $k = \text{argmin}\{f_1, \dots, f_N\}$ and set $t \leftarrow 0$
 - 5: **while** $\text{Criterion}(t, \mathfrak{X}, \vec{x}_*(t), f(\vec{x}_*(t)), \dots) == \text{False}$ **do** \triangleright Finalizer, h_f
 - 6: $t \leftarrow t + 1$
 - 7: **for each** $\text{SEARCHOPERATOR} \in \{h_{76}, h_{79}, h_{195}\}$ **do**
 - 8: $X(t) \leftarrow \text{SEARCHOPERATOR}(X(t - 1))$
 - 9: Update $f_n(t), \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \vec{x}_*(t)$, and the additional information
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **end while**
 - 12: **return** $\vec{x}_* \approx \vec{x}_*(t)$
-

3.4 Problems

The validation of the proposed automated design strategies was conducted on a collection of low-level problems, each represented by a pair

$$P_i = (\mathfrak{X}_i, f_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, 5,$$

where \mathfrak{X}_i denotes the feasible search space associated with the i -th problem, and $f_i : \mathfrak{X}_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ represents its objective function to be minimized.

The set of considered problems is

$$P = \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5\}.$$

Concretely, the problems addressed were:

- P_1 – the Automatic Voltage Regulator with a classical PID controller.
- P_2 – the Automatic Voltage Regulator with a Fractional-Order PID controller.
- P_3 – the DC-DC Buck-Boost converter with an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller.
- P_4 – the segmentation of melanoma images.
- P_5 – the parameter identification of the fractional Zener viscoelastic model from AFM relaxation experiments on cancer cells.

3.5 Summary

This chapter introduced the conceptual and methodological foundations of Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) as applied to metaheuristics. The problem was first formalized as an optimization task over a design space, where the goal is to identify an MH structure MH and its associated hyperparameters Θ that maximize a performance metric Q across repeated executions on the target domain (\mathcal{X}, f) . The design space was instantiated through an operator-based representation, composed of Search Operators (SOs) characterized by their perturbators, selectors, and hyperparameters.

To explore this space, three high-level strategies were presented: the Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH), the Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH), and the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS). Each strategy defines a distinct mechanism for generating and refining candidate MHs, striking a balance between diversification and intensification at the high level. In all cases, performance evaluation relies on robust statistics, specifically the median and interquartile range of best solutions across replications, thus ensuring reproducibility and fairness in comparisons.

Finally, the low-level problems were described in a unified formalism as pairs $P_i = (\mathcal{X}_i, f_i)$, encompassing both engineering and biomedical applications. This common representation enables systematic assessment of the automated design strategies across heterogeneous domains. Overall, the chapter established the AAD workflow as a general computational framework where design space, design strategy, evaluation, and problem domain interact to yield tailored metaheuristics, setting the stage for the experimental validation presented in subsequent chapters.

Chapter 4

Automated Algorithm Design for Control Problems in Electrical Engineering

This chapter presents the application of Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) to representative control problems in electrical engineering. In particular, two case studies are considered: the Automatic Voltage Regulator (AVR), which is crucial for ensuring voltage stability in power generation systems, and the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter, a fundamental component in power electronics for renewable energy integration and storage applications. Both systems exhibit nonlinear dynamics, parameter uncertainties, and stringent performance requirements, making controller tuning a challenging optimization problem. Below, we will describe each of these systems in detail.

4.1 Automatic voltage regulation

The AVR is a fundamental component in the generation and distribution stages of electrical power systems [89]. Its primary function is to automatically adjust the excitation of a synchronous generator to maintain the terminal voltage at a desired reference level, even under varying operating conditions. By compensating for load fluctuations, grid disturbances, or changes in input voltage, the AVR ensures voltage stability and power quality [90]. This regulation prevents harmful variations that could compromise the performance, efficiency, and lifetime of connected equipment. From a control perspective, the AVR is commonly modeled as a fourth-order dynamic system comprising the *amplifier*, *exciter*, *generator*, and *sensor blocks*, which interact to define the system's transient and steady-state response. A basic model of the AVR can be seen in Figure 4.1.

In the initial stage, the *sensing* block (G_s) plays a fundamental role, as it provides the reference information required for all subsequent corrective actions of the AVR. Its main function is to accurately measure the instantaneous output voltage of the system. Based on this measurement, the *error signal* $e(t)$ [v] is computed as the difference between the desired reference voltage (V_{ref} [v]) and the actual output voltage (V_o [v]), which can be expressed

Figure 4.1: Automatic Voltage Regulation (AVR) system.

as:

$$e(t) = V_{\text{ref}}(t) - V_o(t), \quad (4.1)$$

this error becomes the input to the control loop and determines the magnitude of the corrective action to be applied.

According to Figure 4.1, the *amplifier* block (G_a) processes and scales the error signal to regulate the input power supplied to the *exciter* (G_e). The exciter, in turn, adjusts the excitation current of the *generator* (G_g), modifying the magnetic flux and consequently the generated voltage. In this context, the generator converts the available mechanical energy into electrical energy, closing the feedback loop of the AVR.

The model shown in Figure 4.1b provided the transfer function to describe mathematically the AVR system. However, a linearization process must be performed to obtain the mathematical model of each component of the AVR system, considering the relevant time constants, ignoring saturation and nonlinearities [91].

The parameter values used in this work were selected based on [91, 92] to define the transfer functions of each stage in the AVR system, as shown in Table 4.1. Lastly, the total transfer function of the AVR system is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{AVR}}(s) &= \frac{V_o(s)}{V_{\text{ref}}(s)} = \frac{G_a(s)G_e(s)G_g(s)}{1 + G_s(s)G_a(s)G_e(s)G_g(s)} \\ &= \frac{0.1s + 10}{0.0004s^4 + 0.045s^3 + 0.555s^2 + 1.51s + 11}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

In the above expression, the variable s denotes the Laplace operator, which represents a complex frequency defined as $s = \sigma + j\omega$, where σ is the real part associated with exponential growth or decay, and ω is the imaginary part related to oscillatory behavior. In control theory, the Laplace transform is widely employed to analyze and design dynamic systems, as it allows converting differential equations in the time domain into algebraic equations in the frequency domain. Thus, transfer functions such as $G_{\text{AVR}}(s)$ describe the relationship between the input and output signals of the system, facilitating the study of stability and transient response.

Table 4.1: Subsystems and their transfer functions of the Automatic Voltage Regulation (AVR) implemented in this work [92, 93].

AVR Subsystem	Transfer Function	Gain Interval	Time Constant Interval [s]	Used Values
Amplifier	$G_a(s) = \frac{K_a}{1 + s\tau_a}$	$10 < K_a < 400$	$0.02 < \tau_a < 0.1$	$K_a = 10$ $\tau_a = 0.1$
Exciter	$G_e(s) = \frac{K_e}{1 + s\tau_e}$	$1.0 < K_e < 400$	$0.1 < \tau_e < 1.0$	$K_e = 1.0$ $\tau_e = 0.4$
Generator	$G_g(s) = \frac{K_g}{1 + s\tau_g}$	$0.7 < K_g < 1.0$	$1.0 < \tau_g < 2.0$	$K_g = 1.0$ $\tau_g = 1.0$
Sensor	$G_s(s) = \frac{K_s}{1 + s\tau_s}$	$K_s = 1.0$	$0.001 < \tau_s < 0.06$	$K_s = 1.0$ $\tau_s = 0.01$

Figure 4.2 shows the uncontrolled transient response of the AVR system. As can be observed, the uncontrolled response exhibits several undesirable behaviors, including a high overshoot ($M_p = 67.42\%$), a long settling time ($T_s = 6.971$ s), a rise time ($T_r = 0.754$ s), and a considerable steady-state error ($E_{ss} = 0.090$ p.u.). These performance indices clearly indicate that, in its open-loop configuration, the AVR system cannot guarantee voltage stability or acceptable dynamic performance. Such characteristics are inappropriate for practical electrical systems, where large overshoots, slow settling dynamics, and steady-state deviations can compromise power quality and reduce the reliability of connected equipment. Therefore, the design and implementation of a suitable controller becomes essential to guide the system dynamics and achieve the required stability and robustness.

Figure 4.2: Uncontrolled output voltage of the AVR system. It also details the overshoot (M_p [%]), settling time (T_s [s]), rise time (T_r [s]), and steady-state error (E_{ss} [p.u.]).

4.1.1 PID and Fractional-Order PID Controllers

Considering the previously exposed features of the AVR system, a high-performance controller is required to improve the transient state behavior and eliminate the steady-state error. In practice, the design of such controllers must ensure a fast response with minimal overshoot, reduced settling time, and robustness against load variations and external disturbances. Among the control strategies proposed in the literature, two of the most representative approaches are the Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) [94, 95] controller and its extension, the Fractional-Order PID (FOPID) [96]. Subsequently, both controllers are formally defined, and their role in the AVR regulation problem is discussed.

Classical PID Controller. The PID controller is one of the most widely used strategies in industrial control systems due to its simple structure, intuitive design, and ease of implementation [94]. As its name indicates, this controller combines three fundamental control actions in response to the error signal, which is defined as the difference between the reference input and the measured output of the sensor [95]. The transfer function of the PID controller can be expressed as

$$G_{\text{PID}}(s) = K_p + K_i \frac{1}{s} + K_d s, \quad (4.3)$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d represent the proportional, integral, and derivative gains, respectively. Each of these terms contributes to the overall control action in a complementary manner. The proportional gain K_p reduces the present error by providing an immediate corrective action. The integral gain K_i eliminates steady-state error by accumulating the error over time and adjusting the control signal accordingly. Finally, the derivative gain K_d predicts the future behavior of the error by considering its rate of change, which improves the damping of the system response.

Fractional-Order PID Controller. Fractional Calculus is a generalization of classical calculus that extends the concepts of differentiation and integration to non-integer orders [96]. Fractional calculus has proven to be especially useful in engineering, as it allows the modeling of systems whose dynamics cannot be accurately described using only integer-order operators. Formally, the fractional integro-differential operator is expressed as ${}_t \mathcal{D}_t^\mu$, where the order $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$ can take arbitrary real values. Depending on the sign of μ , this operator represents a fractional derivative ($\mu > 0$) or a fractional integral ($\mu < 0$).

Several equivalent definitions exist in the literature, such as the Grünwald–Letnikov, Riemann–Liouville, and Caputo formulations [97, 98], each presenting a trade-off between mathematical generality and practical applicability. The Grünwald–Letnikov and Riemann–Liouville definitions are commonly used for theoretical analysis and numerical approximation, but they require functions to be differentiable over the entire domain, which can limit their applicability to real engineering systems. In contrast, the Caputo formulation is particularly suitable for control applications, as it allows the use of physically meaningful initial conditions expressed in terms of integer-order derivatives, at the cost of a slightly higher computational complexity. A particularly convenient property of the Caputo operator appears under the Laplace transform for

causal systems with zero initial conditions ($t_0 = 0^+$), where

$$\mathcal{L}\{ {}_0\mathcal{D}_t^\mu f(t) \}(s) = s^\mu F(s), \quad (4.4)$$

with $F(s) = \mathcal{L}\{f(t)\}(s)$ and s the Laplace operator. This result provides a direct pathway for incorporating fractional operators into control system design.

Building upon this theory, FOPID controller has been introduced as an extension of the classical PID. By replacing the integer-order integral and derivative actions with their fractional counterparts of orders λ and μ , respectively, the FOPID gains additional flexibility in shaping the closed-loop response [99]. Its transfer function is given by

$$G_{\text{FOPID}}(s) = K_p + K_i s^{-\lambda} + K_d s^\mu, \quad (4.5)$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains.

Inclusion of fractional orders λ and μ enriches the tuning process by providing two additional degrees of freedom, which improve robustness, disturbance rejection, and transient performance compared to conventional PID. As a result, the FOPID controller has attracted increasing interest for the regulation of systems with complex or highly non-linear dynamics, such as the AVR [100, 101].

4.2 DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters

Buck–Boost converters are power electronic devices that regulate voltage levels in direct current (DC) systems. They can operate in two modes: one involves increasing the output voltage (Boost) while the other involves reducing it (Buck). This particularity makes them indispensable elements in integrating renewable energies [102] and battery energy storage [103]. In addition, Buck–Boost converters are convenient when the input voltage may fluctuate, ensuring a stable output voltage for the correct operation of the connected load. Figure 4.3 depicts the circuit diagram of a Buck–Boost converter. The converter is composed of an uncontrolled switching diode (D_s), a controlled switch (S_w), a capacitor (C [F]), an inductor (L [H]), and a resistor (R [Ω]) as load. The input voltage (V_g [V]) is supplied to the converter and can be stepped up or down depending on the switching state of S_w . The output voltage (V_o [V]) is regulated to maintain a stable value, which can be set at levels above or below the source voltage and is often of reversed polarity.

Figure 4.3: Basic circuit diagram of a DC-DC Buck–Boost converter.

The operation principle of this converter is summarized with two possible states driven by Pulse Width Modulation (PWM):

- State 1: $S_w = \text{ON}$ and $D_s = \text{OFF}$, when $nT < t \leq (n + \mathcal{D})T$.
- State 2: $S_w = \text{OFF}$ and $D_s = \text{ON}$, when $(n + \mathcal{D})T < t \leq (n + 1)T$.

Where n is the switching cycle index, T represents the switching period, and \mathcal{D} is the PWM duty cycle.

Therefore, properly adjusting the switch operating point allows us to obtain an output voltage level within the desired limits while ensuring continuous switching between states 1 and 2.

The set of coupled differential equations presented in (4.6) describes the dynamic behavior of the Buck–Boost converter.

$$\begin{aligned} L \frac{dI_L}{dt} &= \mathcal{D} V_g - (1 - \mathcal{D}) V_C, \\ C \frac{dV_C}{dt} &= -\frac{V_C}{R} + (1 - \mathcal{D}) I_L, \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

where V_C [V] is the capacitor voltage, I_L [A] represents the inductor current, and the converter output is $V_o = (I_L - I_C)R$ [V]. It is essential to note that before the Laplace transform $\mathcal{L}\{\cdot\}$ was applied, the model was scaled and nondimensionalized to simplify the analysis.

$$\hat{G}(s) = \frac{k_\tau \mathcal{D}(1 - \mathcal{D})}{s^2 + k_\tau s + (1 - \mathcal{D})^2 k_\tau}, \quad (4.7)$$

since $k_\tau = L/R^2C$ [s^{-1}]. All systems and signals in the s -domain we use the hat notation, i.e., $\hat{G}(s) \equiv \mathcal{L}\{G(t)\}$.

While the linearization process simplifies the analysis and enables the derivation of the transfer function shown in (4.7), it inherently excludes certain nonlinear and dynamic behaviors of the Buck–Boost converter. Notably, the linear model does not capture real-time switching effects and high-frequency transient dynamics intrinsic to DC-DC converters. Additionally, the model does not account for external disturbances or noise that may arise in practical implementations, such as electrical noise or input voltage fluctuations. Despite these limitations, the linearized model provides a sufficiently accurate representation to analyze the system's dynamic response and evaluate the performance of the proposed control scheme.

Table 4.2 displays the component parameters considered to conduct numerical simulations for this case study.

Table 4.2: Configuration of component values in the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter circuit.

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
Source voltage, V_g	25 V	Filter capacitor, C	150 μF
Load resistor, R	20 Ω	Duty cycle, \mathcal{D}	60%
Filter inductor, L	3 mH	Switching frequency, f_s	40 kHz

Figure 4.4 presents the open-loop response of the Buck–Boost converter face to a pulse input using a \mathcal{D} of 60%.

The transient response oscillates with an unacceptable overshoot ($M_p = 87.78\%$) and a long settling time ($T_s = 31.90$ ms). In particular, this overshoot should be corrected for most applications because it may harm electrical components and Printed Circuit Board (PCB) track insulation and reset unprotected event-driver microcontrollers.

Figure 4.4: Open-loop response of the Buck–Boost converter for a pulse-shape input. The main signal features, including the overshoot (M_p), which represents how much of the reference voltage (Ref) has been exceeded, and the settling time (T_s), which indicates the amount of time required for the system to be stable, are presented.

Figure 4.4 also suggests that the Buck–Boost converter requires a control system to drive the response to the voltage user-defined reference. However, the control designer faces several uncertainties, such as inaccurate estimation of model parameters, nonlinearities, and external perturbations involving induced noise and currents that may destabilize the system and make this task challenging. Therefore, we decided to implement an SMC, which is robust against perturbations and disturbances, ensuring convergence in a finite time.

4.2.1 Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers

Sliding Mode Control (SMC) is widely recognized for its robustness against parameter variations and external disturbances. However, one of its main drawbacks is the so-called chattering effect, characterized by high-frequency oscillations in the control signal. This phenomenon may lead to undesirable behavior, such as excessive actuator wear, unbounded control gains, or even instability in practical implementations.

Additionally, it is important to note that the mathematical model of the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter typically assumes ideal circuit components, neglecting parasitic effects such as inductor resistance or capacitor leakage. While these simplifications facilitate the controller’s design and analysis, they may omit relevant dynamics that affect efficiency and stability in real-world converters.

To mitigate these issues, this work employs an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller (ASMC) [104, 105], which incorporates an adaptive gain mechanism capable of adjusting its magnitude in real time to compensate for uncertainties and perturbations. The general scheme of the controlled system is presented in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: DC-DC Buck–Boost converter driven by an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller.

The design begins by defining the error signal (e) and its time derivative,

$$e = V_{\text{ref}} - V_o, \quad (4.8)$$

$$\dot{e} = \dot{V}_{\text{ref}} - \dot{V}_o, \quad (4.9)$$

where V_o is the output voltage (main state variable), and V_{ref} is the voltage reference. Both quantities are normalized to ensure dimensionless operation.

Next, a sliding surface is introduced to specify the desired tracking dynamics. This manifold is commonly expressed as [104]

$$\sigma = \dot{e} + \lambda e, \quad (4.10)$$

where λ is a positive design constant that determines the convergence speed. The SMC objective is to enforce $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ and $\dot{\sigma} \rightarrow 0$ in finite time, ensuring robust tracking performance even under parametric variations.

The adaptive sliding mode control law is defined as

$$u = -2k|\sigma|^{1/2} \text{sign}(\sigma) - \frac{k^2}{2}\sigma, \quad (4.11)$$

where k is the adaptive gain. Its evolution follows the adaptive law

$$\dot{k} = \alpha^{1/2}|\sigma|^{1/2} - \beta^{1/2}k^2, \quad (4.12)$$

with α and β being positive design parameters. This formulation allows k to be continuously adjusted, enhancing robustness and reducing the detrimental effects of chattering while preserving the system's stability.

4.3 Methodology

This section presents the methodology used to design and evaluate tailored MHs algorithms for practical electrical control engineering applications. The overall framework adopts a hierarchical perspective: the high-level domain focuses on the automatic design of MHs through an HH, while the low-level domain addresses specific optimization problems. In particular, two case studies are considered in this section: (i) the tuning of PID and FOPID controllers for an AVR system, and (ii) the tuning of ASMC for DC-DC Buck–Boost converters. Each case study is described below.

4.3.1 Automatic Voltage Regulator with PID and FOPID

The first low-level problem considered in this section is the tuning of PID and FOPID controllers for an AVR system. The AVR is a classical benchmark in control engineering due to its nonlinearities and sensitivity to parameter variations. Its main purpose is to regulate the terminal voltage of a synchronous generator by adjusting the excitation voltage, thereby maintaining stability and robustness under load changes.

Figure 4.6 shows the block diagram of the AVR system, which consists of four main components: amplifier, exciter, generator, and sensor. A parameterized transfer function represents each block according to the standard values found in the literature [92]. The controller (PID or FOPID) is connected in cascade with the AVR system to improve transient and steady-state performance.

Figure 4.6: Block diagram of the AVR system with classical PID and FOPID controllers. The tailored MH tuning the controller parameters $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ by minimizing the objective function, which combines transient and steady-state performance indicators such as overshoot (M_p), steady-state error (E_{ss}), settling time (T_s), and rise time (T_r).

AVR with PID Controller

In the first case, the classic PID controller is tuned using the custom MH (MH_*) obtained through the HH framework described in section 3.2.1. The objective function is defined in terms of the Integral Time Absolute Error (ITAE) index, complemented by other time domain metrics that are critical in evaluating the performance of control systems, such as stabilization time (T_s), rise time (T_r), overshoot (M_p), and steady-state error (E_{ss}). Thus, a composite cost function combining these indicators was designed, expressed as

$$f = \alpha \times (M_p + E_{ss}) + (1 - \alpha) \times (T_s - T_r) + \gamma \times \text{ITAE}, \quad (4.13)$$

where the weighting coefficients $\alpha = 0.3$ and $\gamma = 0.1$ were determined experimentally after several preliminary tests.

In this case, each combination of gains in the decision vector modifies the overall dynamics of the AVR system and, consequently, alters its control characteristics in terms of stability, response speed, and accuracy. Thus, the decision vector for this problem is defined in a three-dimensional design space, given by

$$\vec{x} = (K_p, K_i, K_d)^T \in \mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (4.14)$$

where the parameters are restricted to the interval $(0, 100]$.

The methodology applied to the AVR system with a classical PID controller was structured in three main stages.

Stage 1: High-level design of the tailored MH. The first stage focused on the HH process to obtain the customized MH (MH_*). To this end, each candidate MH was evaluated with a population size of 25 individuals and a maximum of 40 iterations. The HH search was configured with a maximum of 10 steps, and each candidate MH was executed 20 independent times to ensure statistical robustness. In total, 61 HH runs were carried out, producing 61 candidate MHs for the AVR PID tuning problem. For each candidate, the operator cardinality was constrained to lie between two and three. In this case, the HH search was restricted to a short collection of 24 search operators, as summarized in Table 3.3. The main goals of this stage were: (i) to identify the tailored MH_* that achieved the best performance in tuning the PID controller, and (ii) to analyze the selection frequency of the different operator families within the HH framework.

Stage 2: PID tuning. Once MH_* was obtained, it was applied to the low-level problem. The tailored MH_* was employed to tune the PID controller by optimizing the design vector \vec{x} , thus minimizing the cost function in (4.13). This procedure enabled the identification of the controller gains that provided the best trade-off between transient response and steady-state accuracy.

Stage 3: Comparative analysis. Finally, to validate the effectiveness of the tailored MH_* , its performance was compared against several well-established MHs algorithms reported in the literature, namely the Tree Seed Algorithm (TSA) [92], the Improved Kidney

Algorithm (IKA) [93], Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [106], and Differential Evolution (DE) [106].

AVR with FOPID Controller

The methodology applied to the AVR system with a FOPID controller was divided into three main stages. Before describing each of these stages, it is necessary to clarify some fundamental aspects of the FOPID controller. This controller extends the classical PID structure by introducing two additional parameters, the fractional orders λ and μ , which provide greater flexibility to balance robustness and transient performance.

Accordingly, the low-level optimization problem is defined in a five-dimensional design space, such as

$$\vec{x} = (K_p, K_i, K_d, \lambda, \mu)^T \in \mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^5, \quad (4.15)$$

with $K_p \in (0.1, 1.5]$, $K_i \in (0.01, 1]$, $K_d \in (0.01, 1]$, and $\lambda, \mu \in [0.7, 1.5]$. Besides, the objective function associated with this problem is given by

$$f = \min \{ \alpha (M_p + E_{ss}) + (1 - \alpha) (T_s - T_r) + \Omega, \quad \Omega \}, \quad (4.16)$$

since α is the regularization parameter determined after extensive experimentation and predefined as $\alpha = 0.3$, furthermore, Ω is the penalty value that, for simulation purposes, is 500 when the system is unstable and zero when it is stable.

Stage 1: High-level design of the tailored MH. The first stage was devoted to the HH process to obtain the customized MH (MH_{*}). For this purpose, a collection of 205 search operators (SOs) was employed as the heuristic space, combining the perturbators and selectors listed in Table 3.2 with predefined variation parameters and hyperparameters. For the HH process, a population size of 20 and a maximum of 30 iterations were defined for each candidate MH. In addition, 10 steps of HH were executed, and each candidate MH was tested 20 times to evaluate its performance according to the metric in (3.9).

Stage 2: FOPID tuning. Once MH_{*} was obtained, it was applied to the low-level problem. The FOPID controller was tuned in 50 independent runs, storing the controller parameters and fitness values in each case. This procedure allowed us to assess the repeatability of the optimization process and select the best-performing controller among the replicates.

Stage 3: Comparative and robustness analysis. Finally, the last stage consisted of three complementary steps. First, a comparative analysis was carried out with four state-of-the-art approaches reported in the literature, namely Cuckoo Search (CS) [107], Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [108], Improved Marine Predators Algorithm (MP-SEDA) [109], and Simulated Annealing (SA) [110]. Then, a robustness analysis was performed, in which the AVR transfer function parameters ($\tau_a, \tau_e, \tau_g, \tau_s$) were perturbed from -50% to $+50\%$ of their nominal values in increments of 25% . This

simulated significant variations in the system dynamics. Finally, a landscape analysis was conducted by varying the fractional orders λ and μ in the range $[0.5, 2]$ with an increment of 0.01, generating two-dimensional maps of overshoot and settling time.

4.3.2 DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters with Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers

In this problem, the low-level domain focuses on tuning an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller (ASMC) to regulate a DC-DC Buck–Boost converter using a custom model obtained from the HH process. The control tuning process aims to determine the optimal values of the parameters α , β , and λ , which directly influence the control law and, therefore, the transient and steady-state response of the converter (see Figure 4.7). The design vector is defined as

$$\vec{x} = (\alpha, \beta, \lambda)^\top \in \mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (4.17)$$

with $\alpha \in [0.1, 100]$, $\beta \in (0, 5]$, and $\lambda \in (0, 10]$.

Figure 4.7: Block diagram of the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter regulated by an ASMC. The sliding surface is constructed from the tracking error and its derivative, while the adaptive controller adjusts the gains (α, β) online to enhance robustness against parameter variations and external disturbances. The tailored MH tunes the controller parameters by minimizing the objective function, which integrates M_p , E_{ss} , T_s , and T_r .

For this particular case, we decided to look for the controller parameters or gains that would achieve the desired control characteristics. These characteristics are summarized in Table 4.3, which includes M_p , T_s , E_{ss} , and maximum control signal (A_{cc}).

Table 4.3: Desired control features for the dynamic response of the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter coupled with an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller.

Control Features	Symbol	Desired Value	Unit
Overshoot	M_{pd}	1	%
Settling Time	T_{sd}	0.45	ms
Steady-State Error	E_{ssd}	0	V
Max Control Signal	A_{ccd}	50	V

The objective function combines these indicators into a weighted formulation:

$$\vec{x}_* = \underset{\vec{x} \in \mathfrak{X}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ w_1 \left| \frac{M_p - M_{pd}}{M_{pd}} \right| + w_2 \left| \frac{E_{ss} - E_{ssd}}{E_{ssd} + \epsilon} \right| + w_3 \left| \frac{T_s - T_{sd}}{T_{sd}} \right| + P(A_{cc}) \right\}, \quad (4.18)$$

where $w_1 = 0.3$, $w_2 = 1.0$, and $w_3 = 0.7$ are regularization parameters, ϵ avoids division by zero when $E_{ssd} = 0$, and the penalty function is

$$P(A_{cc}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } A_{cc} \leq A_{ccd}, \\ 10, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4.19)$$

with $A_{ccd} = 50$ V being the desired maximum control signal.

Once the optimization problem is established, the methodology to solve it is divided into three stages:

Stage 1: High-level design of the tailored MH. The HH framework was employed to automatically obtain the tailored MH (MH_*). The heuristic space was the same as in the previous applications. Each candidate MH used a population of 20 individuals and a maximum of 30 iterations, while the HH search was limited to 10 steps, balancing exploration and computational cost.

Stage 2: ASMC tuning. Next, the best-performing MH_* was applied to tune the ASMC parameters (α, β, λ) according to the defined objective function. Fifty independent optimization runs were performed to evaluate repeatability and identify robust controller configurations.

Stage 3: Comparative and robustness analysis. Finally, MH_* was evaluated against both well-established and emerging MH, namely PSO, GA, L-SHADE [111], MadDE [112], Marine Predators Algorithm (MPA) [113], and Giant Trevally Optimizer (GTO) [114]. For these comparisons, the algorithm configuration provided by the MEALPY framework¹ was used to facilitate the performance evaluation in optimization problems [115]. Each method allocated a maximum of 1200 objective function

¹The MEALPY framework is freely available at <https://pypi.org/project/mealpy/>, and it was last accessed on 15 November 2024.

evaluations to ensure a fair comparison across all implemented algorithms. In addition, robustness tests were performed by perturbing converter parameters and injecting disturbances into the system, assessing sensitivity in terms of M_p , T_s , E_{ss} , and control effort.

4.4 Experimental Results

This section presents the experimental results obtained from applying the proposed methodology to two control-oriented optimization problems. First, the AVR system is analyzed with both classical PID and FOPID controllers tuned by tailored MHs. Second, a DC-DC buck converter is studied under the design of an ASMC, also optimized using the HH-based approach. In each case, the results include the identification of the tailored MHs, the evaluation of their performance, and a comparative analysis against algorithms reported in the literature.

All experiments in this study were conducted using Python version 3.9 on an ASUS TUF Gaming F17, equipped with an AMD Ryzen™ 7 Processor 5700G, featuring 8 CPU Cores, and supported by 16GB RAM, running on a 64-bit Windows 11 operating system. The HH search was implemented using a Simulated Annealing-based approach to customize MHs for solving continuous optimization problems [7]².

4.4.1 Automatic voltage regulation

This section presents the experimental results for AVR systems, considering two controllers: PID and the FOPID. The following subsections detail the tuning process and performance analysis performed for each case.

AVR with PID Controller

The first stage of the experimentation involved tuning a PID controller for the AVR system using an HH approach, as described in the previous section. A total of 61 independent runs were executed, resulting in the generation of 61 customized MHs. All the results of these tests are publicly available³.

This initial analysis focused on monitoring the occurrence of different perturbators, with the intention of identifying whether there was a tendency to favor a specific family. The cardinality of each customized MH was restricted to a minimum of two and a maximum of three perturbators. As shown in Table 4.4, the *Swarm Dynamic* family was the most frequent, with 34 occurrences (18.57%), followed by *Spiral Dynamic* with 22 occurrences (12.02%). *Differential Mutation* and *Random Flight* also exhibited a relevant presence, with 18 (9.83%) and 12 (6.55%) occurrences, respectively. In contrast, the *Central Force Dynamic* family was among the least represented, with only 3 occurrences (1.63%).

²The framework is freely available at <https://pypi.org/project/customhys/>

³The dataset is freely accessible at https://github.com/Danielfz14/Paper_1570993779_CEC_PID_AVR

These results suggest that operators associated with collective or trajectory-based search dynamics (e.g., *Swarm Dynamic* and *Spiral Dynamic*) are more frequently selected during the HH process, which could indicate a natural bias toward balancing exploration and exploitation. Meanwhile, operators such as *Central Force Dynamic*, despite their potential to diversify the search space, were scarcely selected, highlighting that the HH process did not consistently favor less common strategies. This imbalance may have implications for the diversity of MH configurations, as the dominance of certain operator families could potentially lead to performance convergence patterns, while the rare inclusion of others might generate occasional but significant outliers.

It is also important to note that in 34 cases the third perturbator was not required, meaning that the HH process favored MHs with a cardinality of two instead of three. This observation reinforces the idea that combining more operators does not necessarily translate into better results, and in some situations, a simpler configuration may provide a more effective balance between exploration and exploitation.

Table 4.4: Frequency of search operator family usage.

Operator family	SO ₁	SO ₂	SO ₃	Total
Random Search	3	2	2	7
Genetic Uniform Crossover	4	4	1	9
Differential Mutation	3	10	5	18
Random Flight	7	4	1	12
Swarm Dynamic	12	17	5	34
Spiral Dynamic	12	7	3	22
Local Random Walk	3	3	4	10
Firefly Dynamic	4	5	2	11
Genetic Mutation	5	2	1	8
Random Sample	5	3	0	8
Gravitational Search	2	3	2	7
Central Force Dynamic	1	1	1	3
None	-	-	34	34

Although operator frequency analysis provides information on the families most often selected during the HH process, it does not directly reflect their effectiveness in solving the tuning task. Therefore, beyond operator occurrence and MH cardinality, it is necessary to evaluate the overall performance achieved by the generated MHs. This performance analysis enables us to determine whether the frequent use of certain perturbators or the preference for simpler cardinalities translates into measurable improvements in the fitness values obtained. Figure 4.8 depicts a box plot of the performance distribution (3.9) across the 61 runs. The median (Q_2) was 1.0765, while the mean reached 1.4194. The maximum and minimum fitness values were 2.455 and 0.145, respectively. The first quartile (Q_1) was 0.654, and the third quartile (Q_3) was 1.416, yielding an interquartile range of 0.761. Some outliers were identified, with the largest reaching 9.325. This extreme value corresponded to an MH composed of the operators $h_o = h_0 \circ h_{14}$ (see Table 3.3), belonging to the *Central Force Dynamic* and *Local Random*

Walk families. Remarkably, the first operator is the least frequent in the entire test campaign.

Figure 4.8: Distribution of fitness values achieved by the HH process across 61 runs, including quartiles Q_1 , Q_2 , and Q_3 .

Now, examining each operator in detail, Figure 4.9 shows the trend presented by the first operator in the tailored MHs. The operators with the highest percentage of occurrences were the *Spiral Dynamic* and *Swarm Dynamic* perturbators, each with 19.7% of the total selections for the first position. The preference is to start the optimization process with operators capable of promoting broad exploration of the search space while retaining a certain level of exploitation, particularly in the case of swarm-based dynamics, which are inherently designed to balance diversification and intensification. A secondary group of operators also showed considerable presence, namely *Random Flight* (11.5%), *Random Sample* (8.2%), and *Genetic Mutation* (8.2%). Although less dominant, their inclusion as the first operator suggests that additional diversification mechanisms were still considered relevant in the early stages of the HH process. In contrast, perturbators such as *Central Force Dynamic* (1.6%) and *Gravitational Search* (3.3%) were rarely selected in the first position, indicating that their contribution may be more effective when applied in later stages of search rather than as an initial driving force.

Figure 4.9: The trend of operator one from the tailored MH.

Figure 4.10, the selection trend for the second operator in the customized MH sequence is presented. The most remarkable observation is the strong concurrence of the *Swarm Dynamic* perturbator, with 27.9% of the total selections. This indicates that swarm-based operators

are not only effective for initializing the search but also for reinforcing the balance between exploration and exploitation during the intermediate stages. Furthermore, the *Differential Mutation* operator exhibited a high selection rate of 16.4%, suggesting that its diversification and adaptive exploration mechanisms are particularly valuable in this phase of the HH process. In configurations limited to only two operators, this second position often assumes a dual role: complementing initial exploration while beginning to exploit promising candidate solutions.

Figure 4.10: The trend of operator two from the tailored MH.

Figure 4.11 shows the frequency distribution for the third operator in the customized MH sequence. Here, both *Swarm Dynamic* and *Differential Mutation* stood out, each with 18.5% of the total selections. At this stage, the role of *Swarm Dynamic* shifts from a primarily explorative driver to a more exploitative mechanism, intensifying the search around promising regions. Similarly, *Differential Mutation* is recognized for its capacity to introduce variation and refine candidate solutions, supporting the exploitation phase while preventing premature convergence.

Figure 4.11: The trend of operator three from the tailored MH.

When considering the trends for all three operator positions together, a consistent design

principle emerges. The HH process tends to favor a layered strategy: starting with strong exploration operators (*Spiral Dynamic* or *Swarm Dynamic*), reinforcing this diversification in the intermediate stage (notably with *Differential Mutation*), and finalizing with operators that promote exploitation and search intensification (*Swarm Dynamic* and *Differential Mutation*). This progression underlines that effective MH configurations rely on a balance between exploration and exploitation, where exploration dominates the early stages, and exploitation becomes more relevant toward the end of the sequence. When considering the trends for all three operator positions together, a consistent design principle emerges. The HH process tends to favor a layered strategy: starting with operators that emphasize exploration (*Spiral Dynamic* and *Swarm Dynamic*), reinforcing diversity and adaptive adjustments in the intermediate stage (notably with *Differential Mutation*), and finalizing with operators that enhance exploitation and intensification (*Swarm Dynamic* and *Differential Mutation*).

Analyzing the data obtained in this test and inspecting the best three MHs and the worst, we can observe the results obtained by each configuration in the HH process (Table 4.5). The three best-performing MHs consistently included combinations of *Spiral Dynamic* (h_{20}),

Table 4.5: Comparison of the three best and worst MH configurations obtained during the HH process replicates in terms of performance.

SO ₁	SO ₂	SO ₃	Best F _{obj}	Avg. ± St. Dev.	IQR	Perf. (3.9)
h_{20}	h_2	h_{23}	0.111	0.148±0.085	0.027	0.1450
h_{13}	h_{23}	h_2	0.114	0.154±0.085	0.016	0.1457
h_{11}	h_{23}	h_2	0.114	0.138±0.026	0.021	0.1488
h_{21}	h_{21}	None	0.646	2.368±1.560	2.040	3.941
h_6	h_3	h_0	0.754	4.475±2.430	4.211	8.369
h_0	h_{14}	h_{23}	1.105	5.254±3.417	4.440	9.325

Differential Mutation (h_2), and *Swarm Dynamic* (h_{23}). These families complement each other by providing a progressive balance between exploration and exploitation. In particular, *Differential Mutation* (h_2) employs the current-to-best strategy with a greedy selector, favoring convergence toward promising regions, while *Swarm Dynamic* (h_{23}), configured as the constricted version with a greedy selector, reinforces adaptive exploitation. The inclusion of *Spiral Dynamic* (h_{20}) with a direct selector introduces structured exploration at the beginning of the sequence, preparing the ground for later intensification steps. Together, these features explain the extremely low dispersion observed ($\text{IQR} \leq 0.027$) and the best performance scores. In contrast, the worst-performing MHs did not include this triad. The configuration composed exclusively of *Spiral Dynamic* (h_{21}) with a greedy selector in both SO₁ and SO₂ produced higher objective values and wide variability ($\text{IQR} = 2.040$), showing that redundancy without diversification compromises robustness. The combination [h_6, h_3, h_0], involving *Genetic Crossover*, *Differential Mutation* with a direct selector, and *Central Force Dynamic*, displayed even greater variability ($\text{IQR} = 4.211$), evidencing the limitations of direct-selection strategies without adaptive reinforcement. Finally, the configuration [h_0, h_{14}, h_{23}], which mixes *Central Force Dynamic*, *Local Random Walk*, and *Swarm Dynamic*, showed the largest instability ($\text{IQR} = 4.440$), indicating that the inclusion

of low-frequency operators (h_0 and h_{14}) undermined the otherwise strong performance of the swarm-based operator. Overall, the analysis demonstrates that high-performing MHs are systematically associated with the triad of *Spiral Dynamic*, *Differential Mutation*, and *Swarm Dynamic*, configured with selectors that progressively shift from direct exploration to greedy exploitation. Although *Swarm Dynamic* was also present in some of the worst configurations, its isolated use or combination with low-frequency operators such as *Central Force Dynamic* or *Local Random Walk* did not yield adequate performance. This contrast emphasizes that it is not the presence of a single strong operator that ensures success, but rather the synergistic interaction among families and selectors.

Examining the best-performing MH (MH_*) obtained in the previous tests, we observe that it is composed of the following three perturbators:

- h_{20} – *Perturbator*: Spiral Dynamic with radius varying uniformly between 0.8 and 1; *Selector*: Direct.
- h_2 – *Perturbator*: Differential Mutation with mutation scheme rand-to-best-and-current and a scale factor of 1.0; *Selector*: Greedy.
- h_{23} – *Perturbator*: Constriction Swarm Dynamic with a uniform distribution for sampling random variables; *Selector*: Greedy.

To obtain this MH_* , it was necessary to perform an HH process, as seen in Figure 4.12, where each box represents the fitness results obtained after repeating the current candidate MH 20 times. In the seventh step, HH, we observe that MH_7 is an algorithm that outperforms the previous candidates. Therefore $MH_* = MH_7$. Moreover, Figure 4.12 shows the evolution of the performance metric Q , done at step seven, the minimal value of Q obtained.

Figure 4.12: Evolution trend of the low-level fitness value along the HH procedure for the best-achieved MH.

Studying the behavior of the obtained MH_* , we can observe in Figure 4.13 how the MH_* managed to find a solution with a fitness value close to zero, with a high degree of repeatability and fast convergence, which are desired characteristics for this type of solver.

Finally, we analyze the low-level problem (the tuning of the PID controller to control

Figure 4.13: Replicate testing of the tailored $MH_* = MH_7$ for dealing with the low-level problem.

the AVR system); we observe in Table 4.6 the controller’s performance-tuned by the tailored MH_* versus the performance of four MH algorithms that have published their results. These algorithms are the Tree Seed Algorithm (TSA) [92], the Improved Kidney Algorithm (IKA) [93], Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [106], and Differential Evolution (DE) [106]. The overshoot rendered by the MH_* -tuned controller was 1.9%, which represents 7.89, 8.19, 15.74, and 17.23 times lower than those obtained by the IKA, TSA, PSO, and DE-tuned controllers. In addition, the controller tuned with MH_* achieved a settling time of 0.454 s, which positions it as the fastest controller in this comparative analysis. In the case of steady-state error, all algorithms improved this metric, but the controller tuned with MH_* obtained the lowest value among the others. Figure 4.14 summarizes the above analysis, showing the evolution of the output voltage from the AVR system for each controller adjusted via the five different algorithms.

Table 4.6: Results of transient response analysis of the AVR system for different controllers tuned by MH_* , IKA, TSA, PSO, and DE.

Alg.	Fobj.	M_p [%]	T_s [s]	T_r [s]	E_{ss} [p.u.]	K_p	K_i	K_d
MH_*	Proposed in (4.13)	1.96	0.454	0.30	7.84×10^{-6}	0.643	0.438	0.205
IKA [93]	ZGL+ITSE	15.00	0.753	0.12	2.08×10^{-4}	1.128	0.956	0.567
TSA [92]	ITSE	15.57	0.758	0.13	8.86×10^{-4}	1.042	1.009	0.599
PSO [106]	ITSE	29.92	3.399	0.163	8.10×10^{-3}	1.777	0.382	0.318
DE [106]	ITSE	32.74	2.650	0.154	6.56×10^{-3}	1.949	0.443	0.342

Figure 4.14: Step response of the AVR system in a closed-loop and with a PID controller tuned by MH_* , TSA, IKA, PSO, and DE.

AVR with FOPID Controller

The objective is to determine the customized MH capable of delivering the best performance in tuning the FOPID controller for the AVR system. Figure 4.15 illustrates the HH evolution process, where each boxplot represents the fitness values obtained for a candidate MH across 20 independent repetitions. The best performance achieved during the HH process is highlighted with orange dots, evaluated according to the performance metric Q defined in (3.9). The candidate MH improved from an initial value of $Q_0 = 7.93$ (step 0) to $Q_2 = 0.7795$ (step 2), representing an enhancement of 90.17%. The zoomed inset in Figure 4.15 highlights steps where significant improvements occurred. For instance, Q reached 0.6101 at step 5 and decreased further to 0.5482 at step 9, corresponding to 92.30% and 93.08% improvements over the initial value, respectively.

To further examine the improvement achieved, the results from steps 0 and 9 were compared. Figure 4.16a shows the fitness distribution of the candidate MH at the initial step, where stagnation and wide dispersion among replications can be observed. In contrast, Figure 4.16b shows the MH obtained at step 9, denoted as $MH_* = MH_9$, which converges rapidly to a lower fitness value with minimal variation, as evidenced by the narrow boxplot. This comparison highlights the importance of selecting an appropriate MH: the tailored MH_* not only accelerates convergence but also improves solution quality and robustness, underscoring the role of automated selection in balancing exploration and exploitation.

The tailored metaheuristic MH_* consists of two perturbation mechanisms. The first is a member of the *Swarm Dynamic* family, exploiting collective behaviors and information exchange to guide the search. The second is derived from the *Genetic Crossover* family, which introduces new candidate solutions based on recombination and inheritance principles. Both operators employ Metropolis-based selection, enabling probabilistic acceptance of suboptimal solutions to escape local minima. The detailed configuration of these operators, including their variation parameters and hyperparameters, is summarized in Table 4.7.

Figure 4.15: Evolution of the candidate MH for each hyper-heuristic step. Orange dots and dashed lines illustrate the HH process’s performance.

Figure 4.16: Fitness evolution of candidate MHs at steps 0 and 9 of the HH process.

Upon tailoring MH_* , its robustness was assessed through a repeatability test to ensure the results’ reliability. Figure 4.17 depicts boxplots representing the distribution of the FOPID controller’s gains and fractional order variables across 50 iterations of the optimization process. These iterations aimed to verify the consistency of the controller gains and the corresponding fitness values. The results of this experiment emphasize the high repeatability of MH_* , with a median fitness performance of 0.216 and a standard deviation of ± 0.0541 . Such statistical measures indicate a strong reliability in the optimization process under MH_* . Furthermore, this evaluation process identified the optimal set of gains that minimized the objective function, specifically targeting improved control features such as peak overshoot

Table 4.7: Variation parameters and hyperparameters of each operator composing the tailored metaheuristic (MH_{*}).

SOs	Heuristic	Variation Parameters	Hyperparameters
h_{184}	Swarm Dynamic	swarm_approach = Inertial; pdf = Uniform	$\alpha_0 = 0.7, \phi_1 = 2.54, \phi_2 = 2.56$
	Metropolis selection	–	$c = 0.01, k_B = 1.0, \Theta_0 = 1000$
h_{60}	Genetic Crossover	crossover_mechanism = Two-points; pairing_scheme = Rank weighting	$m_p = 0.4$
	Metropolis selection	–	$c = 0.01, k_B = 1.0, \Theta_0 = 1000$

(M_p), settling time (T_s), and rise time (T_r). The fine-tuned gains for the FOPID controller are as follows: $K_p = 1.24987$, $K_i = 0.5280$, $K_d = 0.2656$, $\lambda = 1.0820$, and $\mu = 1.2014$. These delineate the parameters for achieving superior control performance.

Figure 4.17: Distribution of the controller parameters and the resulting fitness values for 50 replicates obtained by MH_{*}.

Table 4.8 provides a comprehensive comparative analysis between the fine-tuned FOPID controller and four existing approaches, all designed under similar operational conditions for AVR systems and optimized through various MHs. This comparison leverages control gains from studies reported in [107–110], specifically applied to the case study. The data indicate that our optimization strategy yields a controller performance approximately 1.69 times faster than the comparator approaches, achieving near-zero overshoot. Notably, despite the designed controller exhibiting a rise time that is 2.13 times longer than that reported in [109], it demonstrates the slightest discrepancy between the settling and rise times (Δ_T), highlighting its efficiency and robustness in dynamic response.

Figure 4.18 illustrates the dynamic responses of the controllers listed in Table 4.8, tracking a Heaviside step function. Upon closer examination, it becomes evident that the controller fine-tuned through the tailored MH reaches the steady state with remarkable swiftness,

Table 4.8: Comparative analysis of the proposed FOPID Controller against published approaches in the literature. Colors indicate performance rankings: blue highlights the best values achieved, whereas yellow denotes the least favorable features.

Approach	Features				Controller gains and orders				
	M_p [%]	T_s [s]	T_r [s]	Δ_T [s]	K_p	K_i	K_d	λ	μ
MH*	0	0.3315	0.2156	0.1159	1.24987	0.5280	0.2656	1.0820	1.2014
Lahcene et al. [110]	0.0271	0.4351	0.2825	0.1526	0.7837	0.5027	0.2307	1.0103	1.0727
Sikander et al. [107]	2.4926	0.8780	0.1133	0.7646	2.5150	0.1629	0.3888	0.9700	1.3800
Ramezani et al. [108]	0.5129	0.5027	0.2438	0.2588	1.2623	0.5531	0.2382	1.1827	1.2555
Mohd Tumari et al. [109]	0.5866	0.4323	0.1010	0.3312	2.9487	0.4533	0.4391	1.4016	1.4154

showcasing superior performance. This enhanced response is attributed to the meticulously fine-tuned control gains, as detailed in the third row of Table 4.8, which significantly improve the system’s transient behavior. Besides, our heuristically tuned controller distinctly outperforms the alternatives in three critical control metrics: M_p , T_s , and the difference between settling and rise times (Δ_T). In comparison, the approach by Sikander et al. [107], represented by the yellow line in the figure, demonstrates the least favorable performance, positioning it at the lower end of the comparative spectrum.

Figure 4.18: Step response of different FOPID controllers designed for the AVR system. The metaheuristic algorithms used to perform the FOPID controller tuning are: MH*, SA by Lahcene et al. [110], CS by Sikander et al. [107], PSO by Ramezani et al. [108], and MP-SEDA by Mohd Tumari et al. [109].

On the other hand, this study quantifies the impact of variations in each AVR transfer function parameter (see Table 4.1) on the performance of the FOPID controller, as detailed in Table 4.9. Our analysis covers three critical control features: M_p , T_s , and T_r , respectively. To achieve this with incremental steps of 25%, the parameters of the transfer functions were varied within a range of -50% to 50% of their nominal values. It is important to note that the following analysis is conducted individually, i.e., for each AVR transfer function parameter variation. Moreover, these performance impacts are contrasted with the control outcomes achieved through the control gains optimized by the tailored MH (referenced in row 3 of Table 4.8).

Concerning τ_a , the overshoot remains at zero for parameter variations of -50% and -25% (as shown in row 3, columns 2 and 3, respectively). However, with a positive increase in this parameter, i.e., at 50% and 75%, the M_p experiences an average increase of 4.71%. Additionally, both T_r and T_s render an average increase of 1.86 and 1.09 times, respectively, irrespective of the variation in τ_a .

Table 4.9: Comparative analysis of the proposed FOPID controller performance across a range of variations in AVR transfer function parameters. τ_a , τ_e , τ_g , and τ_s denote the parameters for the amplifier, exciter, generator, and sensor models, respectively, as detailed in Table 4.1.

Transient response features	Transfer function parameters			
	$\tau_a = 0.05$	$\tau_a = 0.075$	$\tau_a = 0.125$	$\tau_a = 0.15$
M_p [%]	0	0	3.212	6.219
T_s [s]	0.635	0.573	0.558	0.701
T_r [s]	0.261	0.218	0.221	0.228
	$\tau_e = 0.2$	$\tau_e = 0.3$	$\tau_e = 0.5$	$\tau_e = 0.6$
M_p [%]	0	0	2.623	5.325
T_s [s]	1.138	0.774	0.871	1.176
T_r [s]	0.138	0.178	0.249	0.280
	$\tau_g = 0.5$	$\tau_g = 0.75$	$\tau_g = 1.25$	$\tau_g = 1.5$
M_p [%]	3.776	0.798	1.751	3.516
T_s [s]	1.915	0.746	0.415	1.331
T_r [s]	0.119	0.166	0.265	0.313
	$\tau_s = 0.005$	$\tau_s = 0.0075$	$\tau_s = 0.0125$	$\tau_s = 0.015$
M_p [%]	0	0	0.286	0.753
T_s [s]	0.364	0.348	0.319	0.308
T_r [s]	0.226	0.220	0.210	0.206

A similar trend is observed with τ_e , where M_p equals zero for negative variations but experiences an average increase of 3.97% for positive changes. Likewise, the T_s values indicate that the proposed controller response becomes 66.50% slower before achieving a steady state. Interestingly, negative variations in τ_e lead to faster rise times, whereas positive variations result in slower rise times.

In addition, Figures 4.19 and 4.20 illustrate the relationship between the fractional parameters λ and μ , and their impact on two critical control features, M_p and T_s . These contour maps enable the identification of λ - μ combinations that minimize or maximize the overshoot and settling time of the AVR system, with darker colors indicating lower values and lighter colors indicating higher values of these control features. The green marker highlights the minimum M_p and T_s values achieved by the standard PID structure, whereas the red marker signifies the outcomes obtained with the fractional control scheme (referenced in row 4 of Table 4.8).

The analysis reveals that M_p spans a wide range from 0% to 64%, while T_s fluctuates within

Figure 4.19: Landscape of relationship λ and μ and their effects over the overshoot.

Figure 4.20: Landscape of relationship λ and μ and their effects over the settling time.

a more confined spectrum, between 0.33 s and 3.49 s. These plots demarcate reliable regions for stable AVR system operation concerning these control features.

Aiming to refine significantly the transitory response over the traditional PID control (denoted by the green point)—specifically, to reduce overshoot and settling time—the blue regions in these plots are especially targeted. The tailored MH and the proposed fitness criterion suggest a pivotal relationship for the fractional parameters: $\mu > \lambda$ is essential for attaining the optimal response. It becomes apparent that the optimal λ - μ combination can render the controller four times faster with zero overshoot compared to the traditional PID, which exhibits control features of $T_s = 1.34$ s and $M_p = 17.70\%$.

4.4.2 DC-DC Buck–Boost Converters with ASMC

By applying the AAD-based approach to the Buck–Boost converter problem, the goal was to identify a tailored solver for the low-level problem, namely the tuning of an ASMC. The

HH process was executed for ten steps, as illustrated in Figure 4.21a, where the performance metric Q showed a clear tendency to improve as the iterations progressed (blue markers). Each boxplot represents the distribution of fitness values achieved by a candidate MH across 20 independent runs. At step 8, the HH process identified a metaheuristic, denoted as $\text{MH}_8 \equiv \text{MH}_*$, which outperformed previous candidates. As shown in Figure 4.21b, this configuration rapidly converged toward fitness values close to zero, achieving $Q = 2.478 \times 10^{-2}$.

Figure 4.21: (a) The tendency of the performance metric Q along the hyper-heuristic process (High-level problem), where the dashed line represents the performance evolution. (b) The behavior of the custom MH in step 8 ($\text{MH}_* \equiv \text{MH}_8$) generated to solve the low-level problem.

Although the results obtained are promising, the HH process was limited to ten steps; therefore, further improvements may arise if a broader search space is explored. The tailored MH_* identified in step 8 is formally expressed as:

$$\text{MH}_* = \langle h_i, h_{104} \circ h_{190}, h_f \rangle, \quad (4.20)$$

where the operator sequence is crucial, i.e., $h_{190} \circ h_{104} \neq h_{104} \circ h_{190}$, since the order directly influences whether exploration or exploitation dominates the search dynamics. The indices h_{104} and h_{190} correspond to the operator identifiers listed in Table 3.3, which summarizes the collection of search operators employed in this problem.

The first operator, h_{190} , corresponds to an *Inertial Swarm Dynamic* perturbator with random variables sampled from a Lévy probability distribution, followed by a direct selector. The second operator, h_{104} , is a *Genetic Crossover* with a blend mechanism and a tournament pairing scheme of two individuals ($M_T = 2$) with $p_T = 1.0$ and a mating pool factor $m_p = 0.4$, followed by a probabilistic selector with probability $p_s = 0.5$. The configuration of these operators is summarized in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10: Variation parameters and hyperparameters of the search operators composing MH_* .

SO	Heuristic	Variation Parameters	Hyperparameters
h_{190}	Swarm Dynamic	swarm_approach = Inertial; pdf = Lévy	$\alpha_0 = 0.7, \phi_1 = 2.54, \phi_2 = 2.56$
	Direct selection	–	–
h_{104}	Genetic Crossover	crossover_mechanism = Blend; pairing_scheme = Tournament ($M_T = 2, p_T = 1.0$)	$m_p = 0.4$
	Probabilistic selection	–	$p_s = 0.5$

The tailored MH_* obtained for the ASMC design in the Buck–Boost converter is composed of two complementary operators: a swarm-based perturbator providing exploration capability, and a crossover-based operator introducing structured recombination and diversification. Unlike conventional hybrid schemes (e.g., PSO-GA), this configuration emerged through the HH process, where operator type, parameters, and selection mechanisms were automatically chosen and combined, yielding a solver specifically adapted to the low-level control problem.

The performance of MH_* was subsequently evaluated to determine the control features summarized in Table 4.3. Its effectiveness was verified by comparing it with results obtained from classical MHs reported in the literature, such as PSO and GA. The experiment consisted of adjusting the ASMC parameters in 20 independent replicates.

Table 4.11 presents the average and standard deviation of the parameters obtained for the ASMC (α , β , and λ), as well as the fitness values achieved by each MH. The tailored MH_* reached the lowest average fitness value, 1.15×10^{-3} , followed by PSO with 3.17×10^{-2} and GA with 3.08×10^{-1} . This represents improvements by factors of 27.57 and 267.83 over PSO and GA, respectively.

Table 4.11: Average and standard deviation of design parameters and fitness values for Adaptive Sliding Mode Controllers, as optimized by MH_* , PSO, and GA.

Alg.	Average Standard Deviation			Fitness Value
	α	β	λ	
MH_*	50.45 ± 0.25	$0.25 \times 10^{-8} \pm 2.22 \times 10^{-9}$	$1.20 \pm 2.06 \times 10^{-3}$	$1.15 \times 10^{-3} \pm 5.66 \times 10^{-4}$
PSO	64.5 ± 11.11	$1.19 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3.43 \times 10^{-4}$	$1.27 \pm 8.67 \times 10^{-3}$	$3.17 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1.52 \times 10^{-2}$
GA	55.8 ± 17.82	$1.91 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8.56 \times 10^{-4}$	$1.14 \pm 2.07 \times 10^{-1}$	$3.08 \times 10^{-1} \pm 3.29 \times 10^{-1}$

PSO demonstrated competitive performance, achieving better results than GA with a lower average fitness value (3.17×10^{-2}) and a smaller standard deviation (1.52×10^{-2}), indicating greater consistency across replications. Nevertheless, MH_* clearly outperformed

both classical methods in robustness and fitness, showing lower dispersion and improved convergence.

The superior performance of MH_* can be attributed to its composite structure, which integrates complementary exploration and exploitation strategies. Specifically, the Swarm Dynamic perturbator inspired by PSO, implemented with an inertial approach and a Lévy distribution, enhances exploration and mitigates premature convergence. Meanwhile, the Genetic Crossover operator supports exploitation by refining promising regions of the search space, and the Probabilistic Selector dynamically balances diversification and intensification. In contrast, PSO alone lacks the refinement provided by crossover operators, while GA alone exhibits limited exploration dynamics. By leveraging the strengths of both, MH_* achieves a robust and adaptive search mechanism, leading to superior performance.

Figure 4.22 illustrates the distribution of fitness values across the three approaches. MH_* achieved the narrowest interquartile range ($IQR = 6.70 \times 10^{-4}$), reflecting excellent stability and repeatability. PSO showed greater variability ($IQR = 2.04 \times 10^{-2}$), but still considerably lower than GA ($IQR = 0.50$), which suffered from significant dispersion. This confirms that while PSO can be considered a viable option when moderate accuracy is acceptable, the tailored MH_* consistently provides the most reliable results.

Figure 4.22: Fitness values obtained from 20 ASMC designs using the tailored MH_* and two classical metaheuristics (PSO and GA).

An analysis of the control parameters further highlights these differences. The parameter β consistently converged to small values, particularly under MH_* ($\beta = 0.25 \times 10^{-8}$), which is desirable to reduce oscillations and smooth the control effort, thereby addressing the penalty term in (4.18). The parameter α showed a tendency to increase, with PSO reaching an average of 64.5, reflecting an aggressive strategy to minimize steady-state error, albeit at the expense of higher energy consumption. Finally, λ remained relatively stable across methods, with MH_* showing a slight increase ($\lambda = 1.20 \times 10^{-3}$) and the lowest variability, ensuring rapid error correction while maintaining robustness and avoiding excessive control effort.

Avoiding constant saturation and excessive power consumption requires precise parameter adjustment so that the adaptive gain adapts dynamically to the converter's conditions. Although a detailed sensitivity analysis is outside the scope of this work, it is important to note that even small variations in controller gains directly affect M_p , T_s , and E_{ss} . MHs

are particularly valuable in this context, as they enable systematic exploration of parameter configurations that are impractical to determine by trial and error.

Figure 4.23 illustrates the step response of the converter. The MH_* -tuned controller achieved the best performance, with an overshoot of 0.98% and a settling time of 0.4508 ms, while eliminating steady-state error for a Heaviside input. In comparison, PSO and GA produced higher overshoot and longer settling times, consistent with their larger fitness values in Table 4.11.

Figure 4.23: Step response of the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter in closed-loop with an ASMC tuned using MH_* , PSO, and GA. Controller parameters correspond to the average values in Table 4.11 (20 independent runs).

A more detailed view of overshoot behavior across replicates is given in Figure 4.24a. MH_* showed high repeatability, with an average overshoot of 0.9997%, a median of 0.9998%, and minimal dispersion (IQR = 0.0012%). PSO also achieved a median close to 1%, but with higher variability (IQR = 0.035%). This variability is expected since PSO contributes one of the main components of MH_* . In contrast, GA exhibited the poorest results, with a lower median overshoot (0.91%) but significant dispersion (IQR = 0.47%), indicating less consistent performance. A similar trend for the settling time is observed, as shown in Figure 4.24b. The tailored MH_* met the design objective, achieving a median settling time of 0.45 ms with minimal variability (IQR = 0.0013 ms). Although PSO achieved a slightly shorter median settling time (0.43 ms), it deviated from the target specified in the objective function. It exhibited significantly higher variability with an IQR of 0.0572 ms. In contrast, GA presented the longest settling time, with a median of 0.47 ms and the highest dispersion (IQR = 0.1301 ms).

Figure 4.24: (a) Overshoot (M_p [%]) and (b) Settling Time (T_s [s]) values for the Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller tuned by the tailored (MH_*) and two classical (PSO and GA) metaheuristics, corresponding to 20 controller designs.

In addition to the initial tests, further experiments were conducted with robust algorithms widely recognized in optimization competitions, such as MadDE, L-SHADE, MPA, and GTO. These population-based methods are rooted in Differential Evolution (DE), with MadDE and L-SHADE incorporating advanced archive and adaptation strategies [111, 112], while MPA and GTO rely on metaphor-inspired mechanisms.

Table 4.12 summarizes the outcomes. MH_* , L-SHADE, and MadDE exhibited highly competitive performances, whereas MPA and GTO showed larger variability and less consistent results. Notably, MH_* achieved the best fitness value (2.52×10^{-4}), with a median of 3.09×10^{-3} and a narrow IQR (5.19×10^{-3}), evidencing stable performance. L-SHADE and MadDE also reached low best fitness values (2.30×10^{-3} and 4.89×10^{-4} , respectively), but with greater dispersion. In contrast, MPA and GTO obtained acceptable results in isolated runs but exhibited high variability (IQR = 9.61×10^{-2} and 9.46, respectively).

Table 4.12: Fitness metrics for each MH, including best, median, STD, IQR, and p -value from comparisons with MH_* .

Algorithm	Fitness Metrics				
	Best	Median	STD	IQR	p -Value
MH_*	2.52×10^{-4}	3.09×10^{-3}	8.36×10^{-3}	5.19×10^{-3}	–
MadDE	4.89×10^{-4}	9.75×10^{-3}	1.01×10^{-2}	1.79×10^{-2}	1.59×10^{-2}
L-SHADE	2.30×10^{-3}	2.57×10^{-2}	2.69×10^{-2}	2.28×10^{-2}	4.16×10^{-4}
MPA	2.35×10^{-4}	1.76×10^{-2}	2.01×10^{-1}	9.61×10^{-2}	1.59×10^{-2}
GTO	2.32×10^{-1}	3.51×10^{-1}	4.638	9.461	4.78×10^{-5}

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test confirmed the superiority of MH_* over the other methods ($p < 0.05$ in all cases). This outcome is particularly relevant given that MadDE and L-SHADE were carefully engineered by experts and rely on sophisticated adaptation mechanisms, whereas MH_* emerged automatically through an AAD-based process with only two operators.

The ability of MH_* to match and even outperform state-of-the-art methods highlights both the efficiency and robustness of the automated design, reinforcing its potential for solving demanding real-world control problems.

The final stage evaluated the performance of the ASMC tuned with MH_* under dynamic input variations and nonlinear load disturbances. Figure 4.25 shows the converter’s transient response to step and ramp input voltages. The output voltage (green trace) closely tracks the reference (gray trace), achieving fast convergence without overshoot and with minimal delay during ramp inputs. This confirms that the tuned controller ensures both accuracy and responsiveness, essential for voltage regulation under varying operating conditions.

Figure 4.25: Output voltage of the Buck–Boost converter controlled by an ASMC tuned with MH_* under step and ramp input profiles.

Robustness was further examined by subjecting the system to a nonlinear load profile, representative of industrial disturbances (Figure 4.26a). Despite the abrupt load variations, the MH_* -tuned ASMC maintained the output voltage close to the reference, with only minor deviations that were promptly corrected (Figure 4.26b). This demonstrates the controller’s ability to preserve stability under highly perturbed conditions.

Figure 4.26: (a) Nonlinear load disturbance profile. (b) Output voltage of the Buck–Boost converter under disturbances with ASMC tuned by MH_* .

Figure 4.27a details the control action and adaptive gain during disturbances. The control effort remains within feasible bounds, while the adaptive gain adjusts dynamically to

counteract perturbations, ensuring system stability without exceeding energy constraints. Meanwhile, the sliding surface converges to zero in finite time (Figure 4.27b), confirming proper calibration of the adaptive law and effective rejection of nonlinear perturbations.

Figure 4.27: ASMC tuned with MH_* under nonlinear perturbations: (a) control action and adaptive gain, (b) sliding surface evolution.

Overall, these results show that the MH_* -tuned ASMC achieves fast and accurate voltage regulation, robust disturbance rejection, and feasible control effort, validating its suitability for real-world DC-DC converter applications.

4.5 Summary

The tuning of PID, FOPID, and ASMC controllers, although conceptually simple, is not a trivial process in practice. Achieving a suitable balance among the proportional, integral, and derivative actions, together with their fractional extensions or adaptive mechanisms, requires careful consideration of nonlinear dynamics, uncertainties, and operating conditions in electrical systems. Traditionally, this process has relied on the designer's experience, heuristic rules, or trial-and-error procedures that rarely guarantee optimal performance [116–118]. Consequently, controller tuning is commonly reformulated as an optimization problem, where the objective is to determine parameter values that minimize performance indices associated with transient and steady-state behavior.

The literature offers a wide collection of MH approaches to controller tuning, each claiming superior performance under particular scenarios [119, 120]. This diversity raises a fundamental question: *Which algorithm should be preferred for a given application?* To address this challenge, this thesis goes beyond simply adjusting a controller. Instead, it investigates the Automated design of metaheuristic algorithms, a paradigm capable of generating customized solvers that adapt to the structure of AVR and Buck-Boost converter problems, while remaining competitive with classical optimization techniques and more exotic MH proposals.

This chapter introduced the application of Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) to two representative control problems in electrical engineering: the Automatic Voltage Regulator (AVR) and the DC-DC Buck-Boost converter. For the AVR, the methodology considered the

tuning of classical PID and FOPID controllers through tailored MHs automatically obtained using a hyper-heuristic framework. For the Buck-Boost converter, the focus was placed on the design of an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller (ASMC) robust against nonlinearities and external disturbances. The chapter detailed the modeling of both systems, the formulation of optimization problems, and the structure of the AAD framework, including the definition of the heuristic space, performance metrics, and evaluation procedures.

The experimental evaluation across the three applications, PID and FOPID tuning for AVR systems and ASMC design for a Buck–Boost converter, demonstrates the competitiveness of the Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) paradigm in control-oriented optimization. In the PID case, the tailored MH* significantly outperformed classical algorithms such as DE, PSO, TSA, and IKA, reducing overshoot and settling time by factors of up to one order of magnitude. For the FOPID controller, the automatically generated solver achieved near-zero overshoot and the fastest settling time among published approaches, while maintaining robustness under parameter variations of the AVR transfer functions. In the more demanding Buck–Boost converter with ASMC, the tailored MH* not only surpassed GA and PSO but also delivered results comparable to advanced solvers such as MadDE and L-SHADE, despite these relying on multiple operators and complex adaptation strategies. Common traits were observed across all cases: the best-performing MHs emerged with compact configurations of two or three operators, favored layered exploration-exploitation strategies, and showed remarkable repeatability with low variability across runs. Collectively, these findings highlight that AAD can automatically produce solvers that are not only competitive with but in many cases superior to expert-designed MHs, positioning this work among the first concrete demonstrations of its potential in real-world control problems.

Chapter 5

Automated Tailoring of Heuristic-Based Rényi Entropy Maximizers for Efficient Melanoma Segmentation

Melanoma segmentation in dermoscopic images constitutes a challenging optimization problem of high clinical and social relevance, given its direct implications for the early detection of skin cancer. The variability of lesion appearance, presence of artifacts, and the need for precise delineation motivate the development of robust computational strategies. Skin cancer incidence continues to rise worldwide [121]; early and reliable delineation of melanoma in dermoscopy is critical for downstream computer-aided diagnosis. Robust segmentation remains difficult due to hair artifacts, low contrast, illumination changes, and lesion heterogeneity. MHs are attractive for building adaptive pipelines; however, choosing and tuning the “right” MH is non-trivial given the proliferation of variants. AAD and, in particular, HHs provide a principled approach to generating and configuring problem-specific MHs with minimal expert bias. In this chapter, the design strategy relies on a Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH), intending to generate tailored MHs without metaphors, focusing on the maximization of Rényi’s entropy within a 2D histogram space. The design space is constrained to 12 search operators, systematically explored and assembled by the PRHH. In the following sections, we provide a detailed explanation of the key concepts, methodology, and results associated with this application. All data and codes used in this application are publicly available¹.

5.1 Melanoma Image Segmentation

Advances in medical imaging have significantly contributed to the early diagnosis and treatment of skin cancer [122]. Among the different types of skin cancer, melanoma remains one of the most prevalent and aggressive, making early detection a critical research objective. This need is particularly evident in regions with limited access to

¹The dataset is freely accessible at <https://github.com/DanielFz14/SSCI25-Paper7>

specialized care, where occupational exposure to ultraviolet radiation increases the incidence of melanoma and delayed detection can worsen clinical outcomes [123, 124]. In this context, dermoscopic image segmentation plays a central role in computer-aided diagnostic systems by providing reliable delineation of suspicious lesions [125]. Nevertheless, accurate melanoma segmentation remains a challenging task due to lesion heterogeneity, the presence of artifacts such as hair, variations in illumination, and low contrast between the lesion and surrounding skin. To address these challenges, MHs have proved effective in developing adaptive models capable of adjusting to diverse image conditions [126]. Despite their success in several medical imaging applications [127], the design of MH-based solvers remains demanding: selecting a suitable algorithm, configuring its operators, and tuning its hyperparameters requires extensive expertise and exhaustive validation. An alternative is to delegate this task to automated design strategies, which can systematically generate and adapt MHs to the specific problem at hand, thereby reducing dependence on manual expertise.

5.1.1 Multilevel Thresholding

Image thresholding is one of the most widely used techniques in image segmentation, where pixels are partitioned into regions based on their gray-level intensity. In its simplest form, bi-level thresholding separates an image into foreground and background [128]. However, in medical imaging, and particularly in melanoma delineation, this approach is insufficient since lesions often present multiple intensity distributions [129]. Multilevel thresholding extends the problem by introducing multiple thresholds, allowing the image to be partitioned into distinct regions with varying characteristics. The task can be expressed as the search for an optimal set of thresholds that maximizes a given criterion, typically defined through statistical measures. Classical works on two-dimensional entropy [130, 131] have demonstrated that extending thresholding to the 2D domain improves segmentation quality by preserving more spatial information. In practice, the quality of the segmentation is highly sensitive to the chosen thresholds, and the search space grows exponentially with the number of thresholds, making the problem computationally expensive. For this reason, the formulation is often approached as an optimization problem where MHs have proved particularly effective [126, 127, 132].

5.1.2 Two-Dimensional Histograms

A one-dimensional histogram describes the distribution of gray levels in an image, but it discards spatial context, which is essential in medical segmentation. Two-dimensional (2D) histograms address this by combining the gray-level intensity of each pixel with a secondary feature, such as a contrast-enhanced value or a non-local means response [132, 133].

Formally, given a gray-scale image I of size $M \times N$ and a derived image R of equal size, the joint histogram is

$$q(i, j) = \#\{(x, y) \mid I(x, y) = i, R(x, y) = j\}, \quad 0 \leq i, j \leq 255, \quad (5.1)$$

and its normalized form is

$$p(i, j) = \frac{q(i, j)}{M \times N}, \quad (5.2)$$

where $p(i, j)$ is the joint probability of the pair (i, j) .

This representation captures correlations between intensity and local context, making it more robust to artifacts and changes in illumination. For melanoma images, 2D histograms enhance the separability of lesion and background regions, improving the reliability of multilevel thresholding when combined with entropy-based criteria [131].

5.1.3 Rényi Entropy for Segmentation

Entropy-based criteria have been widely used in image thresholding due to their ability to quantify the amount of information contained in an image. Classical formulations include Shannon entropy [134], Tsallis entropy [135], and Rényi entropy [136]. These measures differ mainly in how they weight the distribution of probabilities, providing different levels of sensitivity to pixel intensities and correlations. In practice, Shannon entropy is effective for bi-level thresholding, whereas generalized entropies, such as Tsallis and Rényi, have been shown to yield more robust results in multilevel scenarios [137–139].

For an image characterized by a probability distribution $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^L$ over L gray levels, Shannon entropy is defined as

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^L p_i \log p_i, \quad (5.3)$$

whereas Rényi entropy of order $\alpha \neq 1$ is given by

$$H_\alpha = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \ln \left(\sum_{i=1}^L p_i^\alpha \right). \quad (5.4)$$

Rényi entropy generalizes Shannon's formulation and reduces to it when $\alpha \rightarrow 1$. The parameter α controls the sensitivity of the measure, such as $\alpha < 1$ emphasize low-probability events, while $\alpha > 1$ stresses dominant probabilities. In the case of 2D histograms, the distribution is defined by the joint probability $p(i, j)$ obtained from the pair of gray levels (i, j) . For a set of thresholds $\{g_1, \dots, g_{n-1}\}$ and $\{f_1, \dots, f_{n-1}\}$ applied to the gray-scale and transformed images, respectively, the 2D Rényi entropy is computed over the diagonal subregions of the histogram [131]:

$$H_\alpha(g, f) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} H_\alpha^{(k)}(g_k, f_k), \quad (5.5)$$

with

$$H_\alpha^{(k)}(g_k, f_k) = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \ln \left(\sum_{i=a}^{g_k} \sum_{j=b}^{f_k} \left(\frac{p(i, j)}{p_k} \right)^\alpha \right), \quad (5.6)$$

where p_k is the probability mass of the k -th diagonal subregion. The optimal thresholds are obtained by maximizing this entropy, which promotes partitions that best preserve the structural information of the lesion and background regions.

5.2 Methodology

The proposed methodology addresses melanoma segmentation through multilevel thresholding optimized by Rényi’s entropy over two-dimensional 2D histograms. The process comprises two main levels: the low-level domain, which defines the image representation and the objective function, and the high-level domain, which explores the heuristic space to generate tailored MHs for solving the optimization problem [140].

5.2.1 Low-Level Domain

Figure 5.1 depicts the image processing pipeline used in this study. The process begins with grayscale conversion, followed by an optimized Top-Hat technique that enhances and minimizes tubular structures. A multilevel thresholding process using a 2D-histogram approach is then applied [141], preparing the image for the MH optimization detailed in this section. All experiments utilize the ISIC dataset [142], which comprises images of both healthy skin and melanoma.

Figure 5.1: Overview of the image segmentation process.

Moreover, the transformation function defines the operation whose parameters are optimized, guiding how image data is manipulated for tasks such as feature enhancement or segmentation [143]. Paired with a fitness function that evaluates image quality using predefined metrics, these elements drive optimization by iteratively refining parameters to improve image processing. For melanoma detection, segmentation via multilevel thresholding is employed, using Rényi’s entropy as the objective function [142]. This criterion is particularly effective for delineating melanomas in dermoscopic images, a crucial step in accurately detecting skin cancer.

The low-level domain encompasses all procedures for evaluating candidate solutions, governed by the sequence of search operators that form an MH. In this setting, the objective function is Rényi's entropy computed on a two-dimensional histogram constructed from a gray-scale image and its contrast-enhanced counterpart obtained via Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [144]. CLAHE enhances local contrast while preventing noise over-amplification, highlighting diagnostically relevant structures, as illustrated in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Preprocessing for melanoma segmentation: gray-scale and contrast-enhanced images.

Let $I(i, j)$ denote the gray-scale image and $E(i, j)$ the CLAHE-enhanced image, with pixel coordinates (i, j) . For each local block of size $N \times N$, the histogram is $H(i, j) = \text{Hist}(I_{\text{block}}(i, j))$, which is clipped to avoid over-enhancement as $H_{\text{clip}}(i, j) = \min\{H(i, j), C\}$, where C is the maximum contrast factor. The clipped histogram is redistributed to remove discontinuities, $H_{\text{redist}}(i, j) = (L - 1)N^{-2}H_{\text{clip}}(i, j)$, with $L = 256$ gray levels, and the equalized image is $I_{\text{equ}}(i, j) = \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} H_{\text{redist}}(i, j)$. The final enhanced image is

$$I_{\text{CLAHE}}(i, j) = \min\{I_{\text{equ}}(i, j), C\}. \quad (5.7)$$

Using I and E of size $S \times T$, the 2D histogram $P(i, j)$ counts the co-occurrences of gray levels in I and E ; the normalized joint probability is

$$p(i, j) = \frac{P(i, j)}{ST}.$$

Let $g = \{g_1, \dots, g_{n-1}\}$ and $f = \{f_1, \dots, f_{n-1}\}$ be increasing thresholds on the I - and E -axes, respectively, which partition the 2D histogram into diagonal subregions. The total Rényi entropy is

$$H_\alpha(g, f) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} H_\alpha^{(k)}(g_k, f_k), \quad (5.8)$$

with

$$H_\alpha^{(k)}(g_k, f_k) = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \ln \left(\sum_{i=a}^{g_k} \sum_{j=b}^{f_k} \left(\frac{p(i, j)}{p_k} \right)^\alpha \right), \quad (5.9)$$

where $a = g_{k-1} + 1$, $b = f_{k-1} + 1$, $p_k = \sum_{i=a}^{g_k} \sum_{j=b}^{f_k} p(i, j)$ is the probability mass of the k -th diagonal subregion, and $\alpha \neq 1$. The segmentation task is posed as finding the optimal

thresholds

$$T^* = \operatorname{argmax}_{g,f} H_\alpha(g, f), \quad (5.10)$$

or, equivalently,

$$T^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{g,f} \{-H_\alpha(g, f)\}. \quad (5.11)$$

Since each threshold takes values in $\{0, \dots, 255\}$, the search space grows exponentially with n , rendering exhaustive search infeasible. Consequently, we rely on MH optimization to efficiently explore this space under realistic computational budgets. In our experiments, image packets of sizes $\{10, 20, 30, \dots, 70\}$ are randomly sampled to evaluate candidate MHs and their operator sequences across different population sizes and iteration counts, aiming to identify combinations that achieve accurate and robust segmentation with reduced computational cost.

5.2.2 High-Level Domain

The high-level domain corresponds to the heuristic space $\mathfrak{H} \in \mathbb{H}^\varpi$, where ϖ is the number of SOs used for obtaining an MH. A cardinality of $\varpi = 2$ was used for the implementation performed in this work. For this heuristic space, we employ a collection of 12 SOs obtained by considering different combinations of SOs extracted from ten well-known MHs. Table 3.4 shows the SOs used as heuristic space, composed of different perturbators h_p , their corresponding hyper-parameters, and selectors h_s . To evaluate the performance of an MH candidate, the performance metric defined in (3.9) was used. In this application, we set $N_r = 30$, that is, the number of replicas of the problem in the HH process. We calculated the average Q across different instances to assess the performance of each candidate MH. This metric offers a comprehensive evaluation, capturing instance-specific and generalized performance across all problem instances. To solve the high-level problem in (2.38), we implemented a Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH) for experimentation (see Sect. 3.2.2). The experiments consisted of three tests: Test P₁ used 15 agents and 30 iterations; Test P₂ used 20 agents and 40 iterations; and Test P₃ used 30 agents and 60 iterations. These configurations define the candidate MH's budget. Additionally, our PRHH employed a population of four individuals to explore the heuristic space across ten steps. Finally, Figure 5.3 overviews the methodology for obtaining an MH via an HH process proposed in this application.

5.3 Experimental Results

This section presents the computational validation of the automated design strategy applied to the melanoma segmentation problem. The objective is to assess how the construction of tailored metaheuristics, through the systematic combination and configuration of search operators, affects the performance of Rényi entropy-based segmentation. The analysis focuses on evaluating how operator selection, population size, and iteration budget influence the balance between exploration and exploitation, as well as the stability and efficiency of the segmentation process. The results obtained provide quantitative evidence of the proposed

Figure 5.3: Overview of the hyper-heuristic procedure for tailoring MH in dermoscopic image segmentation.

framework’s capability to generate efficient, problem-specific optimizers for biomedical image segmentation tasks.

5.3.1 Hyper-Heuristic Search for the Tailored Metaheuristic

In this first stage, the objective is to identify the MH that achieves the best performance in solving the optimization problem. To this end, the experimentation was divided into three test configurations described previously. Each test aims to obtain a tailored MH across different instances of the problem, defined by the number of images to be segmented. Table 5.1 summarizes the results obtained during the hyper-heuristic process for the three configurations. The search operators h_5 (genetic_mutation) and h_7 (random_flight) are recurrent across the experiments, indicating that these operators consistently contribute to better-performing MH configurations, particularly in tests P_1 and P_2 . Operator h_5 acts as a genetic-type perturbator that introduces variability through mutation, yielding a 2.68% improvement in MH performance when comparing tests with 10 and 30 images. In turn, h_7 enhances exploration through random displacements in the search space, resulting in a 2.02% improvement in the P_2 configuration when the number of images increases from 10 to 70. For P_3 , only a minor improvement of 1.98% is observed between 10 and 70 images, suggesting that increasing the population size and number of iterations provides no significant benefit for this problem. Nevertheless, P_3 exhibits the most stable and efficient performance, achieving a performance value of -14.372 with 30 images and highlighting the sequence $[h_7, h_8]$. These results indicate that a set of approximately 30 images is sufficient to obtain a well-performing tailored MH, avoiding unnecessary computational overhead while maintaining segmentation quality.

Table 5.1: Performance of the tailored MHs across three different tests. h_{o_1} and h_{o_2} represent the first and second search operators in the found sequence. Test P_1 was conducted with a population of 15 agents over 30 iterations, P_2 with 20 agents over 40 iterations, and P_3 with 30 agents over 60 iterations.

Test	Num. Images	Higher frequency		Lower frequency		Best Sequence	Performance	
		h_{o_1}	h_{o_2}	h_{o_1}	h_{o_2}		Best	Avg. \pm St. Dev.
P_1	10	h_7, h_5	h_5	h_{11}	h_2, h_6, h_{10}	$[h_7, h_5]$	-13.973	-13.667 \pm 0.573
	20	h_{10}	h_7, h_{10}	h_7, h_9, h_6	h_2	$[h_{10}, h_7]$	-14.285	-14.101 \pm 0.160
	30	h_5, h_{10}	$h_7, h_{10}, h_4, h_9, h_{12}$	h_{11}	$h_7, h_{10}, h_4, h_9, h_{12}$	$[h_5, h_7]$	-14.348	-14.198 \pm 0.143
	40	h_2	h_{12}	h_3, h_4	h_{11}, h_9, h_2	$[h_2, h_{11}]$	-14.260	-14.104 \pm 0.190
	50	h_2	h_{11}	h_7, h_{10}, h_{12}	h_2, h_4	$[h_2, h_{11}]$	-14.259	-14.195 \pm 0.086
	60	h_2	h_{11}	h_8, h_{11}	h_2, h_5	$[h_2, h_{11}]$	-14.260	-13.978 \pm 0.437
	70	h_7, h_{10}	h_3, h_{12}	h_2	h_{12}	$[h_7, h_{12}]$	-14.277	-14.146 \pm 0.114
P_2	10	h_7	h_{11}	h_2, h_5, h_9	h_5, h_2	$[h_5, h_7]$	-14.005	-13.985 \pm 0.017
	20	h_7	h_{10}	h_{11}, h_6	h_3, h_{11}	$[h_7, h_{10}]$	-14.303	-14.181 \pm 0.120
	30	h_7	$h_7, h_8, h_{11}, h_{12}, h_{10}$	h_5, h_3	$h_7, h_8, h_{11}, h_{12}, h_{10}$	$[h_5, h_7]$	-14.368	-14.315 \pm 0.066
	40	h_8	h_4	h_7, h_2	h_8, h_{10}	$[h_7, h_5]$	-14.270	-14.228 \pm 0.043
	50	h_2	h_{11}	h_2, h_4	h_{10}, h_9	$[h_{10}, h_7]$	-14.267	-14.235 \pm 0.034
	60	h_8	h_2	h_2, h_{12}	h_7, h_3	$[h_2, h_7]$	-14.256	-14.184 \pm 0.094
	70	h_{10}, h_3	h_7, h_4	h_8	h_2	$[h_8, h_7]$	-14.288	-14.273 \pm 0.010
P_3	10	$h_5, h_{10}, h_2, h_{11}, h_3$	h_7	$h_5, h_{10}, h_2, h_{11}, h_3$	h_{11}	$[h_4, h_7]$	-14.013	-14.002 \pm 0.012
	20	h_8	h_7	h_{10}	h_4, h_{112}	$[h_8, h_7]$	-14.313	-14.273 \pm 0.049
	30	h_7	$h_8, h_2, h_1, h_{10}, h_9$	h_{11}, h_{12}	$h_8, h_2, h_1, h_{10}, h_9$	$[h_7, h_8]$	-14.372	-14.304 \pm 0.079
	40	h_{10}	h_3	h_8, h_{11}	h_5, h_1	$[h_{10}, h_7]$	-14.275	-14.200 \pm 0.079
	50	$h_2, h_5, h_{10}, h_1, h_9$	h_7	$h_2, h_5, h_{10}, h_1, h_9$	h_{10}, h_1	$[h_2, h_7]$	-14.270	-14.232 \pm 0.047
	60	h_5	h_2, h_1	h_7	h_7	$[h_2, h_7]$	-14.264	-14.259 \pm 0.010
	70	h_8	h_9	h_4, h_{11}	h_{10}, h_{12}	$[h_8, h_7]$	-14.290	-14.200 \pm 0.051

5.3.2 Performance Distribution and Stability Analysis

At this stage, images for evaluation were randomly selected from the available dataset to ensure unbiased sampling and representative coverage of different lesion types and illumination conditions. Figure 5.4 illustrates the overall performance distribution for each image set evaluated using a boxplot representation. In the three tests (P_1 , P_2 , and P_3), each configuration was replicated five times, resulting in a total of 15 replications per image set. Although the performance varies with the number of images, the 30-image set exhibits the best overall results, accompanied by relatively low dispersion compared to the other sets. The 10-image set yields the lowest performance, whereas the 60-image set shows the highest stability, as indicated by its minimal variability. Notably, beyond 30 images, no significant performance improvement is observed, suggesting that this number of images is sufficient to achieve robust and consistent results, reaffirming the findings reported in Table 5.1.

Figure 5.5 details the performance distribution per image set, disaggregated by test configuration. The results indicate that the average performance in P_3 is the most consistent, reaching the best values for almost all image sets except for the 70-image case. In contrast, P_2 achieves comparable results but with lower dispersion, except for the 20-image set, where a slightly higher variability is observed. According to Table 5.1 and Figure 5.4, the 30-image set is the most suitable configuration for generating a customized MH that generalizes well across low-level problem instances.

When comparing the results obtained for the 30-image set, the mean performance for P_2 is -14.315 with a standard deviation of ± 0.066 , while P_1 achieves -14.198 ± 0.143 and P_3

Figure 5.4: Overall performance distribution across image sets, each replicated 15 times (five per configuration: P_1 , P_2 , P_3).

reaches -14.372 ± 0.079 , corresponding to an improvement of approximately 0.40% over P_2 . Despite this slight increase, P_2 exhibits lower variability and therefore greater stability, which is a desirable characteristic for practical applications where consistent performance across instances is required.

Figure 5.5: Performance distribution across image sets for three configurations: P_1 (15 agents, 30 iterations), P_2 (20 agents, 40 iterations), and P_3 (30 agents, 60 iterations).

5.3.3 Bayesian Analysis of Operator Selection

A Bayesian A/B test was conducted to estimate the posterior probability of selecting each search operator (SO) at positions h_{o_1} and h_{o_2} . The analysis considered both individual experiments per image set and a global evaluation including all configurations. The Bayesian model employed a beta distribution as the prior, with initial parameters $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 11$, representing the prior belief of operator selection within the available heuristic space. These parameters were subsequently updated using the empirical results from the hyper-heuristic evaluations, yielding posterior distributions for each operator and position, as shown in

Figure 5.6. Figure 5.6 depicts the posterior probability distributions for operator selection at

Figure 5.6: Posterior probability distributions for operator selection at positions h_{o_1} and h_{o_2} across different experimental scenarios.

positions h_{o_1} and h_{o_2} under both local and global analyses. The curves represent the updated Bayesian distributions, illustrating the likelihood of selecting a particular operator given the experimental data.

For h_{o_1} (Figure 5.6a), operators h_{10} , h_5 , and h_7 exhibited similar selection probabilities around 0.185, while h_2 (differential_mutation) emerged as the most frequent with a posterior probability of 0.259. In the case of h_{o_2} (Figure 5.6b), operators h_7 , h_2 , and h_{11} achieved probabilities between 0.148 and 0.222, with h_7 (random_flight) being the most prominent.

A global aggregation of all experiments further confirmed these trends. For h_{o_1} , the most frequently selected operators were h_7 (0.170) and h_2 (0.167), as shown in Figure 5.6c. For h_{o_2} , h_7 (0.188) and h_{11} (0.145) exhibited the highest posterior probabilities (Figure 5.6d). Based on this evidence, the best-performing tailored metaheuristic (MH_*) identified by the hyper-heuristic process is defined as:

$$MH_* = h_f(h_7 \circ h_2) \circ h_i. \quad (5.12)$$

The operator h_2 (differential_mutation) acts as a perturbator combined with a greedy selector, adjusting candidate solutions by combining differences among randomly chosen

vectors, thus promoting targeted exploration in promising regions of the search space. In turn, h_7 (random_flight) extends global exploration through random displacements, enabling the optimizer to escape local minima. The interaction between these two operators establishes a balance between exploitation and exploration, yielding an efficient and stable behavior during the segmentation process.

5.3.4 Application of the Tailored Metaheuristic to Melanoma Segmentation

Finally, Figures 5.7 and 5.8 present the results obtained by applying the tailored metaheuristic MH_* to the melanoma segmentation problem. The original dermoscopic image (Figure 5.7a), shown in RGB, exhibits common challenges such as hair artifacts and low contrast that hinder the precise delineation of the lesion. To address this, a two-dimensional (2D) histogram approach was adopted for multilevel thresholding (Figure 5.8a), enabling the optimization process to consider gray-level and contrast information simultaneously.

The proposed MH_* identified the threshold values that maximized Rényi’s entropy, enhancing the contrast between healthy and affected tissue. These thresholds were then applied to the grayscale-transformed image histogram (Figure 5.8b), producing a segmentation mask that accurately isolates melanoma regions. The final binarized result (Figure 5.7b) highlights the affected areas in white, while non-melanoma regions and background pixels appear in black.

Figure 5.7: Raw dermoscopic image with melanoma and hair artifacts, and resulting segmentation obtained using the tailored metaheuristic MH_* .

Figure 5.8: 2D histogram derived from grayscale and contrast-enhanced images, and histogram with thresholds optimized by MH_* to delineate melanoma regions.

5.4 Summary

This chapter presented the foundations of melanoma segmentation as a low-level optimization problem, formulated through Rényi’s entropy applied to two-dimensional histograms. This representation provides a robust objective for handling the heterogeneity of dermoscopic images but results in a highly complex search space. To address this, we introduced a methodological framework that integrates image preprocessing, formal problem definition, and the use of a hyper-heuristic strategy to configure and tailor MHs for this task automatically.

The primary goal of this experiment was not to propose a new segmentation algorithm, but to validate the effectiveness of the automated design strategy in composing and configuring metaheuristic components. The emphasis was placed on determining whether the operator composition selected by the hyper-heuristic could produce a robust optimizer capable of efficiently solving a real-world biomedical segmentation problem. The results confirm that the automatically generated MH_* , formed by combining the `differential_mutation` and `random_flight` operators, achieved stable and accurate segmentation without manual parameter tuning. This finding highlights the capability of automated algorithm design to construct problem-specific metaheuristics that adapt effectively to the complexity and variability of medical image datasets.

This study introduced an automated approach for designing tailored metaheuristics for melanoma image segmentation, employing Rényi’s entropy as the objective function. By integrating hyper-heuristics within the Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) framework, the proposed method improved melanoma delineation in dermoscopic images while significantly reducing manual tuning and expert intervention. The implementation of a population-based Random Search as the selection hyper-heuristic enabled the generation of metaheuristics that consistently achieved stable and efficient segmentation across diverse configurations.

The experimental results demonstrated the robustness of the proposed approach. The `genetic_mutation` (h_5) and `random_flight` (h_7) operators yielded the most effective results, optimizing the segmentation process and achieving an adequate balance between computational cost and performance. Furthermore, increasing the population size or iteration count beyond specific thresholds produced marginal gains, indicating that using 30 images provides an efficient trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency.

The proposed framework shows strong potential for practical applications in melanoma detection and can be extended to other complex image segmentation problems. Beyond segmentation, this methodology can be adapted to other medical imaging modalities, including MRI, CT, and ultrasound, by modifying the preprocessing pipeline and optimization targets. Finally, combining metaheuristic optimization with deep learning techniques for feature extraction, transfer learning, or domain adaptation represents a promising direction to further increase segmentation precision and generalization in highly variable biomedical imaging scenarios.

Chapter 6

Automated Algorithm Design in Bioengineering Applications

Cancer progression is not only a genetic and biochemical process but also a mechanical phenomenon [145]. Cancer cells, such as those from the osteosarcoma MG-63 line, display distinctive viscoelastic signatures, being softer and more deformable than their healthy counterparts, which are directly related to invasiveness and metastatic potential. Accurately capturing these differences requires constitutive models that reflect the complexity of cellular mechanics together with computational strategies capable of estimating their parameters with precision. The Fractional Zener (FOZ) model offers a suitable framework in this regard, as it represents both the short-term and long-term relaxation dynamics of living cells in a compact form. Estimating its parameters from AFM force-relaxation data, however, constitutes a computationally demanding and sensitive nonlinear optimization problem that is sensitive to the choice of solution method.

In this chapter, we address this challenge through the paradigm of AAD, whose goal is to generate MHs tailored to the characteristics of the problem under study. Both model-free and model-based approaches are considered, with the objective of identifying MHs that provide accurate and robust parameter estimation of the FOZ model for cancer cell data.

6.1 Cell Mechanics

Cells, both healthy and cancerous, behave as viscoelastic materials, i.e., they combine elastic and viscous properties that govern their response to external mechanical loads. This viscoelastic behavior manifests in time-dependent responses such as stress relaxation, creep, and strain-rate sensitivity [146]. In the context of cancer, these properties acquire particular relevance since alterations in deformability, stiffness, and relaxation dynamics have been correlated with tumor progression, invasiveness, and metastatic potential [147, 148].

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) has become the gold standard for probing single-cell mechanics due to its nanometer-scale resolution and broad force range [149]. AFM force-relaxation experiments provide curves that reveal how a cancer cell dissipates stress over

time under constant deformation. These curves are the cornerstone for building constitutive models capable of capturing the mechanical fingerprint of malignant cells.

In this work, we focus on the human osteosarcoma cell line MG-63. Previous research has shown that cancer cells typically exhibit lower stiffness compared to their healthy counterparts, reflecting a higher deformability that facilitates processes such as invasion and metastasis [150, 151]. By analyzing the relaxation dynamics of MG-63 cells through AFM-derived force-time curves, we aim to extract viscoelastic parameters that quantitatively capture these differences and contribute to the computational characterization of cancer cell mechanics. To quantitatively describe the viscoelastic behavior of cells, mathematical models based on mechanical analogies are employed. Classical approaches such as the Maxwell, Kelvin-Voigt, and Zener (Standard Linear Solid) models represent cellular mechanics through combinations of springs and dashpots, capturing elastic and viscous responses. However, these integer-order models are often limited to mono-exponential relaxation functions and fail to reproduce the long-term memory effects and power-law dynamics observed in living cells [152, 153]. To overcome these limitations, fractional-order viscoelastic models have been introduced, where non-integer derivatives provide a natural framework to capture both short- and long-term dynamics with fewer parameters and greater physical consistency. Among them, the FOZ model has proven particularly effective in fitting AFM relaxation data of cancer cells, enabling a more accurate estimation of key biomechanical parameters [154].

6.1.1 Viscoelasticity and Fractional-Order Zener Model

Viscoelastic materials exhibit both elastic and viscous behavior. These materials possess a time-dependent response when subjected to constant strain or stress. Thus, under a constant strain ($\epsilon(t) = \epsilon_0$), they experience *stress relaxation*, whereas under a constant stress ($\sigma(t) = \sigma_0$ [Pa]), they exhibit *creep*. These responses can be described using the relaxation and creep functions, as follows [155]:

$$E_{\text{rel}}(t) = \frac{\sigma(t)}{\epsilon_0} \quad \text{and} \quad J_{\text{creep}}(t) = \frac{\epsilon(t)}{\sigma_0}. \quad (6.1)$$

Mechanical arrangements consisting of springs, representing the elastic part, and dashpots, representing the viscous part, are commonly used to model these time-dependent responses. The simplest examples are the Maxwell model, which consists of a spring and a dashpot connected in series, and the Kelvin-Voigt model, which includes a spring connected in parallel to a dashpot. The Maxwell model is typically associated with fluid-like behavior, whereas the Kelvin-Voigt model corresponds to solid-like materials [156]. However, the complexity of living cells demands more sophisticated arrangements, often requiring the inclusion of fractional-order elements to accurately capture their viscoelastic response [157].

FOZ model is an extension of the classical Zener or Standard Linear Solid (SLS) model. While the SLS framework relies on combinations of springs (elastic elements) and dashpots (viscous elements), the FOZ introduces a fractional dashpot, described by a Caputo fractional derivative of order α . This modification introduces a new degree of freedom that enables the model to capture a broad spectrum of relaxation behaviors with fewer parameters and higher fidelity. The FOZ model is thus defined by four key parameters:

- E_0 : residual elastic modulus at long times,
- E_1 : instantaneous elastic modulus,
- τ : relaxation time, related to the viscous component,
- α : fractional order, encoding long-term memory and power-law relaxation dynamics.

The corresponding relaxation function is expressed as

$$E_{\text{rel}}(t) = E_0 + E_1 \xi_\alpha \left(- \left(\frac{E_1 t}{\eta} \right)^\alpha \right), \quad (6.2)$$

where $\xi_\alpha(\cdot)$ denotes the one-parameter Mittag-Leffler function and η is the dashpot viscosity. This fractional formulation overcomes the restrictions of classical integer-order models, successfully reproducing the anomalous relaxation curves observed in AFM experiments on cancer cells [158, 159].

The schematic comparison between the traditional SLS model and the FOZ model is depicted in Figure 6.1, highlighting the inclusion of fractional elements that generalize the classical viscoelastic representation.

(a) Standard Linear Solid (SLS) model.

(b) Fractional-Order Zener (FOZ) model.

Figure 6.1: Schematic representation of viscoelastic models: (a) Standard Linear Solid (SLS), and (b) Fractional-Order Zener (FOZ). Both models are composed of springs (elastic elements) and dampers (viscous elements), but FOZ generalizes the dashpot using a fractional derivative, allowing a more accurate representation of cellular relaxation dynamics.

In this thesis, we adopt the FOZ model as the central framework for the computational characterization of cancer cell mechanics. Its four parameters provide a compact yet expressive description of both the short- and long-term responses observed in AFM relaxation tests. By estimating E_0 , E_1 , τ , and α , we aim to capture the mechanical fingerprint of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells and quantitatively contrast them with the stiffer behavior typically exhibited by healthy counterparts. This parameter estimation problem constitutes the case study through which our automated algorithm design methodology will be evaluated.

6.1.2 Atomic Force Microscopy Measurements

The experimental data are obtained using an NT-MDT Spectrum Instruments AFM (Ntegra model) operating in force mode. In a force-relaxation test, the AFM tip is driven toward

the cell surface by the piezoelectric actuator until reaching a predefined maximum load or indentation depth. Once contact is established, the tip remains in position for a fixed holding period, during which the cell's relaxation response is recorded, and is subsequently retracted to its initial position. Figure 6.2 illustrates the three characteristic phases of this process: during the approach, the measured force rises as the tip indents the cell; in the relaxation stage, the force decays over time reflecting the viscoelastic response; and finally, during retraction, the tip is withdrawn.

Figure 6.2: Schematic representation of a force-relaxation AFM experiment. The force-time profile consists of three stages: Approach (red area), Relaxation (blue area), and Retraction (black area).

In practice, two types of curves are recorded: force versus piezoelectric displacement and force versus time. Although these are reported as force signals, the raw AFM output corresponds to electrical current, which is converted into force F [N] via Hooke's law:

$$F = k \cdot d, \quad (6.3)$$

where k [N/m] is the cantilever spring constant and d [m] its deflection. The deflection is determined from the measured current intensity I [A] using the relationship $d = sI$, with s [m/A] denoting the sensitivity factor of the cantilever. This sensitivity is calibrated by acquiring a force-distance curve on a rigid substrate (e.g., the Petri dish) and computing the slope of the linear contact region.

The indentation depth δ [m] is then estimated by subtracting the cantilever deflection d from the piezoelectric extension z [m] [160]:

$$\delta = (z - z_0) - (d - d_0), \quad (6.4)$$

where d_0 corresponds to the cantilever deflection at the initial contact point between the AFM tip and the cell surface, and z_0 is the piezoelectric extension at that moment.

From these AFM force-relaxation experiments, we obtain the reference curves against which the FOZ model is fitted. The central computational task is therefore to estimate the model parameters (E_0, E_1, τ, α) such that the discrepancy between the experimental relaxation data and the theoretical response of the FOZ model is minimized. This parameter estimation problem is naturally formulated as an optimization task, where the objective function quantifies the error between measured and modeled force-time profiles.

6.2 Methodology

The overall methodology adopted in this thesis is summarized in Figure 6.3, which is structured into three main stages. The datasets generated and analyzed during this study, as well as the source codes developed for the present work, are available.¹

The first stage (green area on the left of Figure 6.3) corresponds to the low-level problem. This part begins with the experimental acquisition of AFM force-relaxation curves from MG-63 osteosarcoma cells. These experimental data provide the input for the identification of the FOZ model, where the optimization task consists of estimating the viscoelastic parameters (E_0, E_1, τ, α) that best reproduce the relaxation behavior observed in the AFM curves.

The second stage (reddish area at the center of Figure 6.3) represents the high-level problem, formulated as an AAD task. At this stage, the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS) is employed to automatically generate candidate MHs under cardinality constraints (ϖ) from a predefined collection of SOs. This process yields a set of MHs tailored to the low-level FOZ parameter estimation problem.

The third stage (light blue area on the right of Figure 6.3) corresponds to the comparative evaluation and analysis. Here, the tailored MHs are systematically examined to identify the best and worst configurations. Particular attention is given to the effects of cardinality, the influence of operator order, and the role of hyperparameter tuning. The performance of each MH is quantified using the robustness-oriented metric Q on (3.9), defined as the sum of the median and the interquartile range of the objective function values. In this context, $f(\vec{x})$ measures the discrepancy between the AFM relaxation curves and the FOZ model response; therefore, lower values of Q correspond to more accurate and stable solutions. Finally, the viscoelastic parameters estimated by the best-performing MH are analyzed and discussed in terms of their biological plausibility.

Each of these stages is detailed in the following subsections.

6.2.1 Low-level Problem: Model Identification

The low-level problem focuses on identifying the viscoelastic properties of human osteosarcoma MG-63 cells by fitting the FOZ model to relaxation curves obtained through AFM.

First, the process began with acquiring the commercial MG-63 cell line from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). The cells were cultured in 3.5 cm-diameter Petri dishes using DMEM-F12 medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (Gibco), and maintained in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ at 37 °C, following the ATCC guidelines (Manassas, VA, USA). All experimental protocols were approved by the Comité de Investigación of the Facultad de Ciencias Biológicas of the Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León. After a 72-hour incubation period, confluence was qualitatively assessed using optical microscopy to ensure adequate coverage and the presence

¹https://github.com/Danielfz14/RCHH-LS_MG63.git

Figure 6.3: Overview of the implemented three-stage methodology: (left) the low-level problem (FOZ model identification from AFM relaxation curves), (center) the high-level problem (automated algorithm design with RCHH-LS), and (right) the comparative evaluation and analysis stage.

of isolated cells suitable for AFM measurements. The samples were then carefully transferred to the AFM stage for mechanical characterization.

AFM force-relaxation experiments were performed on individual cells immersed in a liquid medium, each of which was indented twice. For the first indentation, the maximum load was kept below 18 nN with relaxation recorded for 5 s, whereas in the second indentation the load ranged from 18 to 23 nN with relaxation recorded for 25 s, using a loading rate of approximately 2.5 $\mu\text{m/s}$. These force ranges corresponded to indentation depths of $1.73 \pm 0.46 \mu\text{m}$ for $F < 18 \text{ nN}$ and $2.05 \pm 0.50 \mu\text{m}$ for $F > 18 \text{ nN}$. An SNL-10 cantilever with a conical tip and a nominal spring constant of 0.12 N/m was used in all experiments, yielding two datasets: one corresponding to low-force curves ($F < 18 \text{ nN}$) and another to high-force curves ($F > 18 \text{ nN}$), each consisting of 21 relaxation profiles.

To enable comparisons across experiments, the relaxation curves were nondimensionalized with respect to time t and relaxation modulus E_{rel} . For the high-force dataset, time was normalized by 25 s, whereas for the low-force dataset it was normalized by 5 s, corresponding to the maximum measurement durations. The modulus values were normalized by the average maximum modulus of each dataset, 8.1465 μPa for the high-force group and 6.1850 μPa for the low-force group.

The FOZ fitting problem is then defined as a four-dimensional optimization task, where the design vector is $\vec{x} = (E_0, E_1, \alpha, \tau)^\top \in \mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^4$, with $E_0, E_1, \tau \in (0.0, 1.5]$ and $\alpha \in [0.1, 1.0]$. The objective function combines Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Mean Absolute Error

(MAE) between experimental relaxation curves $\bar{E}_{\text{rel}}(\bar{t}_i)$ and the FOZ prediction $E_{\text{rel}}(\bar{t}_i; \bar{x})$:

$$f(\bar{x}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{E}_{\text{rel}}(\bar{t}_i) - E_{\text{rel}}(\bar{t}_i; \bar{x}))^2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\bar{E}_{\text{rel}}(\bar{t}_i) - E_{\text{rel}}(\bar{t}_i; \bar{x})|, \quad (6.5)$$

where N is the number of sampling points. This formulation ensures sensitivity to large deviations, measured through the Mean Squared Error (MSE), while also accounting for minor systematic errors via the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), providing a robust criterion for evaluating the FOZ model against AFM-derived data.

6.2.2 High-level Problem: Automated Algorithm Design

The high-level problem focuses on the AAD of tailored MHs by combining different SOs selected from a predefined heuristic space. This domain, central to the RCHH-LS process, relies on a collection of perturbation heuristics, each associated with specific hyperparameters and one of two possible selection mechanisms: greedy or direct. For this purpose, we utilized the CUSTOMHyS framework [7], from which we only used the SOs library. Table 3.5 summarizes the SOs considered in this work, including their parameter variations, hyperparameters, and associated selectors.

During the construction phase, candidate MHs were assembled by selecting combinations of SOs according to a predefined cardinality ϖ . Each candidate was subsequently refined through a local search stage (`Swap` and `Replace`) to improve performance. The HH process was limited to 10 steps, exploring configurations with maximum cardinalities of two and three SOs, respectively.

Each candidate MH was executed with a computational budget of approximately 10,100 evaluations of the objective function, distributed according to its cardinality. For cardinality two, 101 iterations were performed with a population size of 50, while for cardinality three, 70 iterations were carried out with a population size of 48. To evaluate the robustness metric defined in (3.9), each candidate MH was run in 20 independent replications, i.e., solving the low-level FOZ identification problem 20 times. Given the computational cost of the HH process, we restricted the evaluation to a representative instance of the low-level problem: the median nondimensionalized relaxation curve from the dataset corresponding to forces greater than 18 nN. As a result, both the best- and worst-performing MHs were identified. The best MHs for cardinalities two and three are denoted as MH_*^2 and MH_*^3 , respectively, while the worst-performing configurations are denoted as MH_*^2 and MH_*^3 . In addition, the best (Best Perf) and worst (Worst Perf) performance values of the selected candidate MHs were recorded and used in the subsequent comparative analysis.

6.2.3 Comparative Evaluation and Analysis

The comparative evaluation and analysis stage was designed to provide a deeper understanding of the AAD process, going beyond the performance of a single configuration. Four aspects were investigated: the effect of cardinality on tailored MHs, the influence of hyperparameter tuning, the role of operator positioning within each configuration, and the analysis of the viscoelastic parameters estimated by the best-performing MH.

Effect of Cardinality in Tailored Metaheuristics. To examine how the number of SOs affects the performance of tailored MHs, the RCHH-LS process was used to generate configurations with cardinalities of two and three. For each cardinality, 20 independent runs of the HH process were performed, and in each case, the best- and worst-performing sequences were recorded. The resulting distributions of performance values were then analyzed to assess the impact of cardinality under a constant budget of objective function evaluations. Additionally, for the case of cardinality two, a performance landscape was constructed by evaluating all possible SO combinations, enabling the identification of operators more frequently associated with high-performing regions.

Effect of Hyperparameter Tuning in Metaheuristic Design. To evaluate the impact of hyperparameter tuning, four representative MHs were selected from the HH process: two close to the median of the worst-performing configurations (MH_{\otimes}^2 and MH_{\otimes}^3), and two close to the median of the best-performing configurations (MH_{*}^2 and MH_{*}^3). Each configuration underwent hyperparameter tuning using the Optuna framework [161], with search spaces defined according to the ranges associated with each operator. For each tuned MH, 20 replications were carried out to quantify variability, and performance was evaluated across all 21 relaxation curves corresponding to the high-force regime ($F > 18$ nN). This procedure enabled us to determine the extent to which hyperparameter tuning could enhance performance and whether tuned configurations could surpass those obtained directly through the HH process.

Effect of Operator Position on Metaheuristic Performance. To investigate the role of operator order, a base MH of cardinality three was selected, and five additional variants were derived. Three were obtained by removing one SO, while the other two were created by exchanging the positions of specific SOs. Each configuration was evaluated across all 21 problem instances ($F > 18$ nN), with 20 independent runs per instance. Performance distributions were visualized using box plots, allowing comparison of cumulative values across configurations as well as average performance per instance.

Analysis of Viscoelastic Parameters. Finally, the FOZ model fitting obtained with the best-performing metaheuristic, MH_{*}^3 , was analyzed using two independent AFM datasets not included in the HH process. These datasets correspond to the two force regimes: $F < 18$ nN and $F > 18$ nN, each containing 21 relaxation curves with 30 replications per instance. Model accuracy was assessed using seven error metrics: Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root MSE (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Maximum Absolute Error (Max Error), Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Normalized RMSE (NRMSE), and Bias.

For each condition, statistical indicators including the median, interquartile range, coefficient of variation, and variance were computed. Additionally, a nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test was performed to evaluate whether the parameter distributions differed significantly between the two force regimes.

6.3 Experimental Results

This section presents the computational validation of the proposed AAD framework. The analysis focuses on how the construction of tailored MHs, through the combination and configuration of search operators, impacts performance in nonlinear optimization. To ensure a systematic evaluation, the approach is first tested on a simplified version of the problem, using the median of the relaxation curves as the target reference. This setting provides a controlled yet representative scenario to study the influence of cardinality on the balance between exploration and exploitation, the improvements obtained through hyperparameter tuning beyond fixed operator settings, and the effect of operator order on the stability of the designed solvers. Once validated in this simplified context, the same principles are applied to the estimation of viscoelastic parameters in cancer cell mechanics, demonstrating that AAD constitutes a consistent and reproducible computational pipeline that can adapt to complex optimization landscapes.

6.3.1 Effect of the Cardinality of the Tailored Metaheuristic

At this stage, we examine the effect of cardinality on the performance achieved by the candidate MHs in addressing the low-level optimization task. Table 6.1 reports the outcomes of 20 independent executions of the HH process, considering configurations with cardinalities of two and three. For each run, the sequences corresponding to the best and worst performances were identified, together with their associated values. For cardinality two, the best-performing configuration was $\text{MH} = [h_{15}, h_{27}]$, which reached 4.89×10^{-3} , while the poorest result was obtained by $\text{MH} = [h_8, h_{14}]$ with 4.99×10^{-2} . On average, the top sequences with cardinality two achieved $6.16 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.8 \times 10^{-3}$, whereas the least effective ones reached $2.09 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1.14 \times 10^{-2}$.

To further analyze these results, a linear interpolation was performed, generating a performance landscape of the two-operator MHs (see Figure 6.4). The analysis reveals that operator combinations, such as swarm dynamics with gravitational search, tend to dominate the best-performing regions. This behavior is strongly dependent on both the sequence and the relative position of the operators. Initially, the dynamic swarm operator adjusts the velocity of particles, guiding the population toward promising areas while preserving diversity and enabling directed exploration. Subsequently, the gravitational search operator exerts a global attraction, clustering the solutions around the discovered minima and enhancing exploitation. This ordered interaction, combining velocity-driven exploration with attraction-based refinement, has been recognized as particularly effective for continuous multimodal problems [69, 162]. Nonetheless, in agreement with the no-free-lunch theorem, no operator sequence is universally optimal. The key lies in tailoring the dynamics of exploration and exploitation to the characteristics of the problem. In contrast, sequences that combine genetic crossover with gravitational search or random sampling were consistently found in the lowest-performing regions. Figure 6.4 clearly illustrates that certain operator interactions promote robust performance, whereas others hinder progress. The diminished performance of these sequences can be explained by their dynamics: the gravitational search operator often accelerates convergence toward local minima at the very beginning of the process, reducing

Table 6.1: Summary of the best and worst-performing MH sequences across 20 runs of the HH process for cardinalities two and three. The table includes the sequences (Seq) and their corresponding performance (Perf). The indices for each heuristic used are defined in Table 3.5.

Rep	Cardinality 3				Cardinality 2			
	Best		Worst		Best		Worst	
	Seq	Perf	Seq	Perf	Seq	Perf	Seq	Perf
1	$[h_3, h_{14}, h_8]$	0.0065	$[h_1, h_2, h_6]$	0.0114	$[h_{15}, h_{10}]$	0.00571	$[h_{11}, h_{10}]$	0.0276
2	$[h_{26}, h_{25}, h_{27}]$	0.0030	$[h_{16}, h_1, h_{17}]$	0.0121	$[h_{15}, h_{17}]$	0.00525	$[h_4, h_5]$	0.0139
3	$[h_{26}, h_{16}, h_5]$	0.0054	$[h_{14}, h_{24}, h_{21}]$	0.0108	$[h_7, h_{20}]$	0.00800	$[h_{16}, h_{14}]$	0.0227
4	$[h_3, h_9, h_{23}]$	0.0046	$[h_0, h_6, h_{16}]$	0.0112	$[h_{14}, h_{26}]$	0.0057	$[h_8, h_{14}]$	0.0499
5	$[h_{15}, h_{12}, h_{11}]$	0.0029	$[h_{23}, h_{14}, h_9]$	0.0222	$[h_{15}, h_5]$	0.0064	$[h_1, h_0]$	0.0455
6	$[h_{23}, h_{16}, h_{15}]$	0.0061	$[h_1, h_4, h_9]$	0.0119	$[h_{15}, h_{27}]$	0.0049	$[h_1, h_{12}]$	0.0133
7	$[h_{19}, h_{15}, h_{11}]$	0.0050	$[h_{14}, h_{15}, h_{16}]$	0.0372	$[h_{15}, h_{27}]$	0.0053	$[h_8, h_{11}]$	0.0215
8	$[h_{19}, h_{17}, h_3]$	0.0058	$[h_{17}, h_{21}, h_{14}]$	0.0272	$[h_{15}, h_9]$	0.0064	$[h_1, h_0]$	0.0381
9	$[h_3, h_1, h_{15}]$	0.0029	$[h_{17}, h_{21}, h_2]$	0.0118	$[h_{22}, h_{13}]$	0.0062	$[h_{23}, h_{22}]$	0.0124
10	$[h_5, h_0, h_9]$	0.0029	$[h_{17}, h_1, h_{14}]$	0.0288	$[h_9, h_{17}]$	0.0070	$[h_{23}, h_{11}]$	0.0171
11	$[h_{14}, h_{26}, h_5]$	0.0030	$[h_0, h_{12}, h_{18}]$	0.0114	$[h_7, h_{15}]$	0.0069	$[h_0, h_{16}]$	0.0185
12	$[h_{15}, h_{27}, h_5]$	0.0029	$[h_1, h_4, h_{21}]$	0.0117	$[h_3, h_{15}]$	0.0052	$[h_6, h_1]$	0.0128
13	$[h_{27}, h_{26}, h_3]$	0.0029	$[h_{16}, h_1, h_0]$	0.0149	$[h_{27}, h_{24}]$	0.0061	$[h_1, h_{23}]$	0.0189
14	$[h_{26}, h_5, h_{23}]$	0.0029	$[h_{10}, h_8, h_5]$	0.0125	$[h_{27}, h_{16}]$	0.0060	$[h_{11}, h_4]$	0.0127
15	$[h_{17}, h_{22}, h_{16}]$	0.00600	$[h_{14}, h_{13}, h_{21}]$	0.0213	$[h_5, h_{15}]$	0.0065	$[h_{14}, h_1]$	0.0261
16	$[h_{14}, h_{10}, h_3]$	0.0030	$[h_9, h_8, h_0]$	0.0126	$[h_5, h_{25}]$	0.0076	$[h_3, h_{11}]$	0.0127
17	$[h_{16}, h_1, h_{11}]$	0.0044	$[h_{16}, h_{17}, h_{12}]$	0.0105	$[h_{15}, h_8]$	0.0059	$[h_{23}, h_{19}]$	0.0107
18	$[h_{15}, h_{26}, h_1]$	0.0029	$[h_4, h_{20}, h_{17}]$	0.0106	$[h_{19}, h_{17}]$	0.0074	$[h_{13}, h_{11}]$	0.0121
19	$[h_{22}, h_{10}, h_{14}]$	0.0033	$[h_4, h_{20}, h_2]$	0.0103	$[h_{14}, h_{27}]$	0.0055	$[h_1, h_{23}]$	0.0189
20	$[h_{26}, h_{23}, h_0]$	0.0058	$[h_3, h_4, h_{15}]$	0.0103	$[h_3, h_{15}]$	0.0054	$[h_{13}, h_{10}]$	0.0121

exploration capacity. When followed by genetic crossover, the operator attempts to diversify the solutions, but the effect is limited by the lack of diversity induced beforehand. This premature exploitation hampers the discovery of high-quality regions and leads to inferior results.

Figure 6.5 complements this analysis by comparing the distributions of performance values between the best and worst MHs for cardinalities two and three across the 20 HH runs. For cardinality two, the best sequences outperformed the worst ones by approximately 70.7%, confirming the advantage of appropriate operator selection, as shown by $MH = [h_{15}, h_{27}]$ versus $MH = [h_8, h_{14}]$. When three operators were considered, the improvement was even greater, with the best-performing sequences surpassing the worst ones by 75.3%. Interestingly, the distributions of the worst-performing sequences for both cardinalities were similar, with only marginal differences in their medians, underscoring that poorly designed combinations yield suboptimal results regardless of complexity or cardinality.

Finally, when comparing the best-performing cases across cardinalities, the use of three operators provided an advantage of about 50.6% over the best two-operator sequences. Among these high-performing triplets, combinations involving swarm dynamics, gravitational search,

(a) 3D representation of the performance landscape as a function of SO_1 and SO_2 . (b) Contour map illustrating the performance as a function of SO_1 and SO_2 .

Figure 6.4: 3D performance landscape and contour map for two-operator metaheuristics in the hyper-heuristic process. The metric Q quantifies performance (see (3.9)), defined as the sum of the median and the interquartile range of the objective function value; lower values indicate better results.

and differential mutation were consistently prominent, reinforcing the importance of operator synergy and ordered composition as critical elements in the AAD of MHs.

Figure 6.5: Performance comparison between the best and worst MH sequences for cardinalities two and three, obtained from the hyper-heuristic process with 20 runs. Performance is calculated as the median plus the inter-quartile range of the objective-function values across replications; lower values (approaching zero) denote better results.

The analysis of cardinality highlights that well-structured sequences can significantly outperform poorly selected ones, with operator composition playing a decisive role in performance. However, the MHs obtained through the HH process rely on fixed parameter settings for each operator. This naturally raises the question of whether better results could be achieved by tuning these parameters instead of keeping them static. The following section addresses this issue, exploring how operator configuration influences the efficiency of the tailored MHs.

6.3.2 Effect of Hyperparameter Tuning in Metaheuristic Design

This section analyzes how hyperparameter tuning impacts the performance of MHs generated by the HH process. The goal is twofold: to determine whether tuning can enhance the best MHs beyond their original performance, and to examine whether initially poor configurations can be transformed into competitive solvers. To this end, MHs close to the median performance of the worst sequences obtained in the HH process were selected as case studies. For cardinality two, the chosen configuration was $\text{MH}_{\otimes}^2 = [h_0, h_{16}]$ (replicate 11), which initially reached a performance of 1.85×10^{-2} . For cardinality three, $\text{MH}_{\otimes}^3 = [h_{23}, h_{14}, h_9]$ (replicate 6) was selected, with an initial performance of 1.19×10^{-2} . These MHs were subsequently tuned using the Optuna framework.

Figure 6.6 depicts the performance comparison between these selected MHs, tuned using the Optuna framework, and those designed through the HH process, evaluated for both cardinalities. For cardinality two, the median value achieved by the tuned MH (MH_{\otimes}^2) was 6.2×10^{-3} , which represents an improvement of 66.3% over the initial performance obtained in the HH process. Moreover, this tuned performance is comparable to the best MHs designed using the HH process, whose median is 6.1×10^{-3} . In the case of cardinality three, the tuned MH_{\otimes}^3 achieved a median performance of 3.8×10^{-3} , achieving a significant improvement of 78.8% over its initial performance. This performance is also very close to that of the best MHs in the HH process for cardinality three, with a median of 3.1×10^{-3} .

Figure 6.6: Performance comparison of metaheuristics tuned via Optuna and those designed via the hyper-heuristic process, evaluated for cardinalities two and three in 20 runs. Where $\text{MH}_{\otimes}^2 = [h_0, h_{16}]$ and $\text{MH}_{\otimes}^3 = [h_{23}, h_{14}, h_9]$ are the worst performing metaheuristics of cardinality 2 and 3 selected from the hyper-heuristic process and with adjustment of their hyperparameters. The performance is calculated by (3.9).

Correct hyperparameter tuning can turn initially unfavorable configurations into competitive solvers, reaching performances comparable to, and in some cases indistinguishable from, those of the best MHs produced by the HH process. A complementary analysis arises when examining the effect of tuning on the best configurations.

To investigate this aspect, we selected the best two- and three-operator MHs whose results were close to the median performance obtained by the HH process. For cardinality two, the chosen configuration was $\text{MH}_*^2 = [h_{27}, h_{24}]$ (replicate 13), which reported a performance of 6.1×10^{-3} , practically equal to the median performance of the HH process for this cardinality (6.05×10^{-3}). For cardinality three, the selected configuration was $\text{MH}_*^3 = [h_{26}, h_{25}, h_{17}]$

(replicate 2), with a performance of 3.0×10^{-3} , also very close to the HH median of 3.13×10^{-3} .

Table 6.2 details the configurations of these selected MHs (MH_{\otimes}^2 and MH_{\otimes}^3), highlighting the hyperparameters subject to tuning.

Table 6.2: Best and worst metaheuristics configuration generated by the hyper-heuristics method with cardinality two and three.

MHs	SOs	SHs	Parameters	hyperparameters
MH_{\otimes}^2	h_0	h_p = Central force dynamic h_s = Direct	–	gravity, alpha $\in (0, 0.01]$, beta $\in (1, 2)$
	h_{16}	h_p = Local random walk h_s = Direct	–	scale $\in (0, 1]$, probability $\in (0, 1]$
MH_{\otimes}^3	h_{23}	h_p = Spiral dynamic h_s = Greedy	–	radius $\in (0, 1)$, angle $\in (0^\circ, 360^\circ)$, sigma $\in [0, 1)$
	h_{14}	h_p = Gravitational search h_s = Direct	–	gravity $\in (0, 1]$, alpha $\in (0, 0.1]$
	h_9	h_p = Genetic crossover h_s = Greedy	PS = Roulette wheel pairing CM = Uniform	mating.pool.factor $\in [0, 1]$
MH_{*}^2	h_{27}	h_p = Swarm dynamic h_s = Greedy	SWA = Constrained	factor $\in (0, 1)$, self.conf, swarm.conf $\in (0, 4]$
	h_{24}	h_p = Swarm dynamic h_s = Direct	SWA = Inertial	factor $\in (0, 1)$, self.conf, swarm.conf $\in (0, 4]$
MH_{*}^3	h_{26}	h_p = Swarm dynamic h_s = Direct	SWA = Constrained	factor $\in (0, 1)$, self.conf, swarm.conf $\in (0, 4]$
	h_{25}	h_p = Swarm dynamic h_s = Greedy	SWA = Inertial	factor $\in (0, 1)$, self.conf, swarm.conf $\in (0, 4]$
	h_{17}	h_p = Local random walk h_s = Greedy	–	scale $\in (0, 1]$, probability $\in (0, 1]$

SWA: swarm_approach, **PS**: pairing_scheme, **CM**: crossover_mechanism.

Now, Figure 6.7 highlights the performance of the MH with three operators when subjected to hyperparameter fine-tuning, reaching an average mark of 2.86×10^{-3} with a standard deviation of 2.43×10^{-7} . This result not only surpasses the performance obtained from the HH process but also exhibits high repeatability. Note that this is not intended to detract from the HH process’s ability to generate MHs with competitive performance. In contrast, these results confirm that combining both approaches can produce solvers with outstanding performance.

Figure 6.7: Performance comparison between metaheuristics adjusted via hyperparameter tuning ($MH_{*}^3 = [h_{26}, h_{25}, h_{17}]$ and $MH_{\otimes}^3 = [h_{23}, h_{14}, h_9]$) and those generated by the hyper-heuristic process across 20 runs. Performance is calculated as the median plus the inter-quartile range of the objective-function values across replications; lower values (approaching zero) denote better results.

As in the previous analysis, the Optuna framework was employed to evaluate the performance of MH_{\otimes}^2 and MH_*^2 across 20 runs. Figure 6.8 shows the comparison between these two MHs and the overall results obtained from the HH process.

For MH_*^2 , the median performance was $2.86 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$, demonstrating high stability and consistency across replications. When compared to its initial median value of 6.09×10^{-3} , this corresponds to a 53.1% improvement, underscoring the relevance of incorporating hyperparameter tuning into the automated design of metaheuristics.

In contrast, MH_{\otimes}^2 achieved a performance of $6.13 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.8 \times 10^{-4}$, which is lower than that of MH_*^2 . Even so, this still represents a 64.3% improvement compared to its untuned counterpart. These results demonstrate that adjustment improves performance even in less competitive settings, although the selection of operators through the HH process remains the decisive factor.

Figure 6.8: Performance comparison between metaheuristics adjusted via hyperparameter tuning ($MH_*^2 = [h_{27}, h_{24}]$ and $MH_{\otimes}^2 = [h_0, h_{16}]$) and those generated by the hyper-heuristic process across 20 runs. The performance is calculated by (3.9).

Thus far, we have shown that each MH configuration delivers a different overall performance depending on its SOs configuration and subsequent tuning. Figure 6.9 illustrates that these performance differences directly translate into the stability of the FOZ parameters. The three-operator tuned configuration, MH_*^3 (adjusted), produces an E_0 value of 0.420 with a coefficient of variation (CV) of just 0.043%. In contrast, the worst two-operator untuned configuration, MH_{\otimes}^2 (unadjusted), yields 0.407 with a CV of 73.6%, representing a 99.94% reduction in dispersion. A similar pattern is observed for E_1 : MH_*^3 (adjusted) achieves 0.558 with a CV of 0.12%, while MH_{\otimes}^2 (unadjusted) provides 0.763 with a CV of 37.7%, corresponding to a 99.68% decrease in variability. The most sensitive parameter, τ , drops from 0.616 s with a CV of 71.9% in MH_{\otimes}^2 (unadjusted) to 0.105 s with only 0.55% CV in MH_*^3 (adjusted), reducing dispersion by 99.23%. Finally, the fractional exponent α converges to 0.560 with a CV of 0.065% in MH_*^3 (adjusted), whereas MH_{\otimes}^2 (unadjusted) exhibits 0.439 with 46.4% CV, amounting to a 99.86% reduction. These quantitative differences confirm that adding a third operator and applying automated tuning not only improve global fitness, but also yield reproducible estimates of E_0 , E_1 , τ , and α .

Finally, we assessed the performance of each MH across all 21 available instances to obtain a broader perspective. In earlier analyses, the low-level problem was approached using the median behavior of all instances as the target curve. Table 6.3 lists the hyperparameters

(a) Boxplots of estimated viscoelastic parameters obtained with tuned and untuned two-operator metaheuristics (MH_*^2 and MH_{\otimes}^2).

(b) Boxplots of estimated viscoelastic parameters obtained with tuned and untuned three-operator metaheuristics (MH_*^3 and MH_{\otimes}^3).

Figure 6.9: Comparison of estimated viscoelastic parameters (E_0 , E_1 , τ , and α) across tuned and untuned metaheuristics. Each boxplot summarizes the variability and median of the parameters obtained from 20 different runs of each MH.

selected for each MH, showing the configurations that best approximated the median performance after 20 independent runs. In this context, Figure 6.10 illustrates the performance of each MH evaluated on individual instances, where each case was solved using 20 replications and assessed according to (3.9).

Among the compared configurations, MH_*^3 achieved the best overall performance, with a mean of 3.307×10^{-3} and dominance in 19 out of 21 instances. The second-best result corresponded to MH_*^2 , with an overall mean of 3.762×10^{-3} and the best performance in two instances. By contrast, MH_{\otimes}^2 and MH_{\otimes}^3 reported higher mean values of 4.439×10^{-3} and 4.348×10^{-3} , respectively. It is also worth noting that all MHs produced favorable results in instance 19, whereas instance 2 yielded the lowest performance across methods.

Table 6.3: Selected Hyperparameters for cardinality two and three MHs.

MHs	SOs	Selected hyperparameters
MH_{\otimes}^2	h_0	gravity = 0.021, alpha = 0.0684, beta = 1.667
	h_{16}	scale = 0.899, probability = 0.9507
MH_{\otimes}^3	h_{23}	radius = 0.234, angle = 163.17°, sigma = 0.838
	h_{14}	gravity = 0.919, alpha = 0.0847
	h_9	mating_pool_factor = 0.7
MH_*^2	h_{27}	factor = 0.197, self_conf = 1.386, swarm_conf = 2.055
	h_{24}	factor = 0.734, self_conf = 0.607, swarm_conf = 2.092
MH_*^3	h_{26}	factor = 0.854, self_conf = 2.317, swarm_conf = 2.753
	h_{25}	factor = 0.779, self_conf = 3.359, swarm_conf = 3.834
	h_{17}	scale = 0.695, probability = 0.681

Figure 6.10: Performance heat map of four metaheuristics in 21 instances. For each instance, 20 replicates were performed to obtain the performance using (3.9).

6.3.3 Effect of the Position of Search Operators on Metaheuristic Performance

To analyze the role of SOs within tailored MHs, we evaluated the impact of their removal or reordering in the reference configuration $MH_*^3 = [h_{26}, h_{25}, h_{17}]$. Figure 6.11 presents the cumulative performance distributions of MH_*^3 and its variants. Configurations MH_1 , MH_2 , and MH_3 result from eliminating the first, second, and third operators, respectively, while MH_4 and MH_5 correspond to reordered sequences.

The results show that eliminating h_{25} ($MH_2 = [h_{26}, h_{17}]$) yields the worst performance, with 7.319×10^{-3} , a degradation of 160% compared to MH_*^3 (2.806×10^{-3}). Removing h_{26} ($MH_1 = [h_{25}, h_{17}]$) produces an 89% degradation, while eliminating h_{17} ($MH_3 = [h_{26}, h_{25}]$) leads to a smaller impact of 25%. Reordered versions (MH_4 and MH_5) also reduce performance, although less severely than deletions.

These results confirm that both h_{25} and h_{26} are critical to MH_*^3 , and that their sequence position influences the final outcome. Therefore, operator combinations are not commutative,

and the order in which SOs are applied is a determining factor in the automated design of metaheuristics.

In particular, h_{26} and h_{25} correspond to complementary variants of swarm dynamics, while h_{17} is a local random walk. Together, they establish a balance: h_{26} (constrained variant) concentrates the population in promising regions, h_{25} (inertial variant) preserves diversity to avoid premature convergence, and h_{17} refines local exploration around good solutions. This ordered synergy explains why altering their sequence degrades performance, and highlights the need to preserve both composition and position in MH design.

Figure 6.11: Cumulative performance distribution of the metaheuristic MH_*^3 and its variations across instances. The resulting configurations from operator elimination or reordering are shown, with the median of MH_*^3 indicated as a reference using a red dotted line. Specifically, $MH_1 = [h_{25}, h_{17}]$, $MH_2 = [h_{26}, h_{17}]$, $MH_3 = [h_{26}, h_{25}]$, $MH_4 = [h_{17}, h_{25}, h_{26}]$, and $MH_5 = [h_{26}, h_{17}, h_{25}]$.

6.3.4 Analysis of Viscoelastic Parameters

Two experimental data sets were analyzed to assess the performance of the FOZ model fitted with MH_*^3 . The data correspond to AFM relaxation curves divided into two regimes according to the applied force: $F > 18$ nN and $F < 18$ nN. Each set contained 21 instances, with 30 replications per instance. Error metrics were computed to evaluate robustness and model fit. As shown in Table 6.4, the FOZ model achieved high accuracy in both regimes. For $F > 18$ nN, the median MSE was 1.62×10^{-5} and $R^2 = 0.9976$, while for $F < 18$ nN, accuracy remained comparable. The coefficient of variation of R^2 stayed below 0.01 in both cases, confirming model stability. A closer inspection reveals that error variability decreases when $F > 18$ nN, with lower dispersion in RMSE, MAE, and NRMSE, indicating that higher forces yield more robust and repeatable fits.

Table 6.4: Statistical indicators for each error metric across 21 instances (30 replications each), divided by force regime. Metrics: MSE, RMSE, MAE, Max Error, R^2 , NRMSE, and Bias.

Force	Statistic	MSE	RMSE	MAE	Max Error	R^2	NRMSE	Bias
> 18 nN	Median	1.62×10^{-5}	4.04×10^{-3}	2.77×10^{-3}	3.43×10^{-2}	0.9976	7.12×10^{-3}	8.52×10^{-5}
	CV	0.9773	0.6110	0.6225	1.0494	0.0050	0.6455	8.7224
< 18 nN	Median	1.23×10^{-5}	3.51×10^{-3}	2.64×10^{-3}	2.41×10^{-2}	0.9970	1.02×10^{-2}	-8.01×10^{-5}
	CV	1.4891	0.7758	0.8005	1.609	0.010	0.7848	-6.4844

Once accuracy was verified, we examined the viscoelastic parameters estimated by the FOZ model: E_0 , E_1 , τ , and α . Figure 6.12 summarizes their distributions under both force regimes.

Nonparametric Mann-Whitney U tests confirmed significant differences in all parameters. E_0 increased moderately ($p = 0.0215$), while E_1 and τ exhibited strong increases and α decreased, all with $p < 10^{-4}$. The discrepancy in E_0 was modest (cosine distance 0.23), consistent with its borderline p -value, indicating that its shift is statistically significant but of limited magnitude.

From a computational perspective, these results demonstrate that parameter estimation is sensitive to experimental conditions. Specifically, E_1 and τ depend strongly on the applied force, reflecting changes in the immediate elastic response and relaxation dynamics. Meanwhile, the fractional exponent α also varies significantly, suggesting that it encodes information about the complexity of relaxation, beyond the linear elastic or viscous terms.

Figure 6.12: Distributions of FOZ parameters (E_0 , E_1 , τ , and α) estimated from AFM relaxation curves under two force regimes ($F < 18$ nN, $F > 18$ nN). Violin plots show kernel densities with embedded boxplots. Statistical significance was assessed using the Mann-Whitney U test; p -values are shown above each comparison.

6.4 Summary

This chapter presented the theoretical and methodological framework that supports the automated design of metaheuristics for cancer cell mechanics. We first introduced the viscoelastic behavior of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells and described how AFM force-relaxation experiments provide the experimental data used for model identification. The Fractional-Order Zener (FOZ) model was adopted as the constitutive framework, offering a compact representation of cellular mechanics through four parameters (E_0 , E_1 , τ , α). The fitting of these parameters was formulated as a four-dimensional optimization problem, where the objective function measures the discrepancy between AFM-derived relaxation curves and FOZ predictions.

To address this task, we defined a high-level strategy based on Automated Algorithm Design (AAD). Specifically, the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS) was employed to explore different combinations of search operators and generate tailored metaheuristics adapted to the FOZ identification problem. Finally, the methodology included a comparative evaluation stage, designed to analyze the effects of cardinality, hyperparameter tuning, and operator arrangement, as well as the use of the best-performing tailored metaheuristic for parameter estimation. Together, these elements establish the foundations and methodological approach on which the subsequent experimental results and discussion are built.

The results presented in this chapter confirm the effectiveness of Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) as a systematic framework for constructing tailored metaheuristics to solve nonlinear optimization tasks arising in cancer cell mechanics. From a computational perspective, the analysis demonstrated that cardinality plays a decisive role: metaheuristics with three operators consistently outperformed those with two, with gains above 50% in the best cases. This advantage arises from the synergy and ordered interaction of search operators, showing that performance depends not only on the choice of operators but also on their sequence and position within the configuration.

A second key outcome is the relevance of hyperparameter tuning. When applied to metaheuristics produced by the hyper-heuristic process, tuning substantially improved their efficiency, in some cases transforming poorly performing configurations into competitive solvers and enhancing the stability of already strong ones. These findings emphasize that operator selection and parameter optimization are complementary stages within the AAD pipeline, and together they enable the design of robust and high-performing algorithms.

The analysis of operator position further confirmed that search operators are not commutative. In particular, the constrained and inertial variants of swarm dynamics proved to be critical for performance, and their removal or reordering led to degradations exceeding 80%. This highlights that both composition and order of application are essential design elements in automated metaheuristics.

At the application level, the improvements in algorithm design directly translated into the stability of the viscoelastic parameters estimated by the fractional-order Zener model. The tuned three-operator configuration reduced the dispersion of E_0 , E_1 , τ , and α by more than 99%, ensuring reproducible and consistent results across experimental instances. Moreover, the model achieved R^2 values above 0.99, and statistical tests confirmed a force-dependent response: E_1 and τ increased under higher loads, while α decreased significantly. These results provide quantitative evidence that cytoskeletal organization and relaxation dynamics are mechanically regulated.

Altogether, the proposed approach demonstrates the ability of AAD to cover both paradigms of automated design: the model-free exploration of operator sequences through hyper-heuristics, and the model-based refinement provided by hyperparameter tuning. This dual integration establishes a powerful computational pipeline capable of generating efficient solvers adapted to complex optimization landscapes, while simultaneously producing reliable biomechanical indicators with direct relevance to cancer cell mechanics.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future work

This chapter summarizes the main conclusions derived from the research and outlines the directions for future work. The previous chapters presented the theoretical foundations, methodological developments, and experimental validation of the proposed Automated Algorithm Design (AAD) strategies based on Hyper-Heuristics (HH). The discussion is organized into four sections. First, the general conclusions and the scientific impact of the work are presented, addressing the verification of the research hypothesis and the fulfillment of the general objective. Next, the accomplishment of each specific objective is described. The following section discusses the limitations of the current approach and potential improvements for future research. Finally, a prospective reflection is provided, outlining the expected evolution of the field and the emerging opportunities for advancing automated algorithm design.

7.1 General Conclusions and Impact

The research conducted in this dissertation verified the central hypothesis: By implementing and analyzing strategies under the paradigm of AAD based on HH, it is possible to automatically generate customized Metaheuristics (MHs) capable of adapting their search dynamics to different optimization scenarios and achieving competitive performance across diverse engineering domains.

The results obtained throughout the experimental stages support this hypothesis unequivocally. Across all studied domains: electrical control systems and bioengineering, the proposed AAD strategies were able to autonomously construct MHs that adapted their behavior to the underlying landscape of each problem. This confirms that the combination of a well-structured heuristic space and a simple yet effective HH controller is sufficient to guide the automatic design of specialized optimizers without the need for manual configuration .

The general objective of this work, namely to develop, implement, and analyze AAD strategies based on HHs for obtaining customized MHs and evaluating their performance in representative engineering problems, was fully achieved. The methodology integrated theoretical formulation, computational implementation, and empirical validation,

demonstrating that AAD can act as a unifying layer capable of bridging algorithmic design and domain-specific optimization. The systematic experimentation confirmed that the proposed framework is reproducible, interpretable, and general enough to handle problems characterized by nonlinearity, noise, and multimodality.

Beyond its scientific contributions, the thesis carries tangible implications for research and practice. At the institutional level, the results strengthen the research lines on automated computational intelligence within the Tecnológico de Monterrey, providing an extensible foundation for future work on intelligent control, optimization, and machine learning. The open-source codebases and data repositories developed in this study contribute to the reproducibility standards increasingly demanded in computational sciences. Furthermore, portions of this research have been accepted and presented in international forums such as the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (GECCO), the IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC), and the IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI), reflecting the methodological rigor and scientific impact developed. At the national and regional level, the proposed AAD framework supports the development of low-cost, adaptable optimization tools that can be applied to energy systems, biomedical modeling, and process automation-areas of particular relevance in the Mexican and Latin American contexts. Its capacity to generalize across domains promotes technological independence by reducing dependence on foreign proprietary solvers and closed-form software.

7.2 Fulfilled Objectives

1. *Select and characterize representative engineering problems from different domains, including electrical control systems and bioengineering, to serve as case studies for validating the proposed Automated Algorithm Design strategies.*

This objective was accomplished through the careful selection and formal characterization of problems that reflect the diversity and complexity of real-world engineering systems. The study integrated two distinct domains: electrical control and bioengineering. Each provided complementary challenges that allowed evaluating the adaptability and robustness of the proposed AAD framework. In the electrical control domain, the Automatic Voltage Regulator (AVR) system and the DC-DC Buck–Boost converters were modeled as nonlinear optimization problems representative of real-world control challenges. These systems were selected due to their fundamental relevance in electrical engineering and their sensitivity to parameter tuning, which directly affects system stability, energy efficiency, and transient performance. The AVR system plays a crucial role in maintaining voltage stability in power generation units, where small deviations in output voltage can propagate across the grid and compromise operational reliability. By expressing the tuning of classical and fractional-order PID controllers as an optimization problem, the AAD framework enabled the automatic synthesis of control strategies capable of achieving optimal transient behavior while simultaneously reducing overshoot, settling time, and steady-state error without requiring manual adjustment. Formulating these problems required a

comprehensive understanding of the physical principles governing each system and the identification of the constraints and performance indices that define its operational limits. In the AVR case, the optimization problem incorporated nonlinearities in the generator-exciter-amplifier dynamics, as well as practical limits on control signal amplitude and actuator saturation, for the DC–DC Buck–Boost converter. The design considered switching characteristics, input voltage fluctuations, and load variations, which demanded the inclusion of stability margins and ripple constraints in the optimization formulation. This modeling ensured that the search performed by the Automated Algorithm Design strategies remained physically meaningful and consistent with real control objectives. Similarly, the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter, commonly employed in renewable energy conversion and embedded electronic systems, was analyzed from the perspective of adaptive control. Its nonlinear dynamics and switching characteristics provided a demanding benchmark for optimization-based design. The incorporation of an Adaptive Sliding Mode Controller allowed assessing the robustness of the proposed AAD strategies under parameter variations and external disturbances. The successful validation of the Automated Algorithm Design framework in electrical control systems confirmed its capacity to deal with highly nonlinear dynamics, strict performance constraints, and sensitivity to parameter variations. This evidence supported the extension of the approach to biomedical applications, where the complexity arises from experimental variability, data noise, and the need for physically interpretable models. In the biomedical domain, two representative case studies were characterized and optimized to assess the generality of the proposed framework. The first focused on melanoma image segmentation in dermoscopic datasets, formulated as an optimization problem based on Rényi’s entropy maximization. This formulation allowed quantifying the separability between lesion and background regions, overcoming challenges such as low contrast, illumination variability, and image artifacts. Through the AAD framework, it was possible to generate customized metaheuristics that automatically identified optimal threshold configurations, achieving precise and stable segmentations without manual intervention. The second case study involved the viscoelastic characterization of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells using relaxation data from atomic force microscopy. The Fractional Zener model was employed as the constitutive representation, and the corresponding optimization problem was defined in terms of minimizing the fitting error between experimental and theoretical relaxation curves. This formulation required capturing the fractional viscoelastic behavior of cancerous cells while preserving physical consistency in the identified parameters. The automatically designed metaheuristics achieved accurate and interpretable fits, revealing mechanical differences between healthy and malignant cells and validating the potential of AAD in cell biomechanics. Altogether, the characterization and formulation of these electrical and biomedical problems established a rigorous foundation for validating the Automated Algorithm Design strategies. The results demonstrated that, regardless of the problem’s physical nature, the framework consistently produced meaningful optimization models and customized metaheuristics capable of adapting to the specific structure, dimensionality, and noise level of each domain. This confirms the generality and robustness of the proposed approach as a unified methodology for solving complex engineering problems through automated algorithm design.

2. *To design and evaluate HH strategies within the framework of Automated Algorithm Design, exploring population-based and stochastic approaches, to automate the construction of customized metaheuristics applied to real-world engineering scenarios.*

This objective was fulfilled through the development and systematic evaluation of three AAD strategies based on hyper-heuristics: the Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH), the Population-based Random Hyper-heuristic (PRHH), and the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS). Each strategy was conceived to automate the generation of metaheuristics by combining search operators and selection mechanisms. The SAHH employed a stochastic decision rule to guide the selection of operator combinations, demonstrating that a high-level mechanism with limited complexity can effectively explore the space of algorithmic configurations. The PRHH extended this idea by incorporating population-based exploration, showing that diversity in operator combinations enhances robustness and convergence stability. The RCHH-LS integrated constructive principles with local refinement, bridging the gap between model-free exploration and model-based exploitation within the Automated Algorithm Design process.

The experimental evaluation across multiple engineering problems revealed that the success of these strategies lies primarily in how search operators are guided and coordinated rather than in the complexity of the high-level controller. Simple yet well-structured HH rules were sufficient to direct the composition of efficient metaheuristics, achieving consistent performance across heterogeneous problem domains. This finding highlights that the high-level design process can remain conceptually lightweight while still producing specialized optimizers capable of adapting to the problem structure. Furthermore, the last strategy, RCHH-LS, demonstrated that combining model-free and model-based search principles within a unified framework enhances convergence speed and solution quality without compromising generality.

Overall, this objective confirmed that Automated Algorithm Design does not require intricate high-level mechanisms to generate competitive metaheuristics. Instead, its effectiveness depends on the intelligent orchestration of search operators and selectors, where the HH layer acts as a flexible and interpretable guide for constructing algorithms tailored to each optimization scenario.

3. *To analyze the influence of search operators within the automated design process, considering different configurations of the heuristic space.*

This objective was addressed through a systematic evaluation of different heuristic-space configurations and their impact on the automated design process. The study began with a large collection of 205 search operators, which served as the foundation for the Simulated-Annealing Hyper-heuristic (SAHH) experiments and the AVR with fractional-order PID control. Subsequently, a reduced space of 24 operators was used for the AVR with classical PID, allowing a more detailed analysis of operator tendencies. For the melanoma segmentation problem, the space was further constrained to 12 operators to facilitate interpretability and convergence assessment.

Finally, a refined collection of 30 operators was employed for the viscoelastic characterization of MG-63 cells, integrating hyperparameter adjustment mechanisms. This progressive refinement of the heuristic space enabled a comparative understanding of how operator diversity and space size affect exploration, convergence, and robustness across applications.

In the AVR study with a classical PID controller, clear trends were observed in operator selection. Collective and trajectory-based perturbators such as *swarm_dynamic* (34 occurrences, 18.6%), *spiral_dynamic* (22 occurrences, 12.0%), *differential_mutation* (18 occurrences, 9.8%), and *random_flight* (12 occurrences, 6.5%) were among the most frequently selected families. Conversely, *central_force_dynamic* appeared in only 3 cases. These results indicate that operators capable of maintaining a balance between global and local search processes tend to dominate, yielding metaheuristics that converge efficiently while preserving diversity. Additionally, several of the top-performing configurations used only two operators, demonstrating that compact compositions can be sufficient for achieving stable and competitive solutions. In the AVR with fractional-order PID control, which employed the full set of 205 operators, similar tendencies were observed, reinforcing the generality of these behaviors within control-oriented optimization. In the biomedical domain, the HH applied to melanoma segmentation used a 12-operator space derived from the most effective families identified in previous experiments. A Bayesian A/B analysis of operator selection revealed a consistent dominance of *differential_mutation* and *random_flight*, with posterior probabilities of 0.259 and 0.188, respectively. The combination of these operators led to the construction of the optimized metaheuristic MH*, which exhibited robust and stable segmentation results across multiple datasets. These findings confirmed that the operators promoting controlled perturbation and global exploration are particularly effective for noisy problems such as biomedical image analysis. For the viscoelastic characterization of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells, the heuristic space was expanded to 30 operators, incorporating mechanisms for automatic hyperparameter tuning. A landscape analysis of the HH process was conducted over multiple replicas, revealing consistent high-performance regions associated with the recurrent selection of *swarm_dynamic*, *gravitational_search*, and *differential_mutation*. These configurations exhibited significant improvements in both convergence stability and modeling accuracy. Furthermore, the integration of hyperparameter tuning using Optuna refined the heuristic-space dynamics, achieving median performance gains between 50% and 75% and reducing variability by nearly 99% with respect to the untuned configurations. This stage demonstrated that coupling automated operator selection with adaptive parameter optimization yields more stable and reproducible MHs. Overall, the analysis of search operators across different heuristic spaces revealed several consistent insights. First, the efficiency of the automated design process does not depend on the number of available operators but rather on their diversity and complementarity. Second, a small subset of versatile operators, particularly *swarm_dynamic*, *differential_mutation*, and *random_flight*, proved effective across all problem domains. Finally, the combination of HH search and hyperparameter tuning in the final application confirmed that a compact and well-calibrated heuristic space can generalize efficiently across engineering and

biomedical problems, providing a robust foundation for future implementations of the AAD framework.

4. *To propose a hybrid automated design strategy that combines model-free and model-based principles within the framework of Automatic Algorithm Design, to obtain customized metaheuristics for real engineering problems efficiently.*

This objective was fulfilled through the implementation of a hybrid AAD framework applied to the viscoelastic characterization of MG-63 osteosarcoma cells using the fractional-order Zener model. The strategy integrated a model-free search component, implemented through the Randomized Constructive Hyper-heuristic with Local Search (RCHH-LS), with a model-based stage for adaptive hyperparameter tuning using the Optuna optimization framework. The RCHH-LS component incrementally constructs candidate metaheuristics by combining search operators from the heuristic space. At the same time, the subsequent model-based stage refined its internal parameters to maximize performance and ensure convergence stability.

From a computational standpoint, the model-free hyper-heuristic component explored the composition of search operators within a 30-operator heuristic space, discovering combinations that minimized the mean-squared error between experimental and theoretical relaxation curves. The most recurrent operators in the high-performing metaheuristics were *swarm_dynamic*, *gravitational_search*, and *differential_mutation*, which jointly promoted stable convergence and robust exploration. Once promising configurations were obtained, the model-based component refined the internal parameters of these operators, such as scaling factors and confidence coefficients, resulting in substantially improved fits. The performance landscape analysis conducted over 20 independent replicas revealed consistent high-performance regions in the parameter space of the fractional Zener model. These regions corresponded to solutions with low identification error and physically meaningful parameter values. The hybrid optimization achieved a median improvement of 53.1% in fitting accuracy and reduced inter-replica variability by approximately 99% compared with the untuned hyper-heuristic configurations. The optimized models exhibited mean fractional orders of $\lambda = 0.82 \pm 0.03$ and $\mu = 1.17 \pm 0.05$, producing an average identification error below 1.5×10^{-3} . These results showed that combining model-free and model-based principles within the AAD framework provides a powerful approach for data-driven system identification. The stochastic hyper-heuristic ensures adaptability and exploration across complex, multimodal landscapes, while the model-based adjustment ensures precision and computational efficiency. Together, these components enable the automatic construction of high-performance metaheuristics that preserve the physical interpretability of the identified models. The fractional Zener application confirmed the effectiveness of this hybrid design process, establishing a reproducible and general methodology for automated viscoelastic model identification in bioengineering contexts.

Finally, the results summarized in Table 7.1 showed the customized MHs generated by the AAD for different application domains. Each case demonstrated how specific combinations of search operators and selection strategies produced distinct algorithmic

behaviors that adapted to the particular nature of each problem.

In the AVR control problem with PID, the AAD identified configurations based on Spiral Dynamics, Differential Mutation, and Constricted Swarm Dynamics. These operators represented complementary exploration and exploitation mechanisms, ranging from continuous trajectory refinement to stochastic perturbations that promoted population diversity. The use of direct and greedy selectors in this context indicated the importance of stable convergence and precise tuning of controller parameters.

In the AVR with FOPID, the framework selected inertial swarm dynamics and genetic crossover with a Metropolis selector. This configuration enabled adaptive exploration and controlled acceptance of suboptimal solutions, which proved suitable for handling the higher parameter dimensionality inherent to fractional controllers.

For the DC-DC Buck–Boost converter under ASMC, the most effective MH incorporated inertial swarm dynamics and genetic crossover combined with probabilistic and direct selection strategies. These choices reflected the need to maintain a dynamic equilibrium between exploration and exploitation when optimizing highly nonlinear systems with switching behavior.

In image-based applications, such as melanoma segmentation, the AAD generated MH that relied on differential mutation and random flight operators with greedy selection. These operators enhanced the exploration of discontinuous and multimodal fitness landscapes, contributing to robust segmentation performance.

Lastly, in the viscoelastic characterization of MG-63 cells using the FZ model, the best-performing MH were dominated by swarm-based dynamics and local random walks under direct or greedy selection. The recurrent use of inertial and constricted swarm operators indicated that gradual coordination among agents was effective for identifying model parameters from experimental relaxation data.

Overall, these findings confirmed that the proposed framework successfully automated the discovery of effective operator, selector combinations across diverse problem domains. More importantly, the contribution of this research extended beyond the use of the CUSTOMHyS framework itself. It provided a collection of algorithmic patterns and search behaviors that could guide other researchers in the design or selection of optimization algorithms. Implementations that reproduce the underlying intelligence of these operators, could be employed independently to address new scientific and engineering optimization challenges.

7.3 Limitations and Future Work

Despite the successful validation of the proposed AAD strategies across multiple engineering domains, several limitations and future research directions must be acknowledged. The hybrid HH approach, which integrates model-free and model-based principles, achieved strong performance improvements; however, the process remains computationally demanding. The repeated evaluation of candidate MHs and the

Table 7.1: Summary of customized MHs generated by the AAD for each application domain.

Application	SHs	Variation parameters
AVR with PID	h_p = Spiral Dynamic (h_{20} , see Table 3.3)	–
	h_s = Direct	
	h_p = Differential Mutation (h_2 , see Table 3.3)	rand-to-best-and-current
	h_s = Greedy	
	h_p = Constricted Swarm Dynamic (h_{23} , see Table 3.3)	Uniform distribution
AVR with FOPID	h_p = Inertial Swarm Dynamic (h_{184} , see Table 3.2)	pdf = Uniform
	h_s = Metropolis	
	h_p = Genetic Crossover (h_{60} , see Table 3.2)	crossover mechanism =
	h_s = Metropolis	Two-points; pairing scheme = Rank weighting
DC–DC Buck–Boost Converter (ASMC)	h_p = Inertial Swarm Dynamic (h_{190} , see Table 3.2)	pdf = Lévy
	h_s = Direct	
	h_p = Genetic Crossover (h_{104} , see Table 3.2)	crossover mechanism = Blend;
	h_s = Probabilistic	pairing scheme = Tournament
Melanoma Segmentation	h_p = Differential Mutation (h_2 , see Table 3.4)	/current-to-best/
	h_s = Greedy	
	h_p = Random Flight (h_7 , see Table 3.4)	pdf = Lévy
	h_s = Greedy	
Viscoelastic Characterization (MG-63 Cells, FOZ Model)	h_p = Constricted Swarm Dynamic (h_{26} , see Table 3.5)	pdf = Uniform
	h_s = Direct	
	h_p = Inertial Swarm Dynamic (h_{25} , see Table 3.5)	pdf = Uniform
	h_s = Greedy	
	h_p = Local Random Walk (h_{17} , see Table 3.5)	pdf = Gaussian
	h_s = Greedy	

multi-layered optimization required by the hybrid design contribute to a high computational cost. Future work should focus on reducing this overhead through techniques such as surrogate modeling, incremental evaluation, or adaptive sampling, while maintaining the exploratory capacity of the framework. An immediate research direction involves refining the hybrid strategy so that the model-free and model-based processes operate concurrently rather than sequentially at the end of the HH search. A promising alternative is to employ Genetic Programming to evolve both MH structures and their hyperparameters simultaneously, enabling continuous adaptation throughout the search process. Likewise, incorporating a multi-objective formulation at the high level could allow the AAD framework to optimize conflicting criteria, such as accuracy, convergence speed, and computational effort, within a unified search process. Another key line of development lies in the inclusion of Exploratory Landscape Analysis (ELA) features within the AAD process. Characterizing the problems through landscape descriptors would enable the HH to select or prioritize search operators according to problem structure and modality, enhancing its generalization capacity. This integration would also provide a data-driven foundation for analyzing which operator configurations are most effective for particular problem types. Finally, while the proposed AAD framework demonstrated consistent results in both electrical and bioengineering domains, broader validation under diverse conditions, such as high dimensionality, noise, or constraint-rich problems, remains necessary. Addressing these limitations will help consolidate the AAD methodology as a computationally efficient

and general-purpose approach for the automated design of MHs, strengthening its potential as a reliable tool for solving complex real-world optimization problems.

7.4 Prospectives

The advances presented in this dissertation open several promising directions for the evolution of AAD and HH. The next generation of AAD frameworks should move toward systems capable of reasoning not only about algorithmic performance but also about the trade-offs among multiple optimization criteria. In this regard, future research may incorporate multi-objective high-level controllers that balance convergence speed, accuracy, interpretability, and computational cost simultaneously. Such a development would allow HHs to dynamically adapt their decision policies according to the priorities or constraints imposed by each application domain.

Another important line of progress lies in the convergence between AAD and the recent advances in large-scale artificial intelligence models. The incorporation of Large Language Models (LLMs) into the AAD process offers a unique opportunity to guide or accelerate the generation of algorithmic components. Through prompt-based reasoning and symbolic representation, LLMs could assist in exploring new operator formulations derived from existing families, ensuring diversity without compromising mathematical consistency or the underlying optimization theory. This synergy between statistical learning and formal algorithmic design could lead to semi-autonomous systems capable of discovering new search mechanisms grounded in theoretical principles rather than empirical trial.

Equally relevant is the possibility of achieving a more profound integration between the model-free and model-based paradigms that underpin the current hybrid framework. Instead of alternating between exploratory and parametric stages, future AAD implementations may benefit from co-evolutionary strategies in which structural composition and parameter tuning evolve concurrently. This would enable a continuous exchange of information between the stochastic and analytical components, strengthening both adaptability and interpretability.

In a broader perspective, the field of AAD is progressively moving from algorithm selection toward algorithm synthesis, where optimizers are not predefined entities but evolving constructs shaped by data, context, and user-defined goals. Within this transition, the integration of multi-objective reasoning, machine intelligence, and hybrid modeling stands as the next milestone for building transparent, efficient, and self-improving optimization systems. By maintaining the balance between mathematical rigor and computational innovation, future research can transform AAD from a design methodology into an autonomous scientific instrument for exploring the space of algorithms itself.

Bibliography

- [1] Stephen Cook. The p versus np problem. *Clay Mathematics Institute*, 2(6):3, 2000.
- [2] Naum Zuselevich Shor. *Minimization methods for non-differentiable functions*, volume 3. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [3] Julio Barrera and Carlos A Coello Coello. A review of particle swarm optimization methods used for multimodal optimization. *Innovations in swarm intelligence*, pages 9–37, 2009.
- [4] Sachin Desale, Akhtar Rasool, Sushil Andhale, and Priti Rane. Heuristic and meta-heuristic algorithms and their relevance to the real world: a survey. *Int. J. Comput. Eng. Res. Trends*, 351(5):2349–7084, 2015.
- [5] Laith Abualigah, Mohamed Abd Elaziz, Ahmad M Khasawneh, Mohammad Alshinwan, Rehab Ali Ibrahim, Mohammed AA Al-Qaness, Seyedali Mirjalili, Putra Sumari, and Amir H Gandomi. Meta-heuristic optimization algorithms for solving real-world mechanical engineering design problems: a comprehensive survey, applications, comparative analysis, and results. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 34(6):4081–4110, 2022.
- [6] Jorge Cruz-Duarte, José Ortiz-Bayliss, Iván Amaya, Yong Shi, Hugo Terashima-Marín, and Nelishia Pillay. Towards a Generalised Metaheuristic Model for Continuous Optimisation Problems. *Mathematics*, 8(11):2046, nov 2020. ISSN 2227-7390. doi: 10.3390/math8112046.
- [7] Jorge Cruz-Duarte, Ivan Amaya, José Ortiz-Bayliss, Santiago Conant-Pablos, Hugo Terashima-Marín, and Yong Shi. Hyper-heuristics to customise metaheuristics for continuous optimisation. *Swarm Evol. Comput.*, 66:100935, 2021. ISSN 2210-6502. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2021.100935>.
- [8] El-Ghazali Talbi. *Metaheuristics: from design to implementation*. John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [9] Alain Hertz, Eric Taillard, and Dominique De Werra. A tutorial on tabu search. In *Proc. of Giornate di Lavoro AIRO*, volume 95, pages 13–24, 1995.
- [10] DE Goldberg and JH Holland. Genetic algorithms and machine learning. *Machine learning*, 3(2-3):95–99, 1988. doi: 10.1023/A:1022602019183.

- [11] J Kennedy and R Eberhart. Particle swarm optimization (PSO). In *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Neural Netw.*, pages 1942–1948, 1995. doi: 10.1109/ICNN.1995.488968.
- [12] Marco Dorigo, Mauro Birattari, and Thomas Stützle. Ant colony optimization. *IEEE computational intelligence magazine*, 1(4):28–39, 2007.
- [13] Scott Kirkpatrick, C. D. Gelatt Jr., and M. P. Vecchi. Optimization by Simulated Annealing. *Science*, 220(4598):671–680, 1983.
- [14] Kenneth Sörensen. Metaheuristics—the metaphor exposed. *International Transactions in Operational Research*, 22(1):3–18, 2015. doi: 10.1111/itor.12001.
- [15] Adam P Piotrowski, Jaroslaw J Napiorkowski, and Pawel M Rowinski. How novel is the “novel” black hole optimization approach? *Information Sciences*, 267:191–200, 2014.
- [16] Alexandros Tzanetos and Georgios Dounias. Nature inspired optimization algorithms or simply variations of metaheuristics? *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 54:1841–1862, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-020-09893-8>.
- [17] Jesica de Armas, Eduardo Lalla-Ruiz, Surafel Lulseged Tilahun, and Stefan Voß. Similarity in metaheuristics: a gentle step towards a comparison methodology. *Natural Computing*, 21(2):265–287, 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11047-020-09837-9>.
- [18] Felipe Campelo and Claus Aranha. Sharks, zombies and volleyball: Lessons from the evolutionary computation bestiary. In *LIFELIKE Computing Systems Workshop 2021*, pages 1–6. CEUR-WS.org, 2021. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/artl_a_00402.
- [19] Christian Leonardo Camacho-Villalón, Marco Dorigo, and Thomas Stützle. The intelligent water drops algorithm: why it cannot be considered a novel algorithm: A brief discussion on the use of metaphors in optimization. *Swarm Intelligence*, 13(3): 173–192, 2019.
- [20] Christian L Camacho-Villalón, Thomas Stützle, and Marco Dorigo. Designing new metaheuristics: manual versus automatic approaches. *Intelligent Computing*, 2:0048, 2023.
- [21] David Wolpert and William Macready. No free lunch theorems for optimization. *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.*, 1(1):67–82, 1997.
- [22] Peter Merz. Advanced fitness landscape analysis and the performance of memetic algorithms. *Evolutionary Computation*, 12(3):303–325, 2004.
- [23] Leonardo CT Bezerra, Manuel López-Ibáñez, and Thomas Stützle. Automatic component-wise design of multiobjective evolutionary algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 20(3):403–417, 2015. doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2015.2474158.
- [24] Thomas Stützle and Manuel López-Ibáñez. Automated design of metaheuristic algorithms. In *Handbook of metaheuristics*, pages 541–579. Springer, 2019. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-91086-4_17.

- [25] Wenjie Yi, Rong Qu, Licheng Jiao, and Ben Niu. Automated design of metaheuristics using reinforcement learning within a novel general search framework. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 2022. doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2022.3197298.
- [26] Qi Zhao, Bai Yan, Taiwei Hu, Xianglong Chen, Jian Yang, Shi Cheng, and Yuhui Shi. Autoopt: A general framework for automatically designing metaheuristic optimization algorithms with diverse structures. *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence*, 2025.
- [27] Agoston E Eiben and James E Smith. *Introduction to evolutionary computing*. Springer, 2015.
- [28] Manuel López-Ibáñez, Jérémie Dubois-Lacoste, Leslie Pérez Cáceres, Mauro Birattari, and Thomas Stützle. The irace package: Iterated racing for automatic algorithm configuration. *Operations Research Perspectives*, 3:43–58, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orp.2016.09.002>.
- [29] Rong Qu, Graham Kendall, and Nelishia Pillay. The general combinatorial optimisation problem: Towards automated algorithm design. *IEEE Comput. Intell. Mag.*, 15(2): 14–23, 2020. doi: 10.1109/MCI.2020.2976182.
- [30] Jorge Cruz-Duarte, José Ortiz-Bayliss, Ivan Amaya, and Nelishia Pillay. Global optimisation through hyper-heuristics: Unfolding population-based metaheuristics. *Applied Sciences*, 11(12):5620, jun 2021. doi: 10.3390/app11125620.
- [31] Helena Stegherr, Michael Heider, Leopold Luley, and Jörg Hähner. Design of large-scale metaheuristic component studies. In *Proc. Gen. Evol. Comp. Conf. Comp. (GECCO)*, pages 1217–1226, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3449726.3463168>.
- [32] Edmund K Burke, Matthew R Hyde, Graham Kendall, Gabriela Ochoa, Ender Özcan, and John R Woodward. A classification of hyper-heuristic approaches: revisited. *Handbook of metaheuristics*, pages 453–477, 2019. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-91086-4_14.
- [33] Jerry Swan, Patrick De Causmaecker, Simon Martin, and Ender Özcan. A re-characterization of hyper-heuristics. In *Recent developments in metaheuristics*, pages 75–89. Springer, 2017.
- [34] Nelishia Pillay and Rong Qu. Assessing hyper-heuristic performance. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 72(11):2503–2516, 2021.
- [35] Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, Ivan Amaya, José C Ortiz-Bayliss, Hugo Terashima-Marín, and Yong Shi. Customhys: customising optimisation metaheuristics via hyper-heuristic search. *SoftwareX*, 12:100628, 2020.
- [36] Pascal Kerschke, Holger H Hoos, Frank Neumann, and Heike Trautmann. Automated algorithm selection: Survey and perspectives. *Evolutionary computation*, 27(1):3–45, 2019.
- [37] Sara Tari, Holger Hoos, Julie Jacques, Marie-Eléonore Kessaci, and Laetitia Jourdan. Automatic configuration of a multi-objective local search for imbalanced classification.

In *International Conference on Parallel Problem Solving from Nature*, pages 65–77. Springer, 2020.

- [38] Niki van Stein and Thomas Bäck. Llamea: A large language model evolutionary algorithm for automatically generating metaheuristics. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 2024.
- [39] Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, Ivan Amaya, José Carlos Ortiz-Bayliss, and Nelishia Pillay. Automated design of unfolded metaheuristics and the effect of population size. In *2021 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, pages 1155–1162. IEEE, 2021.
- [40] Jose M Tapia-Avitia, Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, Ivan Amaya, Jose Carlos Ortiz-Bayliss, Hugo Terashima-Marin, and Nelishia Pillay. A Primary Study on Hyper-Heuristics Powered by Artificial Neural Networks for Customising Population-based Metaheuristics in Continuous Optimisation Problems. In *2022 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, pages 1–8. IEEE, 2022. doi: 10.1109/CEC55065.2022.9870275.
- [41] José M Tapia-Avitia, Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, Ivan Amaya, Jose Carlos Ortiz-Bayliss, Hugo Terashima-Marin, and Nelishia Pillay. Analysing hyper-heuristics based on neural networks for the automatic design of population-based metaheuristics in continuous optimisation problems. *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, 89:101616, 2024.
- [42] Panos Y Papalambros. The optimization paradigm in engineering design: promises and challenges. *Computer-Aided Design*, 34(12):939–951, 2002.
- [43] Chrysanthos Maraveas, Panagiotis G Asteris, Konstantinos G Arvanitis, Thomas Bartzanas, and Dimitrios Loukatos. Application of bio and nature-inspired algorithms in agricultural engineering. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 30(3): 1979–2012, 2023.
- [44] Dario Floreano and Claudio Mattiussi. *Bio-inspired artificial intelligence: theories, methods, and technologies*. MIT press, 2008.
- [45] Singiresu S Rao. *Engineering optimization: theory and practice*. John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [46] Daniel F. Zambrano-Gutierrez, Jorge M. Cruz-Duarte, Juan Gabriel Avina-Cervantes, José Carlos Ortiz-Bayliss, Jesús Joaquín Yanez-Borjas, and Iván Amaya. Automatic Design of Metaheuristics for Practical Engineering Applications. *IEEE Access*, 11: 7262–7276, 2023. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3236836.
- [47] John H. Drake, Ahmed Kheiri, Ender Özcan, and Edmund K. Burke. Recent advances in selection hyper-heuristics. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, 285(2):405–428, 2020. ISSN 03772217. doi: 10.1016/j.ejor.2019.07.073.
- [48] Kashif Hussain, Mohd Najib Mohd Salleh, Shi Cheng, and Yuhui Shi. Metaheuristic research: a comprehensive survey. *Artif. Intell. Rev.*, 52(4):2191–2233, 2019.

- [49] Abdulaziz Alorf. A survey of recently developed metaheuristics and their comparative analysis. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 117:105622, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.105622>.
- [50] Thomas A Feo and Mauricio GC Resende. Greedy randomized adaptive search procedures. *Journal of global optimization*, 6(2):109–133, 1995.
- [51] Alberto Franzin and Thomas Stützle. Revisiting simulated annealing: A component-based analysis. *Computers and Operations Research*, 104:191–206, 2019. ISSN 03050548. doi: 10.1016/j.cor.2018.12.015.
- [52] Mark Hauschild and Martin Pelikan. An introduction and survey of estimation of distribution algorithms. *Swarm and evolutionary computation*, 1(3):111–128, 2011.
- [53] Mandavilli Srinivas and Lalit M Patnaik. Genetic algorithms: A survey. *computer*, 27(6):17–26, 1994. doi: 10.1109/2.294849.
- [54] Kenneth V Price. Differential evolution. In *Handbook of optimization: From classical to modern approach*, pages 187–214. Springer, 2013.
- [55] Helena Ramalhinho Lourenço, Olivier C Martin, and Thomas Stützle. Iterated local search: Framework and applications. In *Handbook of metaheuristics*, pages 129–168. Springer, 2018.
- [56] Dervis Karaboga, Beyza Gorkemli, Celal Ozturk, and Nurhan Karaboga. A comprehensive survey: artificial bee colony (abc) algorithm and applications. *Artif. Intell. Rev.*, 42(1):21–57, 2014.
- [57] Christian Igel, Nikolaus Hansen, and Stefan Roth. Covariance matrix adaptation for multi-objective optimization. *Evolutionary computation*, 15(1):1–28, 2007.
- [58] Pierre Hansen, Nenad Mladenović, Jack Brimberg, and José A Moreno Pérez. Variable neighborhood search. In *Handbook of metaheuristics*, pages 57–97. Springer, 2018.
- [59] Peter Cowling, Graham Kendall, and Eric Soubeiga. A hyperheuristic approach to scheduling a sales summit. In *International conference on the practice and theory of automated timetabling*, pages 176–190. Springer, 2000.
- [60] Nelishia Pillay and Rong Qu. *Hyper-Heuristics: Theory and Applications*. Springer, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96514-7>.
- [61] Edmund K Burke, Michel Gendreau, Matthew Hyde, Graham Kendall, Gabriela Ochoa, Ender Özcan, and Rong Qu. Hyper-heuristics: A survey of the state of the art. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 64:1695–1724, 2013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1057/jors.2013.71>.
- [62] Yuchang Zhang, Ruibin Bai, Rong Qu, Chaofan Tu, and Jiahuan Jin. A deep reinforcement learning based hyper-heuristic for combinatorial optimisation with uncertainties. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 300(2):418–427, 2022.
- [63] Edmund K Burke, Mathew R Hyde, Graham Kendall, Gabriela Ochoa, Ender Ozcan, and John R Woodward. Exploring hyper-heuristic methodologies with genetic

- programming. In *Computational intelligence: Collaboration, fusion and emergence*, pages 177–201. Springer, 2009.
- [64] James Bergstra and Yoshua Bengio. Random search for hyper-parameter optimization. *Journal of machine learning research*, 13(Feb):281–305, 2012.
- [65] Scott Kirkpatrick, C Daniel Gelatt Jr, and Mario P Vecchi. Optimization by simulated annealing. *science*, 220(4598):671–680, 1983. doi: DOI:10.1126/science.220.4598.671.
- [66] Xin-She Yang and Suash Deb. Cuckoo search via Lévy flights. In *2009 World Congress on Nature & Biologically Inspired Computing (NaBIC)*, pages 210–214. IEEE, 2009.
- [67] Gilbert Syswerda et al. Uniform crossover in genetic algorithms. In *ICGA*, volume 3, 1989.
- [68] Swagatam Das, Sankha Subhra Mullick, and Ponnuthurai N Suganthan. Recent advances in differential evolution—an updated survey. *Swarm and evolutionary computation*, 27:1–30, 2016.
- [69] Maurice Clerc and James Kennedy. The particle swarm-explosion, stability, and convergence in a multidimensional complex space. *Evolutionary Computation, IEEE Transactions on*, 6(1):58–73, 2002.
- [70] Xin-She Yang. *Nature-inspired metaheuristic algorithms*. Luniver press, 2010.
- [71] Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, Ignacio Martin-Diaz, JU Munoz-Minjares, Luis A Sanchez-Galindo, Juan G Avina-Cervantes, Arturo Garcia-Perez, and C Rodrigo Correa-Cely. Primary study on the stochastic spiral optimization algorithm. In *2017 IEEE international autumn meeting on power, electronics and computing (ROPEC)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2017.
- [72] Richard A Formato. Central force optimization: a new deterministic gradient-like optimization metaheuristic. *Opsearch*, 46(1):25–51, 2009.
- [73] Anupam Biswas, KK Mishra, Shailesh Tiwari, and AK Misra. Physics-inspired optimization algorithms: a survey. *Journal of Optimization*, 2013(1):438152, 2013.
- [74] Matej Črepinšek, Shih-Hsi Liu, and Marjan Mernik. Exploration and exploitation in evolutionary algorithms: A survey. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, 45(3):1–33, 2013.
- [75] Kashif Hussain, Mohd Najib Mohd Salleh, Shi Cheng, and Yuhui Shi. On the exploration and exploitation in popular swarm-based metaheuristic algorithms. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 31(11):7665–7683, 2019.
- [76] Bernardo Morales-Castañeda, Daniel Zaldivar, Erik Cuevas, Fernando Fausto, and Alma Rodríguez. A better balance in metaheuristic algorithms: Does it exist? *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, 54:100671, 2020.
- [77] Kenichi Tamura and Keiichiro Yasuda. Spiral dynamics inspired optimization. *Journal of Advanced Computational Intelligence and Intelligent Informatics*, 15(8):1116–1122, 2011.

- [78] Valentín Osuna-Enciso, Erik Cuevas, and Bernardo Morales Castañeda. A diversity metric for population-based metaheuristic algorithms. *Information Sciences*, 586: 192–208, 2022.
- [79] Qi Zhao, Qiqi Duan, Bai Yan, Shi Cheng, and Yuhui Shi. Automated design of metaheuristic algorithms: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.06532*, 2023.
- [80] Manuel Lopez-Ibanez and Thomas Stutzle. The automatic design of multiobjective ant colony optimization algorithms. *IEEE transactions on evolutionary computation*, 16(6):861–875, 2012.
- [81] John R Koza. Genetic programming as a means for programming computers by natural selection. *Statistics and computing*, 4(2):87–112, 1994.
- [82] Rahul Kapoor and Nelishia Pillay. A genetic programming approach to the automated design of cnn models for image classification and video shorts creation. *Genetic Programming and Evolvable Machines*, 25(1):10, 2024.
- [83] Brian W Goldman and Daniel R Tauritz. Self-configuring crossover. In *Proceedings of the 13th annual conference companion on Genetic and evolutionary computation*, pages 575–582, 2011.
- [84] Furong Ye, Carola Doerr, Hao Wang, and Thomas Bäck. Automated configuration of genetic algorithms by tuning for anytime performance. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 26(6):1526–1538, 2022.
- [85] Ahmed Hassan and Nelishia Pillay. Hybrid metaheuristics: An automated approach. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 130:132–144, 2019. ISSN 09574174. doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2019.04.027.
- [86] Nikolaus Hansen, Anne Auger, Dimo Brockhoff, and Tea Tušar. Anytime performance assessment in blackbox optimization benchmarking. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 26(6):1293–1305, 2022.
- [87] Manuel López-Ibáñez and Thomas Stützle. Automatically improving the anytime behaviour of optimisation algorithms. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 235(3):569–582, 2014.
- [88] Aymeric Blot, Alexis Pernet, Laetitia Jourdan, Marie-Éléonore Kessaci-Marmion, and Holger H Hoos. Automatically configuring multi-objective local search using multi-objective optimisation. In *International Conference on Evolutionary Multi-Criterion Optimization*, pages 61–76. Springer, 2017.
- [89] Priyanka Madanrao Patil and SK Patil. Automatic voltage regulator. In *2020 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Engineering (ic-ETITE)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2020.
- [90] Abul R Hasan, Thomas S Martis, and AHM Sadrul Ula. Design and implementation of a fuzzy controller based automatic voltage regulator for a synchronous generator. *IEEE Transactions on energy conversion*, 9(3):550–557, 1994.

- [91] Hirotaka Yoshida, Kenichi Kawata, Yoshikazu Fukuyama, Shinichi Takayama, and Yosuke Nakanishi. A particle swarm optimization for reactive power and voltage control considering voltage security assessment. *IEEE Transactions on power systems*, 15(4):1232–1239, 2000.
- [92] Ercan Köse. Optimal control of avr system with tree seed algorithm-based pid controller. *IEEE Access*, 8:89457–89467, 2020.
- [93] Serdar Ekinci and Baran Hekimoğlu. Improved kidney-inspired algorithm approach for tuning of pid controller in avr system. *IEEE Access*, 7:39935–39947, 2019.
- [94] Mouayad A Sahib and Bestoun S Ahmed. A new multiobjective performance criterion used in pid tuning optimization algorithms. *Journal of advanced research*, 7(1): 125–134, 2016.
- [95] Katsuhiko Ogata. *Modern Control Engineering*. Prentice Hall PTR, USA, 4th edition, 2001. ISBN 0130609072.
- [96] Igor Podlubny. *Fractional differential equations: an introduction to fractional derivatives, fractional differential equations, to methods of their solution and some of their applications*. Elsevier, 1998.
- [97] Concepción A Monje, YangQuan Chen, Blas M Vinagre, Dingyu Xue, and Vicente Feliu-Battle. *Fractional-order systems and controls: fundamentals and applications*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [98] Michele Caputo. Linear models of dissipation whose q is almost frequency independent—ii. *Geophysical Journal International*, 13(5):529–539, 1967.
- [99] Igor Podlubny. Fractional-order systems and fractional-order controllers. *Institute of Experimental Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Kosice*, 12(3):1–18, 1994.
- [100] Adeel Ahmad Jamil, Wen Fu Tu, Syed Wajhat Ali, Yacine Terriche, and Josep M Guerrero. Fractional-order pid controllers for temperature control: A review. *Energies*, 15(10):3800, 2022.
- [101] Daniel Fernando Zambrano-Gutierrez, Gerardo Humberto Valencia-Rivera, Juan Gabriel Avina-Cervantes, Ivan Amaya, and Jorge Mario Cruz-Duarte. Designing heuristic-based tuners for fractional-order pid controllers in automatic voltage regulator systems using a hyper-heuristic approach. *Fractal and Fractional*, 8(4):223, 2024.
- [102] Sara Hasanpour, Alfred Baghrmian, and Hamed Mojallali. Analysis and Modeling of a New Coupled-Inductor Buck–Boost DC–DC Converter for Renewable Energy Applications. *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, 35(8):8088–8101, 2020. doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2019.2962325.
- [103] Hyeon-Seok Lee and Jae-Jung Yun. High-efficiency bidirectional buck–boost converter for photovoltaic and energy storage systems in a smart grid. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 34(5):4316–4328, 2018.
- [104] Enrique Alvaro-Mendoza, Alejandro Gonzalez-Garcia, Herman Castañeda, and Jesús

- De León-Morales. Novel adaptive law for super-twisting controller: Usv tracking control under disturbances. *ISA transactions*, 139:561–573, 2023.
- [105] Daniel F Zambrano-Gutierrez, Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, Herman Castañeda, and Juan Gabriel Avina-Cervantes. Optimization of adaptive sliding mode controllers using customized metaheuristics in dc-dc buck-boost converters. *Mathematics*, 12(23):3709, 2024.
- [106] Haluk Gozde and M Cengiz Taplamacioglu. Comparative performance analysis of artificial bee colony algorithm for automatic voltage regulator (avr) system. *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, 348(8):1927–1946, 2011.
- [107] Afzal Sikander, Padmanabh Thakur, Ramesh C Bansal, and S Rajasekar. A novel technique to design cuckoo search based fopid controller for avr in power systems. *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 70:261–274, 2018.
- [108] Hadi Ramezani, Saeed Balochian, and Asef Zare. Design of optimal fractional-order pid controllers using particle swarm optimization algorithm for automatic voltage regulator (avr) system. *Journal of Control, Automation and Electrical Systems*, 24(5):601–611, 2013.
- [109] Mohd Zaidi Mohd Tumari, Mohd Ashraf Ahmad, Mohd Helmi Suid, and Mok Ren Hao. An improved marine predators algorithm-tuned fractional-order pid controller for automatic voltage regulator system. *Fractal and Fractional*, 7(7):561, 2023.
- [110] Rouani Lahcene, Sebbane Abdeldjalil, and Kheldoun Aissa. Optimal tuning of fractional order pid controller for avr system using simulated annealing optimization algorithm. In *2017 5th International Conference on Electrical Engineering - Boumerdes (ICEE-B)*, pages 1–6, 2017. doi: 10.1109/ICEE-B.2017.8192194.
- [111] Ryoji Tanabe and Alex S Fukunaga. Improving the search performance of shade using linear population size reduction. In *2014 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, pages 1658–1665. IEEE, 2014.
- [112] Subhodip Biswas, Debanjan Saha, Shuvodeep De, Adam D Cobb, Swagatam Das, and Brian A Jalaian. Improving differential evolution through bayesian hyperparameter optimization. In *2021 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, pages 832–840. IEEE, 2021.
- [113] Afshin Faramarzi, Mohammad Heidarinejad, Seyedali Mirjalili, and Amir H Gandomi. Marine predators algorithm: A nature-inspired metaheuristic. *Expert systems with applications*, 152:113377, 2020.
- [114] Haval Tariq Sadeeq and Adnan Mohsin Abdulazeez. Giant trevally optimizer (gto): A novel metaheuristic algorithm for global optimization and challenging engineering problems. *Ieee Access*, 10:121615–121640, 2022.
- [115] Nguyen Van Thieu and Seyedali Mirjalili. Mealpy: An open-source library for latest meta-heuristic algorithms in python. *Journal of Systems Architecture*, 139:102871, 2023.

- [116] José David Rojas, Orlando Arrieta, and Ramon Vilanova. *Industrial PID controller tuning*. Springer, 2021.
- [117] Ahmed M Nassef, Mohammad Ali Abdelkareem, Hussein M Maghrabie, and Ahmad Baroutaji. Metaheuristic-based algorithms for optimizing fractional-order controllers—a recent, systematic, and comprehensive review. *Fractal and Fractional*, 7(7):553, 2023.
- [118] Davut Izci, Serdar Ekinici, and Seyedali Mirjalili. Optimal pid plus second-order derivative controller design for avr system using a modified runge kutta optimizer and bode’s ideal reference model. *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, 11(3): 1247–1264, 2023.
- [119] Ahmed M Nassef, Mohammad Ali Abdelkareem, Hussein M Maghrabie, and Ahmad Baroutaji. Review of metaheuristic optimization algorithms for power systems problems. *Sustainability*, 15(12):9434, 2023.
- [120] Gerardo Humberto Valencia-Rivera, Maria Torcoroma Benavides-Robles, Alonso Vela Morales, Ivan Amaya, Jorge M Cruz-Duarte, José Carlos Ortiz-Bayliss, and Juan Gabriel Avina-Cervantes. A systematic review of metaheuristic algorithms in electric power systems optimization. *Applied Soft Computing*, 150:111047, 2024.
- [121] Ulrike Leiter, Ulrike Keim, and Claus Garbe. Epidemiology of skin cancer: update 2019. *Sunlight, vitamin D and skin cancer*, pages 123–139, 2020.
- [122] Navid Razmjoooy, Mohsen Ashourian, Maryam Karimifard, Vania V Estrela, Hermes J Loschi, Douglas Do Nascimento, Reinaldo P França, and Mikhail Vishnevski. Computer-aided diagnosis of skin cancer: a review. *Current medical imaging*, 16(7): 781–793, 2020.
- [123] Trisha Kaundinya, Roopal V Kundu, and Joe Feinglass. The epidemiology of skin cancer by uv index: Cross-sectional analysis from the 2019 behavioral risk factor surveillance survey. *Archives of Dermatological Research*, 315(3):613–615, 2023.
- [124] Adnan Abdulazeez et al. A review on utilizing machine learning classification algorithms for skin cancer. *Journal of Applied Science and Technology Trends*, 5(2): 60–71, 2024.
- [125] World Health Organization et al. The effect of occupational exposure to solar ultraviolet radiation on malignant skin melanoma and non-melanoma skin cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis from the who/ilo joint estimates of the work-related burden of disease and injury, 2021.
- [126] Diego Oliva, Mohamed Abd Elaziz, and Salvador Hinojosa. *Metaheuristic algorithms for image segmentation: theory and applications*. Springer, 2019.
- [127] Erick Rodríguez-Esparza, Laura A Zanella-Calzada, Daniel Zaldivar, and Carlos E Galván-Tejada. Automatic detection of malignant masses in digital mammograms based on a mcet-hho approach. *Applications of Hybrid Metaheuristic Algorithms for Image Processing*, pages 351–374, 2020.

- [128] Nobuyuki Otsu et al. A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms. *Automatica*, 11(285-296):23–27, 1975.
- [129] Mehmet Sezgin and Bulent Sankur. Survey over image thresholding techniques and quantitative performance evaluation. *Journal of Electronic imaging*, 13(1):146–168, 2004.
- [130] Ahmed S Abutaleb. Automatic thresholding of gray-level pictures using two-dimensional entropy. *Computer vision, graphics, and image processing*, 47(1): 22–32, 1989.
- [131] Prasanna K Sahoo and Gurdial Arora. A thresholding method based on two-dimensional renyi’s entropy. *Pattern Recognition*, 37(6):1149–1161, 2004.
- [132] Andrea H del Río, Itzel Aranguren, Diego Oliva, Mohamed Abd Elaziz, and Erik Cuevas. Efficient image segmentation through 2d histograms and an improved owl search algorithm. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 12(1): 131–150, 2021.
- [133] Himanshu Mittal and Mukesh Saraswat. An optimum multi-level image thresholding segmentation using non-local means 2d histogram and exponential kbest gravitational search algorithm. *Engineering applications of artificial intelligence*, 71:226–235, 2018.
- [134] MSR Naidu, P Rajesh Kumar, and K Chiranjeevi. Shannon and fuzzy entropy based evolutionary image thresholding for image segmentation. *Alexandria engineering journal*, 57(3):1643–1655, 2018.
- [135] Vijay P Singh, Bellie Sivakumar, and Huijuan Cui. Tsallis entropy theory for modeling in water engineering: A review. *Entropy*, 19(12):641, 2017.
- [136] PA Bromiley, NA Thacker, and E Bouhova-Thacker. Shannon entropy, renyi entropy, and information. *Statistics and Inf. Series (2004-004)*, 9(2004):2–8, 2004.
- [137] N Sri Madhava Raja, Steven Lawrence Fernandes, Nilanjan Dey, Suresh Chandra Satapathy, and V Rajinikanth. Contrast enhanced medical mri evaluation using tsallis entropy and region growing segmentation. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 15(1):961–972, 2024.
- [138] Ling Peng and Dongbo Zhang. An adaptive lévy flight firefly algorithm for multilevel image thresholding based on rényi entropy. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 78(5): 6875–6896, 2022.
- [139] Ahmed Elaraby, Abdulaziz AlMohimeed, and Redhwan MA Saad. An enhanced ct liver segmentation framework using differential evolution-optimized rényi entropy. *Traitement du Signal*, 41(2):1035, 2024.
- [140] Daniel F Zambrano-Gutierrez, Jorge Ramos-Frutos, Oscar Ramos-Soto, Juan Gabriel Avina-Cervantes, Diego Oliva, and Jorge M Cruz-Duarte. Automated tailoring of heuristic-based renyi’s entropy maximizers for efficient melanoma segmentation. In *2025 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Image, Signal Processing and Synthetic Media (CISM)*, pages 1–7. IEEE, 2025.

- [141] Itzel Aranguren, Arturo Valdivia, Marco Pérez-Cisneros, Diego Oliva, and Valentín Osuna-Enciso. Digital image thresholding by using a lateral inhibition 2d histogram and a mutated electromagnetic field optimization. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 81(7):10023–10049, 2022.
- [142] Noel Codella, Veronica Rotemberg, Philipp Tschandl, M Emre Celebi, Stephen Dusza, David Gutman, Brian Helba, Aadi Kalloo, Konstantinos Liopyris, Michael Marchetti, et al. Skin lesion analysis toward melanoma detection 2018: A challenge hosted by the international skin imaging collaboration (isic). *arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.03368*, 2019.
- [143] Oscar Ramos-Soto, Angel Casas-Ordaz, Diego Oliva, Sandra E Balderas-Mata, and Saúl Zapotecas-Martínez. Enhancing retinal oct scans via metaheuristic-driven bayesian speckle denoising. In *2024 IEEE 37th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)*, pages 332–337. IEEE, 2024.
- [144] Karel Zuiderveld. *Contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization*, pages 474–485. Academic Press, Inc., 1994.
- [145] John S Bertram. The molecular biology of cancer. *Molecular aspects of medicine*, 21(6):167–223, 2000.
- [146] Yongfang Xie, Mingling Wang, Min Cheng, Zhiqin Gao, and Guohui Wang. The viscoelastic behaviors of several kinds of cancer cells and normal cells. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials*, 91:54–58, 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2018.11.029>.
- [147] Gaël Runel, Noémie Lopez-Ramirez, Julien Chlasta, and Ingrid Masse. Biomechanical properties of cancer cells. *Cells*, 10(4):887, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells10040887>.
- [148] Mar Eroles and Felix Rico. Advances in mechanical biomarkers. *JOURNAL OF MOLECULAR RECOGNITION*, 36(8), AUG 2023. ISSN 0952-3499. doi: 10.1002/jmr.3022.
- [149] Yuri M Efremov, Takaharu Okajima, and Arvind Raman. Measuring viscoelasticity of soft biological samples using atomic force microscopy. *Soft matter*, 16(1):64–81, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9sm01020c>.
- [150] Sarah E. Cross, Yu-Sheng Jin, Jianyu Rao, and James K. Gimzewski. Nanomechanical analysis of cells from cancer patients. *NATURE NANOTECHNOLOGY*, 2(12): 780–783, DEC 2007. ISSN 1748-3387. doi: 10.1038/nnano.2007.388.
- [151] Malgorzata Lekka, Katarzyna Pogoda, Justyna Gostek, Olesya Klymenko, Szymon Prauzner-Bechcicki, Joanna Wiltowska-Zuber, Justyna Jaczewska, Janusz Lekki, and Zbigniew Stachura. Cancer cell recognition - mechanical phenotype. *MICRON*, 43(12, SI):1259–1266, DEC 2012. ISSN 0968-4328. doi: 10.1016/j.micron.2012.01.019.
- [152] Alessandra Bonfanti, Jonathan Louis Kaplan, Guillaume Charras, and Alexandre

- Kabla. Fractional viscoelastic models for power-law materials. *Soft matter*, 16(26): 6002–6020, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0sm00354a>.
- [153] Anh Vo and Andrew Ekpenyong. Fractional calculus modeling of cell viscoelasticity quantifies drug response and maturation more robustly than integer order models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.02589*, 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.02589>.
- [154] Maricela Rodríguez-Nieto, Priscila Mendoza-Flores, David García-Ortiz, Luis M Montes-de Oca, Marco Mendoza-Villa, Porfiria Barrón-González, Gabriel Espinosa, and Jorge Luis Menchaca. Viscoelastic properties of doxorubicin-treated ht-29 cancer cells by atomic force microscopy: The fractional zener model as an optimal viscoelastic model for cells. *Biomechanics and modeling in mechanobiology*, 19:801–813, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10237-019-01248-9>.
- [155] David Roylance. Engineering viscoelasticity. *Department of Materials Science and Engineering—Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge MA*, 2139:1–37, 2001. doi: https://doi.org/10.1142/9789812386458_0015.
- [156] Richard M Christensen. *Theory of viscoelasticity*. Courier Corporation, 2013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-174252-2.x5001-7>.
- [157] Lizeth Ovalle-Flores, Maricela Rodríguez-Nieto, Diana Zárate-Triviño, Cristina Rodríguez-Padilla, and Jorge Luis Menchaca. Methodologies and models for measuring viscoelastic properties of cancer cells: Towards a universal classification. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials*, 140:105734, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2023.105734>.
- [158] B Carmichael, H Babahosseini, SN Mahmoodi, and M Agah. The fractional viscoelastic response of human breast tissue cells. *Physical biology*, 12(4):046001, 2015. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1478-3975/12/4/046001>.
- [159] Will Zhang, Adela Capilnasiu, and David Nordsletten. Comparative analysis of nonlinear viscoelastic models across common biomechanical experiments. *Journal of Elasticity*, 145(1):117–152, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10659-021-09827-7>.
- [160] David C Lin, Emilios K Dimitriadis, and Ferenc Horkay. Robust strategies for automated AFM force curve analysis—I. non-adhesive indentation of soft, inhomogeneous materials. *J. Biomech. Eng.*, 129(6):430–440, 2007. ISSN 0148-0731. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2720924>.
- [161] Takuya Akiba, Shotaro Sano, Toshihiko Yanase, Takeru Ohta, and Masanori Koyama. Optuna: A next-generation hyperparameter optimization framework. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery & data mining*, pages 2623–2631, 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3292500.3330701>.
- [162] Nor Azlina Ab Aziz, Zuwairie Ibrahim, Marizan Mubin, and Shahdan Sudin. Adaptive switching gravitational search algorithm: an attempt to improve diversity of gravitational search algorithm through its iteration strategy. *Sādhanā*, 42(7): 1103–1121, 2017. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12046-017-0674-0>.